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Algorithm Implementation of Genetic Association Analysis for Rheumatoid Arthritis Data Based on Haplotype Blocks

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Abstract of The Dissertation

The human genome in nature is divided into overlapping blocks. Recently, many genome-wide association studies (GWAS) depend on haplotype blocks rather than individual single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) because they are more powerful in association analysis. Haplotype blocks provide insights into genome structure, function, evolution, and further genomic analysis. Inferred haplotype blocks vary in length and location according to many factors such as the partitioning method, population, and biomarker checks. Dealing with a genome-wide genotype dataset is considered a challenge because of its massive size and its complexity. Several algorithms have been proposed for partitioning haplotype blocks. Most existing algorithms divide genotype data into small blocks and ignore low linkage disequilibrium (LD) regions between strong related SNPs. Other methods produce redundant blocks by identifying LD blocks if all inside SNPs are associated with the block's start and end SNPs. The best applicable haplotype partition method is still a controversial issue. This thesis's primary goal is to provide a profound, clear, and more tangible understanding of haplotype blocks' pattern on a case-control dataset from the North American Rheumatoid Arthritis Consortium (NARAC). We also aimed to apply the most recent and current haplotype block partitioning methods to the NARAC dataset to evaluate each method's results. Furthermore, we aimed to find the minor allele frequency (MAF) role in the partitioning process.

This study first provides a deep description, analysis, and visualization for the NARAC genotypic dataset. We have described the data in general by presenting the number of females and males in both cases and controls and the percentage of missing data. We have counted the numbers of alleles and genotypes and calculated the MAF for each SNP. According to the SNP MAF, we have divided the data into four categories: very rare SNPs, rare SNPs, low-frequency SNPs, and common SNPs. Then, we investigated the region of these SNPs in the chromosome to find the percentage of SNPs in the coding locations and other regions. We have found that each category has a different proportion in each region of consequence annotation. The overall descriptive tables are done first for each chromosome and then for the whole data. This analysis focuses on the autosomal chromosomes. The results could provide clear insight into the manner of the data and its MAF, which can be compared with other datasets. The descriptive analysis findings could help the researchers overview the data and provide an accurate and deep intuitive understanding of such case-control data.

Incontrovertibly, the pre-processing phase is a crucial step to prepare any data for profound considerable analysis. As genome-wide data is considered big data, dealing with such data is not an easy task and still poses a significant challenge. We have illustrated the main pre-processing steps on NARAC data for preparing it for haplotype block partitioning using the different methods and with different platforms. We have summarized the steps of pre-processing the raw genotyped dataset to prepare it for haplotype block partitioning and further analyses. Besides, we present each practical step by clear tables for better visualizing, elucidation, and workflow interpretation. We aimed to overcome the missing data and reform the output in a standardized format. The pre-processing steps improve the understanding of such data formats and build the foundation stone of critical genome-wide experiments and studies. Thus, this work hopes to illuminate the roads for other researchers who use similar data. The pre-processed data will be applied to imputation, BigLD block partitioning under R and Haploview methods. Our sequence of pre-processing steps includes preparing the characters to be in a form that is suitable for imputation. The next step is recording data in 0,1,2 format to be proper for the BigLD. We then have prepared data for Haploview to provide clear haplotype block partitioning, association analysis, and furthermore.

In order to choose the practical haplotype block partitioning method, we have reviewed all the previous methods and the leading genetic projects that aimed to identify the human variations. Then we conducted an experimental comparative study on the most current and common haplotype block partitioning methods as the following: the BigLD in R programming language, the confidence interval test (CIT), four-gamete test (FGT), and solid spine of linkage disequilibrium (SSLD), the last three methods are done under Haploview platform. The methods produce different outcomes, so we have standardized the results and evaluated them with ten different parameters.

One of the most powerful methods to minimize errors in large genotyped datasets is by dropping the site where the MAF less than the specified threshold. Discarding the MAF immensely affects the SNP density, which accordingly affects the haplotype block partitioning results. There is little evidence of MAF's influence on haplotype blocks, making it difficult for the researcher to decide which MAF value should be applied. This study moreover intended to find the effect of the MAF threshold in the given genome-wide dataset. We have investigated the MAF threshold's role in haplotype partitioning by applying the four proposed methods with five different MAF thresholds. The analysis has been done over the whole

autosomes from chromosome 1 to chromosome 22. The five values of MAF are 0.001, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05 and 0.1. As the five MAF thresholds have been examined over the four different haplotype block partitioning methods over the 22 chromosomes, this results in 440 outputs. We have evaluated the results by calculating various evaluation parameters. Additionally, we have measured the computational time of the BigLD and Haploview method.

The results provide important insight into the impact of MAF over methods. The correlation of SNPs within blocks tends to be more rigorous when higher MAF cutoffs are applied. This study proposes that this behavior is that many sites should not consider an SNP and could be caused by random mutation. MAF remarkably affects SNP density, the number of haplotype blocks, mean block length, and mean r^2 within the block. The important conclusion drawn from all the results is that MAF should be considered carefully depending on the haplotype block partitioning method.

Dedication

I am dedicated to my beloved parents, whose words of encouragement ring in my ears. I also dedicate this dissertation to my sisters and brothers, who have never left my side and are very special. My sincere, grateful feeling is to my family and relatives for being there for me throughout the journey. I will always appreciate all they have done.

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List of Publications

This dissertation is composed of a summary and the following original publications, reproduced here by permission.

- I. F. S. Ibrahim, M. N. Saad, A. M. Said, and H. F. A. Hamed, "Haplotype Block Partitioning for NARAC Dataset Using Interval Graph Modeling of Clusters Algorithm," *2018 9th Cairo International Biomedical Engineering Conference (CIBEC)*, Cairo, Egypt, 2018, pp. 134-137.
DOI: 10.1109/CIBEC.2018.8641758

- II. Pre-processing Steps for Genome-wide High-density NARAC Dataset Facilitates its Haplotype Block Partitioning, *Journal of Advanced Engineering Trends (JAET)*, July 2021,40(2), pp. 61-69

- III. F. S. Ibrahim, M. N. Saad, A. M. Said, and H. F. A. Hamed, "Exploratory Genome-wide Analysis for NARAC Dataset with Preparation for Haplotype Block Partitioning Application through Minor Allele Frequency Quality Control Viewpoint." *Genomics & Bioinformatics. (Ready for submission)*

- IV. F. S. Ibrahim, M. N. Saad, A. M. Said, and H. F. A. Hamed, "A revolution in Genetic projects and Haplotype Block Partitioning Methods: Review paper," *World Journal of Medical Genetics (Ready for submission)*

- V. F. S. Ibrahim, M. N. Saad, A. M. Said, and H. F. A. Hamed, "Influence of Minor Allele Frequency on Haplotype Block Partitioning." *Biocybernetics and Biomedical Engineering. (Under preparation)*

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List of Abbreviations and Symbols

SNP	Single nucleotide polymorphism
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
A	Adenine
C	Cytosine
G	Guanine
T	Thymine
GWAS	Genome-wide association study
BP	Base pair
MAF	Minor allele frequency
LD	Linkage disequilibrium
D	deviation
D'	Normalized deviation
r^2	Correlation coefficient
HWE	Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium
HGP	Human genome project
RA	Rheumatoid arthritis
NARAC	North American Rheumatoid Arthritis Consortium
1KGP	1000 Genomes Project
rsID	Reference SNP identification

Chapter 1

Introduction, background, and preliminary

1.1. Introduction and overview

Although there are numerous probable causes of human diseases, the genetic factor is often one of the most influential risk factors for common complex disease. Genetics is often strongly associated with autoimmune disorders, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, psychiatric illnesses, and even infectious diseases. Understanding the human genetic differences and their relationship with the diseases has tremendous practical implications in disease prediction, diagnosis, and treatment. Identifying the regions associated with and contribute to complex diseases continues to be a hard job and a difficult challenge. Most diseases are also influenced by varying degrees of environmental factors. So, this makes identifying the disease-associated regions quite harder. Generally, there are many genetic identifiers; the most common one is the single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP). Lately, researchers tend to adopt regional-based and haplotype block-based association approaches to select the genetic biomarker. This dissertation aims to analyze population-based SNP arrays from rheumatoid arthritis (RA) dataset to partition its haplotype blocks. We explore, describe, and explicate the patterns of the data. Also, we practically apply and compare several haplotype block partitioning methods for association analysis on a genome-wide scale.

1.2. Background

1.2.1. Bioinformatics and genetics

Bioinformatics is a complex, growing interdisciplinary field that combines biology and engineering; it develops software tools, algorithms, and methods to understand biological data, especially when dealing with a complex and large dataset. As a multidisciplinary field, bioinformatics merges biology, information engineering, mathematics, computer science, and statistics to interpret and analyze biological data [1], [2]. The bioinformatics intersected fields have been visualized in the Venn diagram (Figure 1.1). Simply the bioinformatics focuses on the engineering tools that work on biological data to solve problems [3]. Bioinformatics is an entry avenue for applying genetics since it is the computational branch of

molecular biology [1]. Genetics is a branch of science, specifically in biology, concerned with studying genes, genetic variation, and heredity in organisms [4].

Figure 1.1: Radical Venn diagram shows the bioinformatics disciplines.

The need to deal with massive datasets was the reason for bioinformatics genesis as a unique discipline [5]. The first use of the term bioinformatics was in 1970 when Paulien Hogeweg, together with Ben Hesper, invented it [6]. Recently, bioinformatics is used in a large number of fields for numerous applications, for instance: in personalized medicine, preventative medicine, gene therapy, drug development, evolutionary studies, antibiotic resistance, waste cleanup, climate change studies, alternative energy sources, crop improvement, forensic analysis, bio-weapon creation, improve nutritional quality, varieties, veterinary science, analysis, biotechnology, etc. [7]–[15]. In this dissertation, our study focused on human genetic variation to understand its pattern, which has potential subsequent application in medicine.

1.2.2. Foundational milestones in genetics and genomics

The following is a brief timeline overview of genetics' history and development with a summary timeline of the milestones (See Figure 1.2). In 1865, Gregor Mendel first identified the laws of heredity and eventually became known as the father of modern genetics [16], [17]. His contributions to the basic principles of genetics nowadays are incredibly relevant in thinking about human disease's genetic basis.

Miescher deserves credit for discovering the chemical of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) in 1871 [18]. In 1882, the German biologist Walter Fleming discovered the chromosomes [19]. The British biologist William Bateson created the term "genetics" in 1905 [20]. In 1944, Avery and his colleagues figured out that DNA was a hereditary material [21]. However, if we had to pick one single historic accomplishment that set the stage for genomics, it would have to be Watson and Crick's contribution by the discovery of the double-helical structure in 1953 [22]. Arguably, this accomplishment was one of the most important scientific discoveries of the last century because it set the stage for so much of what was going to take place in biomedical research since 1953.

Figure 1.2: Foundational evolutions and milestones in genetics and genomics.

In 1977, The first genuinely efficient technique to sequence DNA was discovered [23]. The international Human Genome Project begins in 1990, intending to sequence the entire human genetic code. In 1995, the first sequence of an entire genome from a microbe was determined [24]. In 2000, the completion of the draft human genome was jointly announced [25]. The full sequence – containing 30,000 to 40,000 genes – is completed in 2003 [26].

1.2.3. Chromosomes, DNA, and the central dogma of genetics

The raw material of bioinformatics and genetics is genetic data [27]. The DNA house in the nuclei of all eukaryotic cells. The human has tens of trillions of cells, and cells have a nucleus that contains the genome. The nucleus encloses the DNA in the form of threadlike X-shaped strands called chromosomes. Figure 1.3 is a schematic picture showing a breakdown of largest to smallest where we find genetic information.

Figure 1.4: A schematic picture showing a breakdown of largest to smallest where we find genetic information.

The DNA is not a single long thread. It is divided into several segments of uneven lengths; simply, it is the huge threads of unwinding chromosomes. The sections in the DNA that are responsible for protein synthesis are called genes (see Figure 1.3). The chromosomes come in homologous pairs and with two varieties: autosomal chromosomes, which are the non-sex chromosomes, and the sex chromosomes, also known as allosomal chromosomes, which determine the gender. Figure 1.4 is a picture of normal male human chromosomes lined up in pairs is called a karyotype.

Figure 1.3: The normal human karyotype. Each number represents the two chromosomes of a homologous pair. (Public domain image from national human genome research institute - glossary of genetics; freely available and used without special permission).

In humans, the genome splits between 23 pairs of chromosomes (half from the father and half from the mother, the total are 46 chromosomes). The first 22 pairs are somatic chromosomes, and the last pair are the sex chromosomes, two X chromosomes in females, and single X and single Y chromosome in males. The pair of homologous chromosomes contain the same genes in the same locations, with slight sequence variations between them. Chromosomes are made of chromatin, which consists of DNA and protein (called histone). Each chromosome has two sister chromatids, an identical copy formed by the DNA replication of a chromosome; Both are joined together by a common point called the centromere. The two identical chromatids are separated from each other into two different cells during the cell division. Each chromosome has one chromatid that replicated later into two sister chromatids in the normal state during this stage. The chromosomes have two parts: P-arm, shorter arm and Q-arm, and longer arm [27]–[29]. Figure 1.5 is an illustration of the chromosome parts and zoom-in its unwounded DNA.

Figure 1.5: The chromosome parts and the and its unwound DNA.

DNA is made up of building blocks connected to form a long chain. The small constituent is called nucleotides, which have three parts; deoxyribose sugar, phosphate -the DNA's backbone- and the nitrogenous base. Nucleotides are bonded together and form the double-helix. The base is the most critical part of the nucleotide since its sequence codes for traits. The DNA nucleobases are adenine (A), guanine (G), cytosine (C), and thymine (T), denoted by their single-letter codes. The bases are responsible for the bonding of two DNA strands. The adenine can

Figure 1.6: The DNA double-helix and the four nitrogenous bases.

only be its counterpart thymine (A-T). Likewise, cytosine can only bond with guanine (C-G). Figure 1.6 visualizes the double helix of the DNA and the four bases. The order of these four nucleobases; the base sequence that allows the DNA to create its sequence. The nitrogenous bases of one DNA strand binds to the corresponding bases in the complement strand. The length of a double-stranded DNA is measured by the number of base pairs. Humans have more than three billion base pairs in the entire genome; this means six billion letters (A, C, G, and T) [30]. The human genome has coding regions and non-coding regions, which is the vast majority of the DNA that comprises more than 98% of the sequence [31]. Non-coding DNA sequences are not translated into

amino acids. The majority of non-coding sequences fall between genes and have no known functions. Some non-coding DNA termed "introns" are found within genes. Another non-coding DNA plays a role in gene regulation. The central dogma of molecular biology is that DNA transcript into ribonucleic acid (RNA) and then RNA translated protein (as illustrate in Figure 1.7).

Figure 1.7: The central dogma of genetics.

Every group of three nucleotides is termed a codon, and each codon is translated into its corresponding amino acids. It could be more than one codon for a specific amino acid but not the opposite. The combinations of 64 codons result in a total of 20 different unique amino acids. The sequence of codons translated into a chain of amino acids, which eventually folds into a complex 3D protein [27]. Figure 1.8 represents the 20 amino acids, and the three termination signals that makeup from the nucleotide codons.

Figure 1.8: The chart represents how four bases form codons and how codons end up with the 20 amino acids.

A specific sequence of nitrogenous bases provides the information for a cell to produce a specific protein. The portions of the DNA that coded to proteins are the genes. Also, genes control the development of traits, and they are the functional unit of heredity. The human genome project (HGP) found about 20,000 to 25,000 genes in humans [25]. Approximately 20,000 of them are protein-coding genes, which means humans have at least 20,000 proteins [32]. The proteins carry out processes that keep the cell alive; they could be structural proteins, storage proteins, transport proteins, antibodies, enzymes, hormones, etc. [33]. Therefore, it is important to sequence the DNA since the change in that sequence spatially translated into protein can cause a series of consequences.

Genomic sequencing is a process of determining the order of nucleotides in DNA by analyzing a sample of DNA taken from the blood. Scientists sequence the genome to find the similarities and differences in the genome. The recent technology makes access to genomic information more accessible, faster, and more cost-effective for researchers [34].

1.2.4. Human genetic variations

All humans are 99.9% genetically identical; only 0.1 % are variations; These differences make the phenotypic differences among humans, contribute to susceptibility and severity to many diseases, affect the drug response , etc. Roughly, more than three million single nucleotide differences between any two persons [35]. Any alteration in the nucleotide sequence of the genome is called mutation [36]. Genetic variation arises mainly from mutations and sexual reproduction; a fusion of genetic material inherited from parents makes a new unique genome [37]. Most mutations occur due to abnormal DNA replication. The most prominent cause of mutations is the DNA damage because of exposure to radiation or carcinogens. There are several categories and types of mutations. If the alternation occurs in the chromosome structure or number, it is called a chromosomal mutation; this kind originates during cell division. The chromosomal mutation could result in deletion, translocation, duplication, or inversion of a segment of the chromosome. On the other hand, when the alternation occurs in the nucleotide sequence, it is called small-scale mutations or gene mutations, including insertions, deletions, and substitutions. The point substitution mutations are subclassified according to their impact on protein sequence into silent, nonsense, missense mutations. Silent mutations occur when the substituted nucleotide does not change the amino acid sequence and produce the same protein; this is possible because more than one codon could code for the same amino acid. The nonsense mutation produces a premature termination codon, which leads to incomplete and usually nonfunctional protein. Missense mutations result in a codon that translates into different amino acids. The silent mutation is also called synonymous substitution, where the nonsense and missense are called nonsynonymous substitution since they affect the amino acid sequence of a protein [38]. The genetic mutation could be neutral, beneficial, and harmful. A single point mutation can cause serious consequences. Sickle cell anemia, for instance, is caused by a single point missense mutation, and cystic fibrosis results from a nonsense mutation. The most widespread form of genetic variation is the single base-pair differences called single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) [39].

1.2.5. SNPs and haplotype blocks

SNP is a substitution mutation of a single nucleotide at a specific position in the DNA genome that is present in at least 1% of the population (Figure 1.9). The possible nucleotide variant is called an allele [40]; An allele is a letter that represents variation in the nucleotide, e.g. (it could be "A" or "C," "G" or "T").

Figure 1.9: The graphical representation of the single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP).

The SNPs are polymorphisms because they occur in different forms widely among the populations. SNPs are usually bi-allelic, which means two different nucleotide variants. The most frequent allele for a given SNP is referred to as the major allele, while the second most frequent allele is called the minor allele [40]. The frequency (MAF) is a critical parameter in genetics because it provides information that differentiates between common and rare variants. Since humans have diploid cells; that contain pairs of homologous chromosomes, one maternal chromosome, and one paternal chromosome, at any locus in the human genome, there are two alleles, one from each parent. The combination of two pairs of alleles is referred to as a genotype. In each locus, a person could have a homozygous genotype where both homologous chromosomes have the same allele. In contrast, it could be a heterozygous genotype where the two alleles are different. Figure 1.10 is a simple example to illustrate the concept of alleles and genotypes; in this example, considering the "A" to be the major allele and "T" to be the minor allele. In the illustrated example, "AA" is the major homozygous genotype, "AT" or "TA" is the heterozygous genotype, and "TT" is the minor homozygous genotype [41]. Generally, the interaction of two different alleles is based on the dominant one. The sequence of alleles inherited together at one chromosome is called a haplotype [42].

Figure 1.10: The illustration of the concept and types of alleles and genotypes.

Recently, SNPs have become a powerful tool for association studies and are treated as a biomarker. The genetic marker is an indicative identifier whose presence is related to disease or associated with its susceptibility. Thus, extracting and studying SNPs have become a substantial demand and an essential part of diagnosis and even treating many conditions. The process of measuring genetic variations of SNPs among individuals is called SNP genotyping [43]. As we can see, SNPs could give some clue why some groups of people more potentially to have certain diseases. The approach of studying the association between the genetic marker and the phenotype (the observable physical properties) along the genome is called genome-wide association study (GWAS). Basically, two strategies are implemented in GWAS; The family-based association studies and the population-based association studies [44]. In this dissertation, we only focus on population-based case-control analysis.

1.2.6. Linkage Disequilibrium (LD)

Two or more SNP loci are said to be in linkage equilibrium when they occur randomly in a population. Conversely, the linkage disequilibrium (LD) is a non-random association of alleles at different SNP loci in the general population [45]. In

most instances, two nearby SNPs share a certain amount of correlation. As an example, Figure 1.11 demonstrates two examples of high and low LD. Supposing there are four SNP loci in a particular community, the first two SNPs are at high LD; whenever the "A" allele is found, the second locus has a "C" allele. Whereas the second two SNPs are at low LD, there is no clear correlation between the last two SNPs. The two SNPs are fully linked, where the accuracy of prediction is 100%. On the contrary, the two SNPs are independent when they occur randomly.

Figure 1.11: Demonstration of high and low linkage disequilibrium (LD)

1.2.7. Measurement of the LD between SNPs

Several methods have been defined to measure the LD. Primarily, three ways are used to measure LD. For simplicity, we will present the first method as an example. Let the following be the portion of three individuals' sequences. Assuming two loci with SNP₁ and SNP₂ on a particular chromosome, each SNP is a bi-allelic SNP; each one has two alleles. The bold blue letters are the SNP₁ alleles, and the bold green letters are the SNP₂ alleles.

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GTGACTGGTAT. . . . .GATCAAGCCAG
GTGACTCGTAT. . . . .GATCAAGCCAG
GTGACTCGTAT. . . . .GATCATGCCAG
    
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Table 1.1 illustrates the alleles of each SNP. The first step to calculate the LD is by calculating the frequency of each allele.

Table 1.1: The alleles and SNPs of the illustration example for measuring the LD

Alleles	SNP ₁	SNP ₂
Allele ₁	G	A
Allele ₂	C	T

Let we consider p_1 and, p_2 as the frequency of the first and second alleles, respectively, at SNP₁. Similarly, let q_1 and, q_2 denote the first and second alleles' frequency, respectively, at SNP₂ (as illustrated in Table 1.2).

Table 1.2: The alleles and their frequency symbols of the illustration example for measuring the LD

SNP1		SNP2	
Allele	Frequency	Allele	Frequency
G	p_1	A	q_1
C	p_2	T	q_2

Then, the haplotype frequencies of the possible haplotypes have to be calculated. Let, p_{11} be the frequency of the haplotype of the first alleles at SNP₁ and SNP₂, p_{12} be the frequency of the haplotype of the first allele at SNP₁ the second allele at SNP₂, p_{21} be the frequency of the haplotype of the second allele at SNP₁, the first allele at SNP₂, and p_{22} be the frequency of the haplotype of the second alleles at SNP₁ and SNP₂. Table 1.3 simplifies the symbols that represent the haplotype frequencies.

Table 1.3: The haplotype frequency symbols of the illustration example for measuring the LD

Haplotype	Frequency	Haplotype	Frequency
GA	p_{11}	GT	q_{12}
CA	p_{21}	CT	q_{22}

The following equation is the first form of measuring LD and the most common expression.

$$D = (p_{11})(p_{22}) - (p_{12})(p_{21}) \quad (1.1)$$

If there is a deviation (D) value, there is a correlation between the two SNPs. While if D equals 0, it means that the equilibrium occurs, and no LD between the two SNPs. When $|D|=1$ it indicates the complete LD [46].

Occasionally, according to the allele frequency of two loci, D 's value could be negative, but actual frequencies are never negative. Thereby, the D value somewhat became problematic because it makes it hard to compare LD between different pairs of alleles. However, to solve this issue, researchers have proposed the standardization method. Lewontin has suggested the normalized deviation (D'), also known as the Lewontin D -prime [47]. The following formula of D' is the standardization of D .

$$D' = \frac{D}{D_{max}} \quad (1.2)$$

The D_{max} is the hypothetical maximum difference between the noticed and expected haplotype frequencies.

$$D_{max} = \begin{cases} \min(p_1q_2, p_2q_1), & D > 0 \\ \min(p_1q_1, p_2q_2), & D < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1.3)$$

Additionally, the third method of measuring the LD is by the Pearson correlation coefficient (r^2), representing the statistical correlation between two SNPs, as shown in the following equation.

$$r^2 = \frac{D^2}{p_1p_2q_1q_2} \quad (1.4)$$

The r^2 takes the value from zero to one, reflecting the strength of the correlation between pairs of alleles [48]. The totally perfect LD means $r^2 = 1$. The strong LD has r^2 higher than 0.8. LD allows us to predict one of the alleles at the second locus based on the allele at the first locus. This high LD happens more frequently when two positions are close to each other. Many other methods are proposed for measuring the LD, but the last three measures are the most common [49].

1.2.8. The visualization of LD

Typically, the degree of pairwise LD is visualized using heat map or D' diagram either r^2 or D' as they both have positive values. Figure 1.12 shows two common ways to visualize LD by plotting color-coded values. Each colored square represents the correlation coefficient r^2 between a pair of SNPs. Figure 1.12 (a) on the left side shows an example of the LD heatmap based on r^2 ; the graph could also be plotted based on the D' [50]. Usually, the distances between SNPs are defined in the

visualization graph Figure 1.12 (b) on the right side elucidates the D' diagram; color codes present the strength of the correlation [51].

Figure 1.12: Visualization of LD. (a) LD heatmap plot, (b) D' diagram

2.1.9. The interpretation of LD

The LD measures how often two alleles are inherited together; how two alleles are always co-inherited. The appearance of high and low LD regions is believed to be a result of two things: the time and recombination process. LD between two alleles is related to the time of the mutation events, population history, and genetic distance. Figure 1.13 is a schematic representation of how SNPs inherited together from the common ancestors and how they appear in population across generations.

Figure 1.13: Schematic representation illustrates the inheritance of SNPs over time

As an example, assuming a common ancestor primarily have two branches. SNP₁ and SNP₂ are from the same first branch; they will be inherited together and more likely to coexist in the next generations. SNP₃ has come out in one offspring branch of the main first branch. Accordingly, SNP₁ and SNP₂ will always appear with SNP₃ but not vice versa. SNP₄ has occurred in the second branch first-generation, SNP₅, and SNP₆ have appeared in the second and third generation, respectively. Thus, SNP₄ will appear wherever SNP₅ or SNP₆ exists. The previous illustration is a small example of how we can predict an SNP depending on the existence of another one. (see Figure 1.13). Simply the cause of high LD is the accumulation of inherited mutations over time from the common ancestors.

Nonetheless, the high LD regions are broken with a very low LD. During the meiosis cell division that is essential to the generation of the gametes (either sperms or eggs), there is a small chance that a pair of paternal chromosomes exchange a segment of DNA with each other, this process called recombination. Figure 1.14 demonstrates the recombination event. Before miosis, the chromosomes are in the form of two sister chromatids. The two homologous chromosomes are aligned and associated with each other, and then they cross over. Crossing over is the exchange of two chromosome fragments between non-sister chromatids. After miosis, the single chromosomes are produced, and they have four different genetic combinations; two will come from the chromatids that did not participate in crossing over, and other two will be recombinant [45], [52].

Figure 1.14: Demonstration of the recombination process: homologous chromosomes before cross over, the cross over between two chromatids, chromosomes after cross over, and after cell division, which resulted in two recombinants and two nonrecombinant chromatids.

Therefore, chromosomes are shuffle, and so produce breakpoints between strong associated SNP called recombination hotspots. The recombination event between two SNPs breaks the association between them (result in low LD). Moreover, the neighboring SNPs are less likely to be impacted by the recombination than distant SNPs [53]–[55]. As the LD is broken by recombination, historical recombinations between pairs of human chromosomes result in the decay of D overtime. Hence, the geneticists could interpret why the genome is organized into block-like structures.

1.2.10. Haplotype blocks and haplotypes

The inheritance of SNPs together over generations and the recombination events result in an underlying structure in the genome described as a series of discrete groups of SNPs [56]. A set of closely associated SNPs located on one chromosome and which contain only a few numbers of distinct alleles in a population is referred to as a haplotype block or LD block [57]. A haplotype is an arrangement of alleles that are inherited together from one chromosome (from a single parent) [58], [59]. As specified by the haplotype-block model, each block should have a high level of LD [57]. Adjacent blocks are disconnected by regions of recombination events called recombination hotspots [60], [61]. Figure 1.15 is a schematic depiction that illustrates the haplotype blocks, haplotype, and recombination hotspots zones along a chromosome. In this descriptive example, three individuals represent the different patterns of haplotypes in a population.

Figure 1.15: Schematic depiction of haplotype blocks, haplotypes, and recombination hotspots.

SNPs in each block are correlated, it means that we can predict the next SNP according to the existing SNP in the sequence. The first discovery of haplotype blocks was in 2001 and was published by Daly and his colleagues [62]. The haplotype block is specified when a portion of a genomic sequence have a higher LD value than a predetermined threshold [56]. The block boundaries should be specified in a manner that minimizes the included SNPs [63]. The sequence of haplotypes has limited numbers of SNP alleles combinations that present the common haplotypes in a population [64]. Ordinarily, two possible alleles in each SNP locus, assuming a haplotype block covering five SNPs, it may have 2^5 haplotypes.

Nevertheless, the number of haplotypes within a block is much less than that and has a low diversity. Usually, the average number of haplotypes are from two to four haplotypes per block [62]. Each population has a different size and pattern of haplotype blocks [65]. The size of blocks varies in range from two to ninety-two kbp [62]. The higher the recombination rate, the smaller is the LD block sizes [66].

1.2.11. Haplotype blocks partitioning and visualization

The process of specifying haplotype block boundaries based on LD taking into account reducing the number of SNPs, is called haplotype block partitioning. The edges of haplotype blocks cannot be directly observed; they must instead be inferred indirectly using algorithms. The LD metrics are applied in haplotype block partitioning. Some evidence reveals that different algorithms of haplotype block partitioning give quite different results when used on the same data [67], [68]. However, another study found that their results are roughly the same and very consistent [69]. However, a literature review of the methods and algorithms of haplotype block partitioning will be covered in chapter 2. After identifying the haplotype blocks, researchers used to visualize the resulted blocks and the included SNPs in a color-coded plot. Figure 1.16 illustrates an example of eight SNPs that are near each other in a region of the chromosome. The black dots in the graph refer to the SNPs. The first four SNPs are highly associated with each other and the last three ones as well, both form two blocks. The graph displays the LD between every two SNPs by creating a triangle for each pairwise. The highest LD on the map is depicted by the red color. The more intense the red color, the higher the LD. The lighter the color, the lower the LD. As we are going down through the graph, the lower layers represent SNPs that are far away from each other. The square that is in the apex of the triangle represents the LD between the first and last SNP.

Figure 1.16: An example of the LD color-coded plot

When drawing a broader scale, the graph will be deeper with a larger number of triangles; each one depicts an LD block.

1.2.12. The role of SNPs and haplotype blocks in diseases

SNPs and haplotypes have many applications in medicine, pharmacology, agriculture, etc. One of the essential results from studying human variation is getting a better understanding of our bodies and genetic epidemiology [70], [71]. Almost any disease has a genetic component. Most hereditary disorders are caused by a single mutation. For instance: cystic fibrosis, sickle cell anemia, color-blindness, Huntington disease, Duchenne muscular dystrophy, etc. In such conditions, the top cause of the disorders is the mutation. However, other conditions developed due to the interaction of multiple genetic and environmental factors. Most diseases fall into this group and are called complex diseases, like diabetes, heart disease, rheumatoid arthritis, obesity, and cancer. The genetic component, in some cases, is fragile, like in infectious diseases. The point is that even if the genetic part is very subtle, but it is still existing. By the way, many people have genetic resistance to viral infection [35]. Figure 1.17 shows that roughly all diseases have genetic components but with different percentages.

Figure 1.17: Almost any disease has a genetic component.

Every single person has some genetic risk and predisposition for some diseases. Fortunately, not all people are affected negatively by the consequences of genetic risk factors. Scientists suggest two reasons: maybe because humans do not live long enough for it to appear or because of the absence of environmental triggers [35]. Hence, the complex traits have modest multiple genetic components, and so it is not easy to specify the particular genetic mutation that contributes to the disease. In this case, GWAS is a powerful tool to pick up the risk SNPs. Both SNPs and haplotype blocks could be used as a genetic marker.

Even though SNPs can be considered as a functional unit of genetic variations. Haplotype blocks consider multiple loci in the genome and can uncover the risk regions that contribute to the disease [72]. Consequently, GWASs had been trying to link SNPs and haplotype blocks with susceptibility and severity of complex traits [68], [73]

1.2.13. SNPs vs. haplotype blocks

The single SNP-based approach is the conventional way in genetic analysis and association studies. Researchers adopt this approach for several reasons. SNPs are abundant in the genome, and that makes them a valuable resource for genetic studies. Researchers have estimated that SNPs occur about once every thousand bp. Moreover, they describe most of the human sequence variations, provide more detailed and accurate association analysis, and are suitable for dealing with limited

genotyped data [74]. A variety of disorders are caused only by one SNP or few mutations, i.e., inherited diseases; in this case, adopting the single SNP-based approach is required and effective [75]. SNPs are also an essential tool for mapping and association because they are stable, easy to score, and located in genes sometimes. The major limitation of a single SNP-based approach, first, SNPs associated with particular traits and complex diseases, typically explain only a small proportion. Second, the SNPs approach does not consider the epistatic impact when different gene loci contribute to the same phenotype. Third, thousands of significantly should be made when dealing with millions of SNPs, which means higher cost and longer time to find the association [72], [76]. However, a single SNP-based approach has explained many diseases and work very well in traits with a single mutation.

Nonetheless, the regional-based approach reveals numerous advantages when dealing with wide-scale genetic data. In complex diseases, many associated risk SNPs have a modest effect. In such a case, considering the interaction of SNPs is essential. Moreover, haplotype blocks reduce the wrong positive association due to genotyping errors. Haplotype blocks have counted as genetic markers and have become a tremendous genetic variation that has a vast range of genetic applications. Haplotype blocks reduce biomarkers efficiently. Each sequence of haplotypes is treated as one unit instead of studying each SNP separately [77]. Dimensional reduction accordingly simplifies the computations and analysis in further association studies; Use of haplotypes in association research reduces the number of tests to be carried out. Additionally, the number of recombinational hotspots could be a sign of the number of cell divisions that serve a lot in evolutionary studies. Also, the haplotype block considers the interrelationship between linked SNPs [78]. Researchers have noticed that multiple mutations are linked to most complex diseases rather than single point mutations. Therefore, regional-based, i.e., haplotype-based and gene-based, association study approaches, are preferred in complex diseases [79], [80]. The main point of preferring the haplotype block over the SNP approach is removing the redundancy. The massive size of genotyped dataset analyses makes the computations a difficult task even with available technology. Geneticists have found more than eighty million SNPs in populations throughout the world [40], [81]. The main challenge of population-based whole-genome investigation lies in dealing with big datasets. Another way to reduce the number of covered SNPs is by selecting the most representative SNPs in each haplotype block, which referred to as the tag SNPs [64], [68], [82], [83].

1.2.14. Rheumatoid arthritis and genetics

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic complex autoimmune condition that primarily affects joints. The cause of RA is not clear; it is believed to be a combination of genetic and environmental factors [84]. These, in turn, results in an immune reaction, which ultimately leads to the development of synovitis, joint damage, and structural bone damage. The patient ends up with pain, disability, and emotional, social, and economic burden [84]. RA affects about 0.5–1% world-wide population, twice likely to appear in women than in men with a top prevalence between the ages of 30 and 50 years [85]. The genetic component is higher than the environmental part in RA, so it's crucial to identify the genetic risk factors which may lead to early detection, treatment, and understanding of the disorder.

1.3. Motivation

Understanding human genetic variation inevitably contributes to understanding ourselves. The genetic variation not just influences our phenotypic differences, but also our predisposition to diseases. It is widely believed that any disease has a genetic component, even infectious diseases; some people have a resistance to it. Nowadays, I think more than any time ever before; it is crucial to study the root causes of illnesses. In particular, RA or any other chronic condition hugely affects the productivity of a person and its quality of life. One in each 17 people has a rare disease, which actually makes rare diseases not so rare and as a category prevalent. Studying the SNPs variations lead to a much deeper insight to unravel mysterious conditions, understanding that better can allow physicians to treat the patient better and in a more sophisticated and precise way, and that's the essence of precision medicine.

Since the haplotype blocks are much more effective and powerful in association analysis, we tend to apply the new partition algorithms on our data. Some methods of haplotype partitioning do not permit intermediate areas of low LD between strong related SNPs and manage to part data into small blocks. Other methods have computation and runtime limitations. Therefore we have made a comparative study on the recent techniques.

While we partition the haplotype blocks, still many questions remain about the pattern of the haplotype blocks, and the parameters that affect its structure and number included SNPs, especially the MAF. So, along with our study, we explore

the role of MAF in haplotype block partitioning on our current data. We hope our comparative strategies could somewhat fill the knowledge gap in this field.

One of the reasons that encourage us in this endeavor is that the subspecialty of associated genetic analysis is limited and not broad in Egypt and particularly in upper Egypt. In this effort, we have tried to raise the initial seed of this field of bioinformatics in Minia and upper Egypt.

Day by day, that genome and exome sequencing has gotten a lot cheaper. Scientists expect in the future; the genome profile might be as popular as an x-ray in the medical records of every patient. We're not there today, but where we are today not just reading sequence data but also edit genes and replace mutant genes by good ones. Scientists are not that far away from a day when they can start to use the genome to prescribe medicines individually in a tailored fashion for patients. At some point in our lives, maybe anyone of us, or people we care about, may become patients, and that's why I think that genetic research is incredibly vital for all of us.

1.4. Research Objectives

The core aims of this dissertation are the following:

- 1) Practically implement computational algorithms to partition genotyped data based on the haplotype blocks.
- 2) Explore and describe our genome-wide database.
- 3) Prepare the genotyped data and impute missing data.
- 4) Find the best haplotype partitioning method applied for the whole-genome case-control dataset to reduce the number of SNPs in the association study.
- 5) Compare the haplotype blocks resulted from the most current method.
- 6) Along with our work, we also apply different MAF thresholds different methods of partitioning to figure out the role of MAF in haplotype block partitioning and compare the results among them.
- 7) Understand the genome pattern and structure via MAF.

The massive size of genotyped dataset analyses and computation was not an easy task. Due to incredible improvement in computers and computation methods, several methods were applied to partition genomes into blocks. Some methods of haplotype partitioning do not permit intermediate areas of low LD between robust related SNPs and tend to part data into small blocks. Other methods have computation and runtime limitations. In this research, therefore, we aim to apply

some of the most common recent haplotype partitioning methods and provide the optimum sequence to fulfill the task.

1.5. Thesis Outlines and organization

This dissertation includes seven chapters:

Chapter 1: Introduction, background, and preliminaries

Chapter 2: A literature review

Chapter 3: Data exploration and description

Chapter: 4 Data Preprocessing

Chapter: 5 Methodology

Chapter: 6 Results

Chapter: 7 Conclusion

Chapter 2

Literature review

2.1. The main projects in genomics

After Watson and Crick uncovered the double-helical structure in 1953, The world was curious about sequencing the entire genome. Many projects are made from that time until today to find the genetic variations. In this section, we will cover the largest and most significant projects in the human genomics. We will focus on projects related to medicine, healthcare, and humans' variations in general.

2.1.1. Human Genome Project

In fact, that first human genome sequence produced by the human genome project (HGP). The cost of the sequence was billion dollars. HGP was a global collaborative scientific research project that aims to detect the base pairs that built human DNA, map all genes of the human genome to identify its locus and function. The project still one of the world's largest scientific projects [87]. HGP officially launched in 1990 and completed in 2003 [26]. The initial sequence and analysis published in 2001 [25]. The project was under supervision by the national institutes of health (NIH) and several other communities around the world.

2.1.2. International HapMap Project

The interpretation of the human genome by the HGP has made it possible to develop a haplotype map (HapMap) of the human genome. The International HapMap Project is a corporation that intends to identify the HapMap of the human genome to elucidate the widespread human genetic variation patterns. Also, the project has aimed to create a genome-wide map of LD and haplotype blocks. In turn, it allows researchers to find genes and genetic variations that affect diseases, health, and respond to drugs. In addition, it facilitates large-scale association-mapping studies. The NIH funded the HapMap project to catalog haplotype blocks throughout the human genome [88]. The Knowledge and data developed by the project are freely available for researchers. HapMap project formally started in 2002, and its outputs published in three phases [89]. More than one million SNPs from 269 participants gained in the project's phase I and published in 2005 [90]. About 3.1 million SNPs genotyped from 270 individuals in phase II, and the results published in 2007 [91]. A more diverse set of human populations was contributed

in the phase III dataset that released in 2009 [92]. Only common SNPs were targeted in the HapMap project with MAF higher than 0.5%.

The HapMap project was worthwhile and beneficial in several applications [93], [94]. The project reduces the number of SNPs needed to investigate the genome for association studies from ten million SNPs into about five hundred thousand tag SNPs. Thus, finding regions that affect diseases more comprehensive and efficient.

2.1.3. The 1000 Genome Project

The 1000 Genomes Project, also referred to as 1KGP initiated in 2008 and was established to catalog the human genetic variation. Geneticists, though it aimed to sequence the entire genomes of at least one thousand participants from different ethnic communities utilizing newly revolutionary technologies [95]. The project completed its pilot phase in 2010 [96]. Two years later, the KGP fulfill its goal by genome-wide sequencing of 1092 participants in 2012 [97]. The project finished in 2015 and recorded its results in a published paper, which became an international reference for genetic variations of humans [40]. Rightly 84.7 million SNPs are targeted by the project; most have MAF higher the 1%. The project provides new avenues for many research opportunities and discoveries [98].

2.1.4. The 100,000 Genomes Project

In 2012, the UK government announced the 100,000 Genome Project that primarily targets rare diseases, infectious diseases, and cancer. In 2015, Other countries participated in the project, i.e., Northern Ireland and Scotland. By the end of 2018, the project finished sequencing 100,000 whole genomes and accomplished its primary goal. A new enterprise in 2019 opens the doors to public participation in genomic research [99]. The project was funded by the National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) and the National Health Service (NHS) England. The project aimed to sequence the whole genomes from more than 100,000 NHS patients. The participants approve accessing their genome data and connecting it with the information about their medical history from the health records. Therefore, researchers could link the medical and genomic data to improve the understanding of the causes and treatment of the diseases. The project results in a huge international medical resource, which is the UK Biobank[81]. About half a million participants age between 40 and 69 contribute to the biobank database. Several research and findings have arisen from the project [98], [100].

However, we did not review projects that aimed to catalog genetic risk factors associated with cancer like the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA); we focused only on projects that capture the general variation. Figure 2.1 shows a review timeline of the biggest genome projects and the main events in each project, which deemed as milestones in medical genetics.

Figure 2.1: The timeline of most common genome projects.

2.2. A literature review on haplotype block partitioning methods

In the early days of HGP, Mark Daly and his colleagues first noticed underlying structures in the genome and described as discrete haplotype blocks. Their study

conducted over 500 kbp on chromosome 5 in 2001. Only 103 common SNPs selected ($>5\%$ MAF) and makeup 11 in consecutive blocks [62]. The results have shown that each block appears every ten to hundreds of kbps. The blocks have only two to four major haplotype patterns. Daly then becomes a pioneer and the discoverer of the haplotype blocks, developer of several programs (i.e., Haploview and Plink) and one of the top hundred most cited researchers [101], [102]. The adopted method at that time was the hidden Markov model (HMM) [62]. LD and measured by a D statistical value.

Two months later, Patil et al. developed the Greedy algorithm to partition more than 24 thousand SNPs ($>10\%$ MAF) from chromosome 21 [63]. The genotype sequence ends up with 4 thousand blocks. The method designs a criterion based on selecting the tag SNPs that represent about 80% of the haplotypes.

In 2002, Zhang et al. developed a dynamic programming (DP) algorithm for haplotype block partitioning using the same Patil dataset [103]. The DP minimizes the number of SNPs into 2,575 blocks using the Patil criterion with performing an optimization technique [77]. The method then integrated into a web interface and software program named HaploBlockFinder [104]. In 2004, the HaploBlock computer program released, which is an updated version of the HaploBlockFinder program. HaploBlock developed to parse the haplotype blocks and to select the tag SNPs [105].

Later in the year, Gabriel et al. proposed the confidence interval (CI) algorithm based on the normalized measure D' [106]. Most applied markers had $> 20\%$ MAF. The marginal error was chosen to be 5% because many faults could be found due to errors of genotyping or genome assembly, recurrent mutation, or gene conversion. The method has tested on different datasets with different ethnicities. The CI method became one of the most popular methods of partitioning for a couple of years and until today [101], [107].

Later the same year, Wang and his colleagues proposed a novel method based on the distribution of recognized recombinations by applying the four-gamete test (FGT) [56]. The method takes advantage of the statistical counting of recombination events that suggested by Hudson [108]. The method based on a particular configuration when appear it indicates a recombination event. The method is appropriate with a low mutation rate species like humans. So, the drawback of this method is that it is not suitable for high mutation rate species as in the bacterial data analysis.

Avi Itzhak and colleagues suggested a new numerical algorithm in early 2003 that choose the minimal group of SNPs requisite to form the haplotype block [109]. This method applied to eleven thousand SNPs and reduced them to 25% to 36%.

Later in 2003, Koivisto et al. developed the minimum description length (MDL) principle, which is based on segmentation algorithms with a clear probabilistic hypothesis of the boundaries. [110]. The methods conducted using Daly data for accurate comparison. In this method, the k-means clustering algorithm was applied to classify the SNPs within the blocks. The MDL method revealed high resistance against genotyping errors and noise [111] since the model did not account for the association between markers at adjacent blocks.

In 2004, Greenspan and Geiger et al. develop an upgraded MDL algorithm [112]. The good point in the method is that it accepts both phased haplotype and unphased data; haplotype phasing means identifying the alleles that form the haplotypes on each chromosome from genotype data [113]. Later in the same year, HapAnalyzer software is produced for haplotype analysis, block partitioning, tag SNPs computing, and association studies [114]. The program exploited the CI method and adopted D' and r^2 measurements. That same year, Kimmel et al. studied the problems and noise with haplotype block partitioning and analysis. Particularly, they investigated the number of SNPs in a block when there is missing or wrong data. As well as the case of multi-populations to find a different block partition in each population. They proposed an algorithm to overcome the problems [115]. The researchers here have assumed the CI algorithm [106].

In early 2005, Barrett et al. proposed the solid spine of LD (SSLD) method, which finds blocks based on the strong pairwise LD with markers at the block boundary [101]. Barrett also combined the CI [59], FGT [56], and SSLD methods in the Haploview platform [101]. Haploview not only partition the haplotypes using three methods but also an integrated program for haplotype analysis, single SNP-based and haplotype-based association studies, tagging SNPs selection, data inquiry from HapMap and visualizing the haplotype analysis results [116]. Haploview was initiated, developed at, and is maintained by Daly's lab at the famous Cambridge's biomedical and genomic research center; the Broad Institute. It could perform in a command-line mode using java for faster analysis or in a graphical user interface (GUI). The program is open source java software and still until now is used and provides robust analysis [117]–[119].

Then, Su et al. incorporated the entropy measure of haplotype diversity and the DP algorithm to overcome the missing data, which reach 20% on Patil et al. data. The method involved an iterative process in each block for inferring missing SNPs and reducing the block entropy [120].

During the same year (2005), a computer program with a GUI dubbed htSNPer created to partition the SNPs into haplotype blocks and select the tagging SNPs. The program has utilized the CI algorithm for phased data. In the case of unphased data, the haplotype estimated using the expectation-maximization (EM) algorithm. The program has a specific criterion to identify the phylotype blocks based on the normalized LD deviation D' , chromosome coverage, confidence boundaries of LD, and assuming no historical recombination [121].

In 2006, Lin et al. propose a linear algorithm to find the most extended haplotype block and missing data process method [122]. Then, that same year, Greenspan and Geiger proposed Markov chains to model haplotype blocks genomic regions [123]. By 2007, Yang and Tabus proposed the normalized maximum likelihood model to partition the haplotype SNPs [124].

Pattaro et al. in 2008 developed a method based on Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm [125]. They applied the MCMC algorithm to build a software called MATILDE; this name is taken from an “algorithm to identify linkage disequilibrium blocks.” The program clusters contiguous SNPs into haplotype blocks and makes statistical testing for association studies. The LD is computed either by D' [47] or r^2 . The algorithm shows significant computational speed [125].

In 2009, Sazonova et al. proposed a new block partitioning algorithm for cost-efficient data referred to as xor-genotype data [126]. Xor-genotypes are less expensive sequences data than the full genotypes and also distinguish heterozygous loci from homozygous loci [127]. The algorithm allows missing entries and simultaneously finding of LD blocks. Therefore, such a method was practical, efficient, and fast.

In the same year, (2009), Ali Katanforoush et al., suggested a global haplotype block partitioning method for case-control association studies with maximal associated SNP pairs [128]. The method reported a large average size of blocks and significant dimensional reduction.

In 2010, Zahiri et al. proposed a novel powerful DP algorithm for block partitioning [129]. The calculation can be done in sophisticated polynomial time

complexity concerning the number of SNPs and haplotypes, which make the method very efficient.

The haplotype blocks are affected by populations admixture. As we described earlier in chapter 1, genetic recombinations break genomes into blocks, which means that descendants of the admixture event are made up of different combinations of ancestral blocks. In 2011, Pugach et al. proposed a method based on wavelet transform for dating the time of population admixture [130]. The size and number of admixture blocks give information about when the admixture happened and the rate of recombination. The group suggested the PCA-based genome scanning to parse the admixture in genome-scale processing.

In 2013, Ilhan et al. proposed a genetic algorithm (GA) and support vector machine (SVM) for selecting tagging SNPs and the rest of SNPs in a gene. The method was dubbed GA-SVM; this contribution considerably enhances association studies for complex diseases [131].

As the previous conventional methods of haplotype block partitioning have significant memory problems, immense computational complexity, and time complications usually quadratic runtime complexity. Taliun et al. in 2014 developed a novel method to improve processing time and memory and reduce more than 80% of the computation; so, it is very effective in genome-scale analysis and dense genotyped data [132]. The method referred to as MIG++, and it is initially an upgraded and optimization of the CI method developed by Gabriel et al. [106]. The added computational enhancements of MIG++ makes it better than the original algorithm in term of time and memory. The processing time of partitioning total HapMap II data was approximately 19 days and less than two days for 1KGP CEPH data.

Moreover, it computes LD without any limitations in the distance, blocks length, density, and allele frequency [132]. Which gave the researchers new insight about genome structure: the haplotype block length can be more than one million bps. MIG++ applied to North American Rheumatoid Arthritis Consortium (NARAC) data and showed reliable genome-wide association analysis [132].

One year later, in 2015, Taliun et al. proposed a novel fast method based on a sampling algorithm named S-MIG ++ [133]. The key point of this approach is to sample a small number of SNPs to expect the regions that almost certainly include the haplotype blocks. Then the postprocessing stage obtains the accurate blocks.

This method considerably reduces the calculations and has an extremely swift partitioning process. By comparing the MIG++ and S-MIG++ over approximately quarter-million 1KGP SNPs, the processing time of S-MIG++ was reduced from 19.6 to 1.45 days. Furthermore, the elapsed time is about 5 hours in a parallelized version (more than 92-fold time reduction) [133]. MIG++ implemented under PLINK 1.9 while S-MIG++ implemented under LDExplorer R package [134].

In 2015, Yang Da suggested a multi-allelic haplotype model predict genetic variation based on partitioning [135]. The approach adopted the quantitative genetics model and classified the multi-allelic genotype into dominant and additive values.

Kim and Yoo, in 2016, investigated the impact of SNP density on haplotype block partitioning [136]. The study was made using five different popular haplotype block partitioning methods: CI, FGT, SSLD, MIG++ and S-MIG++ [56], [101], [106], [132], [133]. The SNPs are sampling rather than using the full SNP set from several experimental datasets from 1KGP and HapMap phase 3. The results have exposed that the sampling ratio is directly proportional to the total number of haplotype blocks and inversely proportional to the length of haplotype blocks. The effect of SNP density is exponential for FGT and SSLD and linear for CI, MIG++, and S-MIG++. Generally, the results of SNPs with a density below 50% are extremely different from the original total SNPs set. Therefore, the selection of SNPs is crucial and depends on the application.

In 2018 Kim et al. developed the Big-LD algorithm, a novel method for haplotype block partitioning using interval graph modeling of clusters [137]. The previous methods rely on restricted definitions that do not permit middle loci of low LD between closely linked SNP pairs and have a propensity to break high-density SNP data into multiple small blocks having a strong between-block association. The big-LD method solved this problem by clustering close pairwise LD SNPs, regardless of being spatially consecutive [138]. The method is based on an agglomerative technique beginning with small groups of SNPs in all LD bin regions and continue to combine those groups. In comparison with the previous methods; CI, FGT, SSLD, MCMC, MIG++, and S-MIG++, Big-LD results in larger haplotype blocks. Noteworthy, the haplotype blocks generated by Big-LD, fall in with recombination hotspot areas determined by experiments. Furthermore, Big-LD showed substantial improvement in computing time over earlier methods.

Mainly, the method applied clique-Based clustering (CLQ-D) LD bin construction algorithm, upgraded version of the CLQ [139].

In 2019, Pook et al. developed a HaploBlocker R-package for constructing haplotype blocks taking into account the linkage more than conventional LD measures [140]. The HaploBlocker optimizes the block structure, produces a haplotype library for further analyses, and deals with data with different SNP densities.

Kim et al. in late 2019 provided an R package to optimally define and visualize the haplotype blocks called “gpart” [141]. The method basically is a modified version of Big-LD. Thus, it optimizes the partitioning process, especially in terms of time and memory. Big-LD and gpart are very suitable for implementation on a personal computer. Uniquely, gpart capable of displaying haplotype blocks and genes as many as 20,000 SNPs in one graph.

In 2020 Fatemeh Zamani et al. developed the NCMHap method that clusters the LD structure based on neutrosophic c-means (NCM) algorithm [142]. The algorithm tends to cluster the SNPs data and reduce the number of interactions.

In the middle of 2020, Dong et al. proposed LDBlockShow software to visualize LD and haplotype structures. The merit of this program is that it directly deals with the variant call format (VCF) data files. Furthermore, it simultaneously generates graphs and statistical calculations for association studies [143].

Table 2.1 summarizes the methods from the discovery of haplotype blocks in 2001 until today. The table presents almost the existing haplotype block partitioning methods, the developer, references, the year of publishing the method, the number of SNPs and LD blocks of the examined data that used to investigate the method, and finally, the MAF used by the methods’ authors. Some methods have applied multiple datasets with multiple results; in this literature, we only have focused on the remarkable results.

Table 2.1: Summary of computational methods for haplotype block partitioning.

Computational approaches	Authors and References	Date	No. SNPs	No. Blocks	MAF
Hidden Markov model (HMM)	Daly et al. [62]	2001	103	11	>5%

Greedy algorithm	Patil et al. [63]	2001	24047	4135	>10%
Dynamic programming	Zhang et al. [103]	2002	24047	2,575	>10%
Confidence interval (CI) method	Gabriel et al.	2002	3738	928	>20%
Four-gamete test (FGT)	Wang et al.	2002	Not specified	Not specified	>20%
Numerical algorithm to choose the minimal group of SNPs	Avi Itzhak et al. [109]	2003	11,000	25% to 36% reduction	Not specified
Minimum description length (MDL) principle	Koivisto et al. [110]	2003	45	5	Not specified
Upgraded MDL algorithm	Greenspan and Geiger et al. [112]	2004	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified
Solid spine of LD (SSLD)	Barrett et al. [101]	2005	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified
linear algorithm to find the most extended haplotype block and missing data	Lin et al. [122]	2006	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified
Markov chains to Model haplotype blocks	Greenspan and Geiger [123]	2006	693,114	62,541	Not specified
Normalized maximum likelihood model to partition the haplotype SNPs	Yang and Tabus [124]	2007	103	8	Not specified
Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm	Pattaro et al. [125]	2008	500	114 using r^2 and 215 using $ D' $	>5%
Xor-genotype	Sazonova et al. [126]	2009	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified

Global haplotype block partitioning method for case-control association studies	Ali Katanforoush et al. [128]	2009	22,512	1000	Not specified
Upgraded DP algorithm	Zahiri et al. [129]	2010	15,000	901	Not specified
wavelet transform for dating the time of population admixture	Pugach et al. [130]	2011	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified
GA-SVM	Ilhan et al. [131]	2013	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified
MIG++	Taliun et al. [132]	2014	445,832	98,979	>0.1%
S-MIG++	Taliun et al. [133]	2015	243,080	Not specified	Not specified
BigLD	Kim et al. [137]	2018	75,582	2479	>5%
HaploBlocker	Pook et al. [140]	2019	501,124	2,991	Not specified
gpart	Kim et al. [141]	2020	Not specified	Not specified	>5%
NCMHap	Fatemeh Zamani et al. [142]	2020	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified

From Table 2.1, the haplotype blocks have reduced the biomarkers about 7-10 times. In the term of computational speed and feasibility to work in the environment of a personal computer, the latest method; BigLD, HaploBlocker, and gpart have shown greater possibilities. Table 2.2 present the existing software for LD blocks partitioning, analysis, and visualization.

Table 2.2: Summary of the software for partitioning and analyzing the haplotype blocks.

The method or algorithm	Year	Developer	Reference
HaploBlockFinder	2002	Zhang et al.	[104]

HaploBlock	2004	Zhang et al.	[105]
HapAnalyzer	2004	Jung et al.	[114]
Haploview	2005	Barrett et al.	[101]
htSNPer	2005	Ding et al.	[121]
MATILDE	2008	Pattaro et al.	[125]
MIG++ using PLINK 1.9	2014	Taliun et al.	[132]
S-MIG++ under LDEplorer R package	2015	Taliun et al.	[133]
BigLD R package	2018	Kim et al.	[137]
HaploBlocker	2019	Pook et al.	[140]
Gpart R package	2020	Kim et al.	[141]
LDBlockShow	2020	Dong et al.	[143]

2.3. Discussion and conclusion

Several research contributions have compared some haplotype block partitioning methods. Other literature review contributions have focused on the haplotype phase [144]. Nonetheless, we did not find one literature review presents all haplotype blocks from 2001 to 2020. Shim et al. empirically compare CI and FGT using NARAC data and apply the resulted blocks in association analysis [145]. Indap et al. have experimentally compared Gabriel's method, HapBlock (2004) and MDL method, and identified the common regions between the three methods in order to find all possible regions that may hide SNPs associated with diseases [69]. Saad et al. also have studied the impact of haplotype partitioning using Haploview methods on association analysis of RA using data from NARAC [146]. Kim et al. have made an empirical comparison of Haploview methods (CI, FGT, and SSLD), MIG++, S-MIG++, and BigLD [137], [138]. The results have revealed BigLD capabilities. Gpart algorithm solves the problem of the previous methods and definitions for LD blocks as they do not serve well to identify long-range haplotype blocks in sequencing data such as available in HapMap and 1KGP. Ibrahim et al. have applied the Haploview methods, and BigLD to case-control genome-scale data

and practically have compared the four methods [107]. It is difficult to achieve an absolute rule definition of an LD block; instead of that, we are trying to add a contribution to haplotype block-based association and analysis by comparing the haplotypes block coverage, applying methods that produce LD blocks coincide with the recombination hotspots and finding the optimal practical workflow.

Chapter 3

Data description and exploration

3.1. Data overview

This chapter provides an in-depth description, analysis, and visualization for genotypic data from North American Rheumatoid Arthritis Consortium (NARAC). NARAC dataset is a well-known dataset for genome-wide association studies (GWAS) to rheumatoid arthritis (RA) disease, including 545,080 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) for 868 cases and 1194 controls. In this descriptive study, first, we describe the data in general: a) the number of females and males in both cases and controls and b) the percentage of missing data. We have counted the number of each allele, the numbers of each genotype, the minor allele frequency (MAF) for each SNP. The data are divided into four categories according to the SNP MAF, as following: 1) very rare SNPs, 2) rare SNPs, 3) low-frequency SNPs, and 4) common SNPs. Then, we investigate the region of these SNPs in the chromosome to find the percentage of SNPs in the coding locations and other regions. We have found that each category has a different proportion in each region of consequence annotation. The overall descriptive tables are done first for each chromosome and then for the whole data. This analysis focuses on the autosomal chromosomes. The results could provide clear insight into the manner of the data and the MAF of it, which can be compared with other datasets. The findings of this descriptive exploratory analysis could help the researchers having an overview of the data and provide an accurate and deep intuitive understanding of such case-control data.

NARAC dataset is a genotype case-control dataset for GWAS that can help researchers in both single SNP association and haplotype block-based association analysis. Geneticists who are interested in the genetic associations, drug developers, and data analysts who deal with big data can benefit from this data for the MAF quality control study. NARAC data could be used in comparing data and results with other MAF values in big projects like UK-Biobank, EXAC, 1000GP, and HapMap to understand the pattern and the nature of SNP distribution and characteristics for qualitative and quantitative factors. NARAC is a case-control data for genome-wide analysis with a massive number of SNPs that could be applied for meta-analysis of GWAS. The description of this data could serve researchers in choosing MAF for their GWAS data by uncovering the pattern of MAF and help the researchers to predict the annotation based on MAF. The data consists of two

tables (Spreadsheet of comma-separated values file and map file). High throughput sequencing data obtained from NARAC using Illumina 550 k platform, HumanHap500 v1, HumanHap500 v3, HumanHap300, and HumanHap240 Illumina arrays. The data source institution is the University of Texas. Data providers send data for the authors for further analysis.

3.2. General Data Description

The high-throughput Genetic Analysis Workshop 16 (GAW16) Problem 1 dataset originated from NARAC consists of 545,080 SNPs from the entire genome [147]. NARAC dataset had been helping the researchers to find associated loci to RA [148]. Several associations have been proved by the NARAC dataset [149]–[154]. Autosomal SNPs are 531,689, and 13,395 are allosomal SNPs (located in the sex chromosomes). The SNPs are genotyped from 2,062 participants, including 868 cases and 1194 controls. Table 3.1 describes the gender and status of participants in detail.

Table 3.1: Gender and disease status description for the data.

	Cases	Controls	Total
Male	227	342	569
Female	641	852	1493
Total	868	1194	2,062

The data mainly consists of two files: the SNPs array file and the map file. Table 3.2 shows a sample of the SNPs’ array data; the first ten columns and fifteen rows of the SNPs array file of chromosome 21 as an example. The first seven rows are the first seven rows of dataset files. The second seven rows are taken randomly to show the variability of data. The first nine columns are descriptive information about the data. The first column is the ID of each participant. The second column is the affection column, describes the disease status: 1 for a case and 0 for control. The third column is for gender, where “M” for male and “F” for female. Columns from 4 to 9 are DRB1_1 for HLA-DRB1 allele, DRB1_2 for HLA-DRB1 allele 2, the number of shared epitopes (SE) carried the anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide (anti-CCP) test, and the rheumatoid factor Immunoglobulin M (IgM) level. The next columns from column 10 to column 8060 are the SNPs in chromosome 21. The number of columns is varying in each chromosome depending on the number of SNPs in the given chromosome. The DRB1 is a protein encoded by the HLA-DRB1 gene and plays a central role in the immune system [9]. The DRB has several shared

epitope alleles associated with rheumatoid arthritis [10]. “SENum” is the number of shared epitopes carried (NN = 0, SN = 1, SS = 2). Where SS for homozygous SE alleles, SN for heterozygous and NN for the absence of SE allele [11]. The SE status is the shared epitope status (yes or no). Column eight is for a result of the Anti-CCP test [6,7]. RFUW is the result of the rheumatoid factor IgM test from the University of Washington. The question mark “?” in the in anti-CCP and RFUW indicates missing valued. The genotyped SNPs data are in the format “X_X,” where X is a nitrogenous base (A, C, G, T) and ?_? is the code of missing SNP. In this work, we substantially focus on the genotypic data, i.e., the SNPs, since we describe the data exploration and pre-processing stages. So, during data analysis, we have omitted the first nine informative columns.

Table 3.2: Sample of the SNPs’ array data showing the information columns and one column of the SNPs. “F” for female,” M” for male, and “?” for missing data

Participant s ID	Affection	Sex	DRB1_1	DRB1_2	SE Num	SE Status	Anti- CCP	RFUW	rs1043988 4
D0024949	0	F	0101	0401	SS	yes	?	?	G_G
D0024302	0	F	0101	7	SN	yes	?	?	G_G
D0023151	0	F	0101	11	SN	yes	?	?	G_G
D0022042	0	F	0101	2	SN	yes	?	?	G_G
D0021275	0	F	0101	7	SN	yes	?	?	G_G
D0021163	0	F	0101	0403	SN	yes	?	?	G_G
D0020795	0	F	0101	3	SN	yes	?	?	G_G
6045201	1	F	0101	7	SN	yes	31.3	142	G_G
D0023027	0	M	0101	3	SN	yes	?	?	G_G
1015200	1	M	0101	0403	SN	yes	112.9	405	?_?
D0015941	0	F	2	7	NN	no	?	?	A_G
D0016405	0	F	0101	7	SN	yes	?	?	?_?
KNH763243	1	M	0404	0301	SN	yes	99	?	G_G
1074200	1	F	0101	1001	SS	yes	98.7	61	G_G

Table 3.3 is a sample of map files extracted from three chromosomes. The map file consists of three columns, the first column is for the chromosome number, the second for the reference SNP Identifier (rsID), and the third is for the physical location.

Table 3.3: Sample of the map file from three chromosomes data.

Chromosome	rsID	Position
1	rs3094315	792429
1	rs12562034	808311
11	rs3802985	188510
11	rs3741411	189256
21	rs2821850	13693682
21	rs2257226	13695103

3.3. Experimental data exploration

NARAC dataset comes in two compressed files for all chromosomes: the SNPs array file and the map file. We have split the row dataset into disjointed 23 matrices for the 23 pairs of chromosomes. The only 22 autosomal SNPs were picked up for description and pre-processing. The block diagram (Figure 3.3) expresses all steps performed for the exploration and description of the data. First, we have counted the number of cases and controls in males and females Separately as described previously in Table 3.1. Second, we have assessed the percentage of genotype missingness. Third, we have computed the distribution of the alleles and genotypes in each chromosome and the entire data. Fourth, we calculate the MAF of each SNP. Accordingly, the SNPs are classified into four categories [155], [156]. To find the effect of each MAF range, we used the effect variant predictor tool (EVP).

3.3.1. Missing data estimation

During the genotyping process, some genotypes are remaining undetected. We have demonstrated the missing SNPs by exploring the missing data in each chromosome, the percentage of missing data, and the average missing data throughout the 22 chromosomes. Table 3.4 displays the matrix size (No. SNPs \times No. Participants), the number of SNPs, and the missing data with its percentage. Since chromosome 2 is the chromosome that has the largest no. of genotyped SNPs

(44,090), it has the largest matrix size (90,913,580); on the contrary, chromosome 21 (8,051 SNPs) has the least matrix size (16,601,162). Chromosome 19 SNPs show the highest percentage of missing genotypes where chromosome 12 SNPs show the least percentage. The average of the missing data in the entire autosomal data is 0.7581 %.

Figure 3.1: System description of the NARAC dataset

Chapter 3: Data description and exploration

Table 3.4: The SNPs matrix size for every single chromosome, the corresponding number of missing genotypes in the matrix, and the percentage of missing data relative to the original SNP array size (missing data/matrix size $\times 100$). The bold font in the table highlights the maximum and minimum values. “Chr” refers to chromosome number.

	Matrix size SNPs \times Participants	No. SNPs	Missing data	The percentage of the missing data
Chr 1	84,395,598	40,929	<u>634,717</u>	0.7521 %
Chr 2	<u>90,913,580</u>	<u>44,090</u>	612,588	0.6738 %
Chr 3	75,654,780	36,690	534,345	0.7063 %
Chr 4	67,278,936	32,628	505,588	0.7515 %
Chr 5	69,307,944	33,612	496,649	0.7166 %
Chr 6	73,353,588	35,574	545,309	0.7434 %
Chr 7	60,301,128	29,244	456,646	0.7573 %
Chr 8	63,901,380	30,990	434,562	0.6801 %
Chr 9	53,875,936	26,128	379,790	0.7049 %
Chr 10	58,418,522	28,331	436,447	0.7471 %
Chr 11	54,595,574	26,477	413,160	0.7568 %
Chr 12	54,364,630	26,365	370,898	<u>0.6822 %</u>
Chr 13	41,739,004	20,242	290,775	0.6967 %
Chr 14	37,014,962	17,951	259,440	0.7009 %
Chr 15	33,334,292	16,166	228,269	0.6848 %
Chr 16	33,940,520	16,460	256,155	0.7547 %
Chr 17	28,923,674	14,027	247,550	0.8559 %
Chr 18	33,919,900	16,450	234,353	0.6909 %
Chr 19	19,044,632	9,236	235,114	<u>1.2345 %</u>
Chr 20	28,544,266	13,843	212,180	0.7433 %
Chr 21	<u>16,601,162</u>	<u>8,051</u>	127,582	0.7685 %
Chr 22	16,918,710	8,205	<u>148,207</u>	0.8760 %
Total	1,096,342,718	531,689	8,060,324	

3.3.2. Alleles and genotypes distribution

An allele is a form of the SNP at a locus; the four alleles are {A, C, G, and T}. A genotype is referred to a pair of alleles at a locus; the ten genotypes are {AA, AC, AG, AT, CC, CG, CT, GG, GT, and TT}. We count the number alleles and genotypes and their distributions over chromosomes. The pie charts presented in Figure 3.2 show the ratios of each allele and each genotype in the entire data.

Figure 3.2: a) The ratio of alleles in the dataset. b) The ratio of genotypes in the dataset. NA (not available) for missing data

We found that the "A" has the highest number alleles, and in the form of genotype, "AA" has the highest appearance frequency. The "T" allele does not appear at all in the whole dataset. Only three alleles from 4 alleles are found. Therefore, there is no "TT" genotype, or heterozygous genotype include the "T" allele. Thus, only five genotypes from the ten genotype combinations appear in all the 22 chromosomes. The interpretation of this finding is that the absence of "T" alleles could be due to the genotyping strategy. Illumina 550 k platform has two methods to designate SNPs consistently; the top (TOP) and bottom (BOT) designations [14]. NARAC data acquisition by Illumina was based on the TOP reading allele method [1,14]. The TOP designation does impart a strong bias towards TOP SNPs being coded as "A" The line chart is visualizing the pattern distribution of the genotypes over the chromosome (Figure 3.3).

At some points, the "AA" genotype is not the predominant genotype as in chromosome 19 and chromosome 22.

Figure 3.3: The line chart of the total genotype in each chromosome.

Thoroughly, Table 3.5 illustrates the total number of different genotypes in every single chromosome.

Table 3.5: The number of genotypes in each chromosome. The bold, underlined font indicates a different pattern of genotype distribution.

Chr number	<u>A_A</u>	<u>A_C</u>	<u>A_G</u>	<u>C_C</u>	<u>G_G</u>
Chr 1	26,711,789	4,679,998	21,573,287	5,415,320	25,380,487
Chr 2	29,387,008	5,344,696	23,395,413	5,944,536	26,229,339
Chr 3	24,434,880	4,577,379	19,483,580	4,954,827	21,669,769
Chr 4	21,808,914	4,003,871	17,215,774	4,481,729	19,263,060
Chr 5	22,220,079	4,076,066	17,843,069	4,468,676	20,203,405
Chr 6	23,359,865	4,107,270	18,836,266	4,775,374	21,729,504
Chr 7	19,492,287	3,419,232	15,711,607	3,762,752	17,458,604
Chr 8	20,752,359	3,966,195	16,203,455	4,356,741	18,188,068
Chr 9	17,151,884	3,368,748	13,698,956	3,643,776	15,632,782
Chr 10	18,187,731	3,367,975	14,824,804	3,937,084	17,664,481
Chr 11	16,959,638	3,241,818	13,991,250	3,763,034	16,226,674

Chr 12	17,447,409	3,119,705	13,887,874	3,548,997	15,989,747
Chr 13	13,452,880	2,437,565	10,576,597	2,767,172	12,214,015
Chr 14	11,768,072	2,125,190	9,442,896	2,480,514	10,938,850
Chr 15	10,706,328	1,950,093	8,647,270	2,214,684	9,587,648
Chr 16	10,555,211	2,133,220	8,691,439	2,301,504	10,002,991
Chr 17	8,739,076	1,599,478	7,699,901	1,747,699	8,889,970
Chr 18	10,861,749	1,990,102	8,696,911	2,190,454	9,946,331
Chr 19	5,478,691	1,047,547	5,109,706	1,160,977	6,012,597
Chr 20	8,818,815	1,580,480	7,410,244	1,788,390	8,734,157
Chr 21	5,080,859	1,004,138	4,313,524	1,113,977	4,961,082
Chr 22	5,021,364	901,120	4,480,904	989,707	5,377,408
Total	348,396,888	64,041,886	281,734,727	71,807,924	322,300,969

3.4. MAF over the entire data

The minor allele frequency (MAF) is the second most frequent allele. One of the most critical analyses of genotypic data is discarding loci with SNPs that have MAF below predefined thresholds [15,16]. Dropping MAF ensures that the SNPs are polymorphic and not appear by chance or mistake in the genotyping process. The following equation calculates MAF for a specific locus.

$$MAF = \frac{(n * 2) + t}{2(j + n + t)} \quad (2.1)$$

Where “n” represents the number of minor homozygotes, “j” is the number of major homozygotes, and “t” is the number of heterozygotes. SNPs that have MAF below 0.001 are very rare, SNPs that have MAF between 0.001 and 0.01 are rare SNPs, SNPs that have MAF between 0.01 and 0.05 are low-frequency SNPs, and SNPs that have MAF above 0.05 are common SNPs [81], [139], [155], [156]. Table 3.6 illustrate the number of SNPs in each class for all chromosomes. The finding indicates that the very rare and rare SNPs are approximately equal in numbers. The bold font in the table clarifies that some chromosomes have higher rare SNPs than very rare SNPs. In general, both very rare SNPs and rare SNPs represent 4.2% of all SNPs, while low-frequency SNPs are 5.3%, and the common SNPs are 90.5%.

Table 3.6: The number of very rare SNPs, rare SNPs, low-frequency SNPs, and common SNPs in all chromosomes. The bold underlined font highlights the chromosome where very rare SNPs are higher in number than the rare SNPs.

Chromosome number	Very rare SNPs	Rare SNPs	Low-frequency SNPs	Common SNPs	No. SNPs
Chr 1	940	972	2275	36742	40,929
Chr 2	<u>1064</u>	<u>975</u>	2281	39770	44,090
Chr 3	773	813	1790	33314	36,690
Chr 4	686	679	1783	30464	32,628
Chr 5	686	679	1783	30464	33,612
Chr 6	633	778	1953	32210	35,574
Chr 7	<u>560</u>	<u>545</u>	1532	26607	29,244
Chr 8	<u>722</u>	<u>667</u>	1701	27900	30,990
Chr 9	439	577	1317	23795	26,128
Chr 10	524	717	1547	25543	28,331
Chr 11	559	569	1347	24002	26,477
Chr 12	<u>573</u>	<u>548</u>	1402	23842	26,365
Chr 13	414	440	1198	18190	20,242
Chr 14	337	367	970	16277	17,951
Chr 15	292	378	887	14609	16,166
Chr 16	<u>358</u>	<u>313</u>	814	14975	16,460
Chr 17	<u>247</u>	<u>226</u>	681	12873	14,027
Chr 18	<u>389</u>	<u>342</u>	875	14844	16,450
Chr 19	113	126	438	8559	9,236
Chr 20	258	265	729	12591	13,843
Chr 21	106	153	393	7399	8,051
Chr 22	<u>168</u>	<u>142</u>	420	7475	8,205
Total	10905	11338	28067	481379	531,689
Percentage	2.0510%	2.1324%	5.2788%	90.5377%	100%

This data description is preparation for studying the effect of MAF on GWAS results. Figure 3.4 presents the histogram of the MAF distribution from 0 to 0.05; The upper right-side window is the zoomed view of the very rare, the rare, and the low-frequency SNPs. Although the number of common SNPs is more abundant than other categories in general, the very rare SNPs have a relatively high number of SNPs in a narrow range of MAF. The range from 0 to 0.001 MAF, which includes

very rare SNPs, has the highest frequency in the histogram, see the zoomed view. Extrapolating the bottom left side of the graph (Figure 3.4), the highest bar is in the range from 0 to 0.005, which includes the very rare SNPs and a portion of the rare ones. The rate then begins to decrease until it reaches the lower value at 0.015. The very rare seems that it is the cause of the high value in the comprehensive left graph. The low-frequency (0.01:0.05) range shows the lowest frequencies in general. Excluding SNPs with MAF= 0.001 while filtering SNPs will discard 2.05% of the total number of SNPs. The threshold of MAF = 0.01 discards 4.18% of the SNPs. While setting MAF= 0.05 will exclude 9.46% of the SNP data. The MAF histogram of the NARAC dataset is a right-skewed, and we test each chromosome individually, and they have the same trend as the comprehensive histogram. The histogram is similar to the histogram of the UK Biobank dataset [81] but with lower values in the range from (0.01:0.05). To find the effect of SNPs in each MAF category, we test its significance using the effect variant predictor (EVP) tool [157]. The SNPs fall in 18 varying types with different ratios for each type of annotation (see Table 1 of the appendix A, which shows the kinds of consequences annotation).

Figure 3.4: The histogram of the MAF distribution for all the SNPs of the NARAC dataset. The right graph is the zoomed view of the MAF from 0:0.05.

EVP tool provides the annotation and percentages of all regions of the variants (SNPs). The SNPs “rs”s are extracted from the map file and uploaded to the EVP for SNP annotation. Finding the annotation of each category shows the impact of

Figure 3.5: The first four pie charts are for all consequence’s regions. (a) the consequences of very rare SNPs, (b) the consequences of rare SNPs, (c) the consequences of the low-frequency SNPs (d) the consequences of common SNPs. The second four pie charts are for coding consequences. (e) the coding consequences of the very rare SNPs. (f) the coding consequences of the rare SNPs. (g) the coding consequences of the low-frequency SNPs. (h) the coding consequences of the common SNPs.

each frequency category in the chromosome region and physical functionality, consequently. Variants analysis could give a prediction for the functional areas which could predict the SNPs that have a potential impact. In this analysis, we have analyzed the SNPs of the whole genome at once, and separated chromosome, by pre-classified SNPs into four categories, as in the UK biobank [156]. We summarize the variant-type percentages of all consequences and the coding

Figure 3.6: (a) The all consequences distribution, (b) The coding consequences distribution.

consequences in pie-charts, as in Figure 3.5, which indicates the ratio of each variant type for the comprehensive annotation for each class for the total SNPs [157].

The results of separated chromosomes are described in Supplementary material, Tables 2-5 are for all consequences, and Tables 6-9 are for code consequences. The resulted tables lead to several observations about the pattern of the dataset: The SNPs are more common in introns regions. The low-frequency SNPs show the least intron variants. There is no splice region variant in the entire dataset except in the chromosome 20 SNPs with rare MAF. Missense variants appear more in common SNPs. The missense variant percentage is directly proportional to MAF. Where, The lower MAF, the higher the synonymous variant percentage. The following regions appear more in common SNPs: start lost, stop lost, stop gained, coding sequence variant and, incomplete terminal codon variant. In general, the common SNPs are more likely to be in the coding and functional regions than other categories. We found in general that the common SNPs are the most significant areas. See the supplementary material for more details and information.

The distribution consequences of all SNPs of each portion over the 22 chromosomes are illustrated by line-chart in fig. 6. The distribution of all effects is shown in Figure 3.6 (a). The following categories are neglected because they represent a little small portion: TF- binding side variant, 3-prime UTR variant, missense variants, synonymous, and others. The introns and non-coding variants are the dominant regions. Figure 3.6 (b) is for coding consequences, and the trend is interchanging dominance between the missense and synonymous variants.

3.5. Conclusion

This chapter provides a descriptive analysis for a high throughput case-control genotyped dataset produced by NARAC. The percentage of missing data for each chromosome was calculated, and it ranged between 0.68% and 1.23%. The statistical calculations demonstrate the pattern and distribution of the genotypes, alleles, and their MAF. The allele "T" was absent in all data; however, it may be because of the genotyping process, yet it is still questionable. The SNPs are classified according to the MAF to find the effect of each range. The consequences of the SNPs were obtained by the EVP tool. The descriptive data were presented in tables, pie charts, bar charts, and line charts.

Chapter 4

Data pre-processing and quality control

4.1. Introduction

In recent years, the advent of fast genotyping and high-throughput sequencing technologies has increased the availability and accessibility of dens SNP-arrays. The large-scale genotype data has opened new avenues of genome-wide analysis, empirical association studies, and numerous researches for population genetics [158]. Yet, dealing with such genome-scale big data that consist of millions or even billions of genotypes is a considerable burden and time-consuming [159]. We have presented the dataset and uncovered its pattern and properties in chapter 3 earlier. The raw data is unsuitable for haplotype block partition and many genetic analyses. The pre-processing is a crucial step to prepare any data for considerable analysis. In this chapter, we shall present the proposed pre-processing steps and quality-control techniques that have been adopted. The pre-processing step confirms that the dataset is applicable for the subsequent analyses and suitable for several platforms. Although this step takes a prolonged time, it is necessary to get a handle on the nature of the data to ensure the data quality and to build a robust and flexible work sequence. The pre-processed data will be easily applied to imputation methods, BigLD block partitioning under R and Haploview.

4.2. System description

Figure 4.1 is a scheme that summarizes all the pre-processing steps from the raw data into an output that would be fitting for further analysis. As explored in chapter 3, NARAC data consists of 545,080 SNPs from the entire genome of 2,062 participants [147]. The entire raw data come as two files, the SNPs array file, and the map file. Initially, we have separated the dataset into 23 files for the 23 chromosomes using Perl programming language. Our study and analysis is just based only on the autosomal SNPs because allosome pairs have different structures, two X chromosomes in females and one X and one Y chromosome in males [160], [161]. We neglected the allosome SNPs and worked only on the 22 chromosomes. The number of SNPs in the sex chromosomes are 13,395. After excluding the chromosome 23 SNPs we end up with 531,689 SNPs. Generally, we have reformatted the data, imputed the missing data, recode the data to fit the haplotype block partitioning methods; The BigLD under R programming language and the Haploview which includes three methods.

Figure 4.1: Summary of the pre-processing system and experimental design

4.3. Overview of the raw data and Proposed Pre-processing Algorithm

The first nine descriptive columns -which defined earlier in chapter 3- were truncated since the SNPs' data is targeted in the pre-processing step. Table 4.1 and Table 4.2 are sample of the row data, Table 4.1 is a portion of the chromosome 21 SNPs matrix raw data after removing the information columns. The size of the SNPs matrices is 1,096,342,718 (531,689 SNPs \times 2,062 participants). Each cell in the matrix is five length character vectors which are: whitespace, the letter of the first allele, then underscore, the letter of the second allele and whitespace. The missing data is represented by “?_?”.

Chapter 4: Data pre-processing and quality control

Table 4.1: A sample of the row dataset from chromosome 21 after trucking the information columns. The genotypes appear in the format where there is an underscore between the characters. “?_?” is for missing data.

rs10439884	rs2260810	rs1296971	rs2257224	rs2257224	rs10439884
G_G	A_A	A_A	G_G	G_G	G_G
G_G	A_A	A_A	G_G	G_G	G_G
G_G	A_A	A_A	G_G	G_G	G_G
G_G	A_A	A_A	A_A	A_A	G_G
G_G	A_A	A_A	G_G	G_G	G_G
G_G	A_A	A_A	G_G	G_G	G_G
G_G	A_A	A_A	G_G	G_G	G_G
G_G	G_G	C_C	A_G	A_G	G_G
A_G	A_G	A_C	A_G	A_G	A_G
A_G	A_G	A_C	G_G	G_G	A_G
?_?	A_G	A_C	A_G	A_G	?_?
G_G	A_G	A_C	G_G	G_G	G_G

Table 4.2 is a sample of the map file from extracted three different chromosomes. Map file consists of three columns, the first column is for the chromosome number, the second for the reference SNP Identifier (rsID), and the third is for the physical location.

Table 4.2: Sample of the map file from three different chromosomes data.

Chromosome	rsID	Position
1	rs3094315	792429
1	rs12562034	808311
11	rs3802985	188510
11	rs3741411	189256
21	rs2821850	13693682
21	rs2257226	13695103

In the subsequent sections we shall illustrate all step of pre-processing in details and present the output of each step with tables. The main outlines are reformatting the data for imputation, Imputing the missing data and recoding the data in 0,1,2 format for further analysis, applying the quality control filtration based on MAF, finally, reformatting the data to be suitable for different haplotype block partition methods.

4.4. Reformatting the data

Reformatting we need to manipulate the string data in each cell. This step takes prolonged time because first, we need to scan 5,481,713,590 characters (total number of cells $1,096,342,718 \times$ the length of the string). The row data format is not suitable for many genetic analysis tools. For instance, to pre-process the data for Imputation, initially, we have removed the underscore between alleles and recode missing data from “?_?” to “NA”. We generate the translation code using "Stringr" package with R version 6.3 [162]. The processing time of this step takes 336 hours using Core i7-8550U CPU @1.80 GHz 1.99 GHz processor, RAM 16 GB, 64-bit operating system x64 based processor. Table 4.3 displays sample of the SNP matrix after reformatting, we show the first four SNPs as in Table 4.2. Briefly, a matrix of the first four SNPs of chromosome 21 and 12 individuals is chosen for describing the pre-process steps. This format is suitable now that is ready for imputation. The missing data is shown by bold font.

Table 4.3: The reformatted sample for preparing the data for imputation. The missing value is spotlighted by bold font.

rs10439884	rs2260810	rs1296971	rs2257224
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	AA
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	GG	CC	AG
AG	AG	AC	AG
AG	AG	AC	GG
NA	AG	AC	AG
GG	AA	AA	GG

4.5. Imputation and recoding

Imputation is a feasible process to overcome the defect of missing data by inferring untyped genotypes based on neighboring SNPs [163], [164]. Not all tools are practically executable with missing data [137]. Data imputation completes the coverage of the SNPs and facilitates the genome-wide analysis by combining the

results genotypes that depend on different genotyping platforms. We recode the data and impute the missing genotypes using the R package "Synbreed" that based on marginal allele distribution [165], [166]. The missing SNPs for a given locus are sampled from the marginal allele distribution. Values are sampled from the given distribution:

$$P(x = 0) = (1 - p)^2 \quad (4.2)$$

$$P(x = 1) = p(1 - p) \quad (4.2)$$

$$P(x = 2) = p^2 \quad (4.3)$$

Where p is the MAF of a given SNP, x is the output predicted value supposing Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) for applied dataset [165]. Dataset should be re-coded in terms of the number of minor alleles rather than biallelic markers to be suitable for block partitioning algorithms. Three genotypes per locus are produced 0, 1 and 2 i.e. homozygous major allele coded as 0 (eq. 4.1), heterozygous allele coded as 1 (eq.4.2), and homozygous minor allele coded as 2 (eq. 4.3). Table is the sampled data after imputation in the biallelic format.

Table 4. 4: The sampled data after imputation in biallelic format.

rs10439884	rs2260810	rs1296971	rs2257224
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	AA
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	AA	AA	GG
GG	GG	CC	AG
AG	AG	AC	AG
AG	AG	AC	GG
GG	AG	AC	AG
GG	AA	AA	GG

Table 4.5 is the sampled data after recoding where 0 is for major homozygous genotype, 1 for the heterozygous genotype, and 2 for the minor homozygous genotype.

4.6. Preparing data for BigLD

The recoded format presented in Table 4.5 is convenient to undergo the BigLD haplotype block partitioning and several genetic analyses. Data imputation completes the coverage of the SNPs and facilitates the genome-wide analysis by combining the results genotypes that depend on different genotyping platforms. We recode the data and impute the missing genotypes using the R package “Synbreed” that is based on marginal allele distribution [165], [166].

Table 4.5: Sampled data after imputation and recoding.

rs10439884	rs2260810	rs1296971	rs2257224
0	0	2	2
0	0	2	2
0	0	2	2
0	0	2	0
0	0	2	2
0	0	2	2
0	0	2	2
0	2	0	1
1	1	1	1
1	1	1	2
1	1	1	1
0	0	2	2

The pre-processed data is saved as a genotype object that combines the SNPs array and the corresponding map file. The new map matrix that defines the SNP genotypes is presented in Table 4.6. The filter SNPs’ arrays thus become valid for haplotype block partitioning. The data format in Table 4.5 is convenient to undergo the BigLD haplotype block partitioning and several genetic analyses. The sampled data after imputation in biallelic markers are shown in Table 4.4. The pre-processed data is saved as a genotype object that combines the SNPs array and the corresponding map file. The filter SNPs’ arrays thus become valid for haplotype block partitioning.

Table 4.6: The sample map file with defined genotypes in each locus. “Refer.” is the reference genotype, also called minor homozygous. “Heter.” For the heterozygous genotype and “Alter.” for the alternative genotype, which also called the minor homozygous

rsID	Chr	Position	Refer.	Heter.	Alter.
rs10439884	21	9993822	GG	AG	AA

rs2260810	21	13562271	AA	AG	GG
rs1296971	21	13609442	CC	AC	AA
rs2257224	21	13690214	AA	AG	GG

4.7. Recoding the data for Haploview

Ultimately, we prepare the data into the final format to fit the Haploview input format. The Haploview input takes up two columns for every single genotype; one for each allele. Table 4.7 shows the sampled in input Haploview format. The data is a non-family based data, so the same ID has been appointed for the family ID, and the individual ID in the first two columns and paternal and maternal IDs have been set as “0” in the third and fourth columns. The Individual’s gender was assigned 1 for male and 2 for female in the fifth column. The sixth column is for the affection status to be used for association tests; the controls =1 and cases =2. The rest of the columns are for marker genotypes. Each marker is represented by two columns, one for each allele. and coded as the following: 1=A, 2=C, 3=G, and 4=T [101].

Table 4.7: The sample of the input format for the Haploview

Family name	Individual ID	Father's ID	Mother's ID	Gender	Affection status	rs10439884	rs10439884	rs2260810	rs2260810	rs1296971	rs1296971
D0024949	D0024949	0	0	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	1
D0024302	D0024302	0	0	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	1
D0023151	D0023151	0	0	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	1
D0022042	D0022042	0	0	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	1
D0021275	D0021275	0	0	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	1
D0021163	D0021163	0	0	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	1
D0020795	D0020795	0	0	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	1
D0020691	D0020691	0	0	2	1	3	3	3	3	2	2
D0019121	D0019121	0	0	2	1	1	3	3	1	1	2
D0018942	D0018942	0	0	2	1	1	3	3	1	1	2
D0016405	D0016405	0	0	2	1	3	3	3	1	1	2
D0016076	D0016076	0	0	2	1	3	3	3	1	1	2

4.8. Minor allele frequency quality control

As we have discussed in chapter 3, that the MAF is an essential quality control procedure that filters variants to ensure that the SNPs are not accidentally acquired during genotyping. Also, MAF gives information to differentiate between common and rare variants in the population [156]. The MAF is the frequency at which the second commonest allele occurs in a given sample or population and expressed as a fraction or percentage. For example, if there are 3 alleles, with frequencies of 0.60, 0.35, and 0.05, the MAF will be 0.35 [17,18,19]. MAF measurement allows only common variants to be considered in a dataset and discarding rare variants that have low contribution and more may occur by the chance in a population [90]. MAF can be any number below 0.5 at any bi-allelic position in the genome [167,168]. If the MAF is less than 0.001 on the site, it is considered a rare mutation and no longer considered as a common SNP in a given population. Variants with MAF values from 0.01 to 0.05 are low-frequency variants [169,172]. Genetic analysis and studies generally apply MAF because it contributes to distinguishing between common and rare variants. Geneticists tend to trunk rare SNPs with MAF below certain point commonly 0.05 as a popular technique of minimizing errors in big SNPs sequence datasets. Although SNPs with very low MAF are less informative, some studies reported that rare variants with $MAF < 0.05$ have manifested more frequently in coding regions than common variants [21,22,14,23]. Based on the natural selection theory, some researchers assume that the rarest variant tends to be deleterious [169]. Therefore, low-frequency variants can contribute significantly to the genetic structure of disease. [18,7,20]. Initially, we have chosen the SNPs with $MAF \geq 0.05$ as it was commonly used in many studies and targeted in the HapMap project in all its phases [91], [172]–[174]. HapMap followed by the KGP which was the first project that has sequenced the genomes of thousands of individuals to detect human genetic variations. A lower threshold of MAF was adopted by KGP and SNPs with frequencies up to 0.01 were detected. KGP has adopted 0.01 MAF from the pilot phase till phase 3 where 2,504 different ethnic individuals were targeted [27,28,29,30,31,32]. 0.01 and 0.05 are the commonest two values of MAF that are selected in the vast majority of genetic analysis studies [34, 23]. Other values of MAF are adopted like 0.005 [181], 0.02 [182] and 0.03 [183]. MAF threshold has impact on many aspects in genetics, i.e. it can affect the genomics database structure [38,39]. Some GWAS studies have reported that MAF differs in the control group than in the case group. Caroline et al. in 2017 has found that cases have a higher MAF than controls in GWAS [186].

The most common SNPs are common in all population, but rare ones are depending on a population. Furthermore, MAF differ in different ethnic groups. The same loci have different MAF according to the population [41,42].

In 2019, Saad et al. studied the effect of partitioning methods on RA association analysis [146]. Different haplotype block partitioning methods were utilized to select one of them to partition the NARAC dataset. A significant block was detected using two different methods, which are CIT and SSLD. Interestingly, while the detected block's size was the same for the two methods (87 Kbp), the number of the SNPs inside each block was different (8 SNPs) in the CIT block and (12 SNPs) in the SSLD block. This discrepancy was due to the MAF threshold of the two methods. The MAF threshold for The CIT method (0.05) was larger than that of the SSLD method (0.001). The result was discarding four influential SNPs by the CIT method for their low MAF. Accordingly, MAF has a significant effect on haplotype block outcomes. This debate was the initial spark for us to investigate the role of MAF on haplotype block partitioning.

We have excluded SNPs that have with MAF less than five predefined thresholds (0.001, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, and 0.1). We end up with 5 SNPs' arrays for each chromosome with their correlative map file. The excluded SNPs are not probably polymorphic and could be appeared by a fault in data acquisition. Essentially, loci with low a MAF were discarded before any genetic analysis as a procedure or preprocessing the data.

Figure 4.2 shows the number of SNPs resulted after applying various MAF thresholds to our experimental data. In this study, we have utilized the five MAF thresholds, each with four different recent haplotype block partitioning methods. Trying to answer the question: Is MAF data manipulation preprocessing can influence the ultimate characteristics of haplotype block partitioning. We have done a deep survey on the effect of MAF on haplotype blocks, but we did not find a clear answer on this point. In the next chapter, we shall present the proposed haplotype block partitioning methods, the post-processing steps to normalize the outputs, and the measured parameters that we adapted to compare the methods and the MAF thresholds.

Figure 4.2: The number of SNPs after applying different MAF thresholds.

4.9. Conclusion

In this empirical study, we have shown the detailed steps for preparing high-density data of 1,096,342,718 genotyped SNPs. Reformatting, imputation, and recoding data into several genotype formats were conducted as a beforehand process. Our sequence of pre-processing includes preparing the character to be n form that is suitable for Imputation which has solved the problem of missing data. The next step is recording data in 0,1,2 format to be ideal for the BigLD. The proposed approach explains how to deal with such a big dataset, which makes it suitable for haplotype block partitioning. We were eventually preparing data for Haploview that can provide clear haplotype block partitioning, association analysis, and furthermore.

Our pre-processing steps pose as a practical guide for the researchers and geneticists who want to make similar analyses. We have gathered all codes and build them under the R programming language, which simplified the process and the workflow. This paper evokes a vivid image of how to pre-process genome-wide data under a personal computer environment in a clearly defined manner. The entire time computing was relatively long; about 750 hours; Thus, in the future work, the parallel computing should be considered. Nowadays, the high throughput genome-scale data are available more than any time before. So, it is essential to address such

data to exploit them and focus on understanding and preparing them in different forms, which eventually help to utilize them.

This study tends to answer several questions regarding MAF. Is it worthy to consider low MAF in complex traits association studies? To how much degree MAF affects the pattern of variation structure in the genome? How MAF affect haplotype block partitioning. We conduct this study over 4 different common haplotype block partitioning methods on whole genome genotyped dataset; NARAC dataset using different MAF thresholds (0.001, 0.02, 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1). In the end of the study we provide some recommendation when choosing MAF threshold in haplotype block partitioning. The novelty of this work that there no direct relationship found between MAF and Haplotype block partitioning and LD. We want to reveal it and uncover the effect of MAF.

Chapter 5

Proposed methods for haplotype block partitioning

In recent years, the advent of fast genotyping and high-throughput sequencing technologies has increased the availability and accessibility of dens SNP-arrays. The large-scale genotype data has opened new avenues of genome-wide analysis, empirical association studies, and numerous researches for population genetics [158]. Yet, dealing with such genome-scale big data that consist of millions or even billions of genotypes is a considerable burden and time-consuming [159]. We have presented the dataset and uncovered its pattern and properties in chapter 3 earlier. Since the raw dataset is unsuitable for haplotype block partition and many genetic analyses, we have shown the adopted pre-processing steps and quality-control technique in chapter 4. In this chapter, we shall present the proposed haplotype block partitioning method. We also made a comparative study of the most popular and recent haplotype block partitioning methods. Finally, we have investigated the role of MAF quality control on block partitioning.

5.1. System description

Figure 5.1 present the block diagram of the system description. The upper part of the flow chart is described earlier in chapter 4. Initially, the proposed system preprocesses the dataset to permit the subsequent analysis. The data were reformatting, imputer, and recoded. Both processed genotyped data files and map files were applied to the block partitioning algorithms. The lower part of the flowchart summarizes the sequence of haplotype block partitioning and the comparative analysis of the methods and MAF thresholds. As we have presented in a literature review in chapter 2, current methods are more applicable, especially in computational time. We have chosen four of the recent haplotype block partitioning methods, which are the BigLD, CIT, FGT, and SSLD, under R and Haploview.

Along with our study, we have investigated the role of MAF in haplotype block partitioning. After applying the four haplotype block partitioning methods with the five MAF thresholds, we have evaluated the results using ten parameters. Our evaluation was based on the following parameters: the total number of blocks, total number of SNPs in all blocks, the total length of all blocks, mean number of SNPs in blocks, mean block length in base pair, the mean r^2 within blocks, the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks, the mean r^2 between consecutive all blocks and the intersection percentage.

Figure 5.1: The block diagram of the system description

As we have discussed in the previous chapters, understanding LD's patterns across the human genome, especially its block-like structures, has interested many researchers in genetics because it provides useful insight for disease association mapping and population genetics. It has been observed that LD block regions can vary in size, and strong LD extends over each block region until it breaks down abruptly, possibly due to recombination hotspots or population genetic phenomenon. Recombination, mutation, selection, or other evolutionary histories can affect LD block patterns in the aspects of location and length of blocks [55]. Therefore, identifying the haplotype blocks can provide evidential groundings for population genetic arguments and necessary information for the design and analysis of genetic association studies for complex diseases. As we presented in chapter 2, researchers have proposed several methods to determine the haplotype blocks. In this research, we have chosen four of the latest and the most common methods of haplotype block partitioning; BigLD under R and CIT, FGT, and SSLD under Haploview. Additionally, we invested the rule of MAF on LD block portioning.

5.2. Proposed Method Based on Interval Graph Modeling

As we have presented in chapter 2, the Big-LD algorithm was developed in 2018. BigLD is based on interval graph modeling of strong pairwise LD clusters [137]. The algorithm has adopted a hierarchical clustering, which means a pair of markers are successively linked to produce larger clusters based on the distance similarity. In discrete mathematics, graph theory is a study of mathematical structures to model pairwise relations [189]. The graph is a set of objects links together in which some pairs are related. The object corresponds to mathematical abstractions referred to as vertex; the connected lines are called edges [190]. Figure 5.2 illustrates the graph theory by an example where $G = (V, E)$, $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ is a set of vertices and $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ is a set of edges. Wherever two vertices are linked with an edge, the two points are incident with an edge and the two vertices are adjacent.

Figure 5.2: A graph with three vertices and three edges.

The degree of a vertex refers to the number of edges incident to a vertex. The graph (H) is a subgraph of G since its edge set, and the vertex set are formed from G (Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3: The subgraph in graph theory illustration

H is supposed to be induced by a vertex group S of G if two points in H are adjacent in H at whatever they are adjacent in G. The interval graph is formed by building a set of intervals as lines. Each interval corresponds to a vertex, and the intervals intersect are determined by the edges (see Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4: An example of five intervals on the real line and the corresponding five-vertex interval graph.

A graph with a weight assigned to each edge the graph is called an edge-weighted graph and expressed as $G = (V, E, w_E)$. A subset of vertices is called a clique when every two vertices in the subset are adjacent [191]. Cliques have been

used on constructions on graphs and, therefore, in many applications, especially in bioinformatics [139], [192]. The clique that is not included in any other clique is called a maximal clique, and the clique with the maximum size in the graph is called the largest clique. BigLD assumed the additive genetic model where the homozygous allele has twice the phenotypic contribution of heterozygous, and each allele act independently. Non-additive genetic models include the dominance of an allele. BigLD measures the pairwise LD using the Pearson correlation coefficient r^2 between two genotypes. The edge-weighted-graph is constructed based on the SNPs and their correlation. The SNPs constitute the vertices and the correlation between every two are represented by edges with a weight that equals to the r^2 between two SNPs. Although the LD between two SNPs usually decreases as the distance increases [193], a set of strongly linked SNPs can be constructed be non-consecutive SNPs. The LD bin is a set of strongly correlated SNPs; each included SNP is strongly linked with all SNPs [137]. BigLD mainly depends on the CLQ algorithm developed by Yoo et al. [139]. CLQ algorithm divides SNPs into LD bins by applying a greedy clique partitioning. The algorithm computes graph's all maximal cliques, and the largest clique is identified as the first LD bin. The previously captured SNPs as the LD bin were then removed. The process is repeated until identifying all LD bins. BigLD is based on interval graph modeling of clusters where the intervals represent the LD bins.

Figure 5.5 summarizes the main steps of BigLD in a brief shot block diagram. Thus, big-LD is based on an agglomerative approach that begins with identifying small groups of SNPs in each LD bin region and then proceeds by combining these groups. The resulted haplotype blocks can be visualized as map charts. Big LD considers the association between highly linked SNP pairs that have in-between low LD regions and not necessarily physically consecutive. This strategy prevents creating multiple small haplotype blocks with high associations between blocks. Besides, Kim et al. have proven by experiments that it matches better with the physical hotspots. Above all, the computing time of BigLD is incomparable faster than any haplotype partitioning method [137]. Accordingly, we have adopted the interval graph modeling algorithm as the first applied method in this empirical study. Then we partition the haplotype blocks using other three common methods for comparison and evaluation process.

For us to apply the BigLD algorithm, the data must be complete without untyped SNPs. The preprocessing steps mentioned in chapter 4 was inevitable to processed in haplotype block partitioning with such a method.

Figure 5.5: The block diagram of BigLD method

We have made the genome-wide analysis using BigLD five-time, each time with a different MAF threshold. The inputs to BigLD are the map file and the SNPs array file. The map file identifies the rsID, SNPs' physical position on a chromosome, and the genotypes description (the reference genotype, the heterozygous genotype, and the alternative genotype). The SNPs array file has to be in a 0,1,2 format. Table 5.1 shows a sample of the resulted in haplotype blocks using the BigLD algorithm. The sampled data are from chromosome 21, and the MAF threshold was 0.5. Columns two and three are the start and end indices of the haplotype blocks. The next two are the start and end SNP's rsID. The final two columns are the start and end base pairs in a given haplotype block. By applying the BigLD algorithm in a genome-scale level with five MAF thresholds, we have ended up with 110 tables. In this study, we have measured various parameters on the given results to make a feasible evaluation. The parameters will be discussed in detail in the next sections.

Table 5.1: A sample of the resulted haplotype blocks using BigLD for chromosome 21.

Chr	Start index	End index	Start rsID	End rsID	Start bp	End bp
21	4	7	rs2257224	rs455947	13690214	13707489
21	12	15	rs2821945	rs3855691	13865210	13895773
21	17	18	rs2792379	rs2775862	14027356	14059449
21	20	23	rs2258197	rs1985740	14087640	14095717

We have plotted and presented the haplotype blocks by heatmap plot. Figure 5.6 illustrates the heatmap of the proposed method for the portion from 13,690,214 to 13,695,103 bp in chromosome 21. This portion, as illustrated, has five haplotype blocks.

Figure 5.6: Heatmap for the haplotype blocks detected by interval graph modeling of clusters for a portion of chromosome 21 from 9,993,822 bp to 14,137,685 bp.

5.3. CIT

As we have mentioned in chapter 2 the CI or confidence interval test (CIT) is developed in 2002 by Gabriel et al. The method is commonly used until now on the Haploview platform. The method is based on measuring the D' between a pair of SNPs to estimate the LD [106]. The haplotype block then is specified a region where

a limited portion ($\leq 5\%$) of the calculations among the SNPs are in weak LD. The algorithm begins with classifying each pair of SNPs into one of three categories according to D' . The first category is the “strong LD” if the upper confidence interval 95% for D' is greater than 0.98 and the lower limit is more than 0.7. The second category is “strong evidence for historical recombination” which result when the upper confidence limit of D' is lower than 0.9. Elsewhere result in the third category “noninformative”. When the first two conditions have been met the pairs said to be informative. After all SNP pairs are classified, the haplotype blocks are defined wherever the peripheral SNP pairs are in the “strong LD” category. CIT have adopted a greedy algorithm to obtain the optimal haplotype blocks. The optimization approach depends on finding the longest block by testing the proportion of the “strong LD” SNP pairs in whole informative SNP pairs located between peripheral SNPs. CIT algorithm adds blocks that do not overlap with the previously taken blocks. Since we apply the method under Haploview platform, its output is a text output file [101]. Table 5.2 illustrates a sample of resulted haplotype blocks on chromosome 21 for SNPs with MAF >0.05 .

Table 5. 2: Haplotype text output file sample resulted by applying CIT on a Haploview.

BLOCK 1. MARKERS: 4 5 6
132 (0.473) 0.277 0.124 0.074
311 (0.467) 0.262 0.114 0.092
112 (0.036) 0.011 0.017 0.008
Multiallelic D prime: 0.054
BLOCK 2. MARKERS: 22 23
33 (0.564) 0.365 0.122 0.076
13 (0.259) 0.103 0.052 0.104
31 (0.175) 0.083 0.075 0.017
Multiallelic D prime: 0.238
BLOCK 3. MARKERS: 26 27
33 (0.551) 0.242 0.174 0.136
13 (0.252) 0.124 0.078 0.049
11 (0.197) 0.081 0.077 0.038
Multiallelic D prime: 0.068
BLOCK 4. MARKERS: 34 35
33 (0.446) 0.313 0.040 0.093
31 (0.328) 0.209 0.064 0.055
11 (0.223) 0.120 0.096 0.006
Multiallelic D prime: 0.189
BLOCK 5. MARKERS: 39 40
31 (0.644) 0.322 0.323 0.000
33 (0.201) 0.015 0.003 0.183
13 (0.155) 0.155 0.000 0.000
Multiallelic D prime: 0.669

The output displays the blocks with its index, the included SNPs, the haplotypes with their frequencies, the matrix of the crossover percentages and the multiallelic D' prime. In the previous example, block 1 has 3 SNPs (4, 5 and 6) and 3 haplotypes (AGC,GAA, and AAC). The alleles (A, C, G, and T) are represented by numbers as (1, 2, 3, and 4) respectively. The matrix of the crossover percentages shows the haplotypes in the rows and the next block's haplotypes in the columns . The same text file is obtained by Haploview for the FGT and SSLD.

5.4. FGT

The FGT developed by Wang et al. detects the historical recombination events. FGT supposes that recombination events do not exist within the block [56]. Whenever the four gametes are determined, it is a sign of the existence of a recombination event. The rare gamete must be specified at least 0.01 frequency to estimate a recombination event. The recombination events are allowed only between haplotype blocks. Therefore, FGT contrary to other methods does not require a threshold for D' or r^2 . The testing process is stopped when a recombination event is observed, and the last SNP assumed to be the ending of the given block.

5.5. SSLD

In Haploview platform, the haplotype blocks can be determined by a third method which is SSLD. Here, the haplotype block defined as a group of SNPs that has strong LD with the peripheral SNPs in the block [101]; the first and last SNPs in the should have strong linkage ($D' > 0.8$) with all intermediate SNPs. However, the intermediate SNPs not necessarily have strong LD with each other. The name solid spine indicates that a spine of strong linkage running from one SNP to another along the edge of the triangle in the LD chart. Figure 5.7 shows an example of haplotype block by SSLD definition where all SNPs in the block are highly linked with the first and last SNPs and the included SNPs are not necessarily linked.

Figure 5.8: Representative example of SSLD definition for haplotype block.

5.6. Post-processing process

After applying the four previous method each with five MAF thresholds to the 22 chromosomes, we have ended up with 440 files (110 tables resulted by BigLD and 330 text files resulted by Haploview). The BigLD tables format was represented previously in Table 5.1 and the Haploview haplotype test file was represented in table 5.2. A data normalization and post-processing are necessary to standardize the output and facilitate the comparative analysis. We have adopted several measurands to validate the proposed methods, to compare the outputs of each of them and to find the role of MAF on haplotype blocks. We have standardized the Haploview text output file to meet to BigLD output table. Table 5.3 is a sample of the normalized data resulted by CIT for chromosome 21 SNPs with $MAF > 0.05$; the same results of Table 5.2 after normalization.

Table 5.3: A sample of normalized haplotype text output file resulted by applying CIT on a Haploview to chromosome 21 SNPs ($MAF > 0.05$).

Chr	Start index	End index	Start rsID	End rsID	Start bp	End bp
21	4	6	rs2257224	rs2257226	13690214	13695103
21	22	23	rs743067	rs1985740	14092050	14095717
21	26	27	rs3115511	rs3115512	14136579	14137685
21	34	35	rs2822383	rs2822391	14322489	14334270
21	39	40	rs2822404	rs8133096	14396024	14398761

5.7. Evaluation parameters

To make a meaningful comparison and to interpret the results in a clear way, we have measured and calculated the evaluation parameters. We have found no previous studies addressing the role of MAF on haplotype block partitioning. However, we have reviewed previous studies and investigated the measurands used in describing the haplotype blocks. In this section we discuss the chosen parameters, its indications, how and why we have considered each of them in the analysis. Ten different parameters have been suggested and calculated: the total number of haplotype blocks, the total number of blocks with considering singleton blocks, total number of SNPs in all blocks, the total length of all blocks (bp), mean number of SNPs in blocks, the mean block length (bp), the mean r^2 within blocks, the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks, the mean r^2 within blocks, the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without considering singleton blocks, the mean r^2 between

consecutive blocks with considering singleton blocks and the intersection percentage. Additionally, we have measured the computational time of the methods.

The number of haplotype block is one of the first parameters that measured from the first discovery of the haplotype blocks [62]. Many research studies have used this parameter to evaluate the haplotype blocks [136], [194]–[196]. The smaller is the number of haplotypes blocks the greater is the reduction rate. The main idea of haplotype block is to find the relationships among SNPs and reduce the biomarker. Having indicated small number haplotype blocks that include the significant SNPs optimize the association studies by reduce the time, computation, and cost. The number of haplotype blocks indicates the number of recombination events. Thus, this parameter can indicate historical implications. Therefore, researchers also measure the total number of blocks to compare between species and populations [194], [195], [197]. In this parameter we only consider the haplotype blocks of two SNPs or more. The second parameter is the total number of blocks with considering the singleton blocks. The singleton block means the LD block with only one SNPs [198]. All SNPs which do not belong to the haplotype block output result are singleton blocks. This parameter indicates the total number of haplotypes since the haplotypes could be singleton haplotypes or groups of haplotypes [199]. Such parameter serves in a GWAS analyses [200]. We calculated the total size of all blocks in term of SNPs and base pairs. To be more precise in our measurement and look deeply in the pattern of blocks we have calculated the mean number SNPs in blocks and mean block length in base pair. All previous parameters provide a morphological description of the resulted haplotype blocks.

In order to measure the correlation within SNPs and blocks, we calculated the mean r^2 within blocks, the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks (without singleton blocks), and the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks (with singleton blocks). The measured parameters are widely used in various genetic and association studies [68], [136], [201], [202].

Moreover, to find the similarity among the different methods we have calculated the intersection percentage. Finally, we compare the computational times of all methods and with each MAF threshold.

In our previous publication we have made a comparative study of the four methods in a chromosomal level. Other parameters have been calculated such the maximum number of SNPs in blocks, the percentage of uncovered SNPs, the median number of SNPs within each block and the median block size (in bp) and the intersection percentage among methods [107]. Figure 5.8 shows a sample of haplotype blocks in chromosome 21 partitioned by the four methods and the intersections among them. The plot shows a sample from chromosomes 21 from SNPs with physical position 9993822 to 14425877 and the regions of intersection which all methods agree.

Figure 5.8: Plot of a sample of chromosome 21 LD blocks produced by FGT, CI, SSLD and BigLD

We suggest that the measured parameters are adequate to describe the results in an optimal way. In the next chapter, we'll get to see how we examined the results and our suggestions and interpretations that lead to more understand the pattern of haplotype blocks and the effect of MAF.

Chapter 6

Results and Discussion

After we have presented the proposed methods and the applied parameters to compare the results in chapter 5, in this chapter, we shall present and discuss all results comprehensively. The detailed, precise results are shown in tables in appendix B and the detailed charts in appendix C. We have chosen the following parameters for the evaluation and the comparative study.

6.1 The total number of haplotype blocks

The number of haplotype block indicates number of genetic events. The more it matches with the recombination hotspots the more reliable is the results. In addition, the redundant blocks that may have in-between correlation lead to redundancy in the further analysis. Since the main idea of haplotype blocks is the reduction in biomarkers, the accurate lower number of haplotype blocks is preferable.

Figure 6.1 is a bar chart summarize the total number of blocks resulted by the four proposed methods of haplotype block partitioning using five different MAF thresholds, which applied to experimental NARAC genome-wide dataset. The zoomed bar chart of each chromosome is clearly presented in appendix C (Figure

Figure 6.1: The total number of haplotype blocks resulted by applying four haplotype block partitioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

C.1 to Figure C.5). The X axis is the chromosomes, each chromosome has 20 bars; four sets, each set consists of five bars for the five MAF thresholds. The Y axis is the total number of haplotype blocks. The FGT with MAF=0.001 produces the highest number of the total haplotype blocks; it produced 8,479 haplotype blocks in chromosome 2 and 101,915 blocks for the entire data.

The chart (Figure 6.1) shows a constant trend in all chromosomes. The highest number of haplotype blocks descending order is as following: FGT, CIT, SSLD, and BigLD. The number of haplotype blocks decreases with increasing MAF threshold. which seems perfectly logical because the higher MAF the higher is the SNPs excluding and as a result a lower number of haplotype blocks (see Figure 6.2). Excluding SNPs with $MAF \leq 0.001$ remain 97.95% of the raw SNPs, $MAF \leq 0.01$ remain 95.82% of the SNPs, $MAF \leq 0.02$ remain 94.86% of the SNPs, $MAF \leq 0.05$ remain 90.54% of the SNPs, and $MAF \leq 0.1$ remain 78.49% of the SNPs.

The results show that the number of haplotype blocks is data dependent. The larger is the number of SNPs the higher is the number of haplotype blocks. Chromosome 2 has the highest number of SNPs and as a result the highest is the number of haplotype blocks while chromosome 21 has the lower number of SNPs and as a result the lower number of haplotype blocks. We suggest that the BigLD has the lower number of the total haplotype blocks because its wider definition that consider the correlation between haplotype blocks.

Figure 6.2: The percentage of included SNPs with respect to the MAF threshold.

We also suggest that FGT results in the lower number of haplotype blocks because it does not depend on LD (neither D' nor r^2). Figure 6.3 shows the bar charts of the data in general i.e. the 22 chromosomes. The pattern is clear and the

Figure 6.3: The total number of haplotype blocks using the four proposed methods and five MAF on genome-wide scale of NARAC data.

descending order of the methods and MAF thresholds is obvious. Table B.1 in appendix B show the detailed results. Figures from C.1 to C.5 shows the bar chart for each chromosome clearly. The pattern is the same along all chromosome except in chromosome 6 and chromosome 9, where BigLD has higher number of blocks than SSLD. BigLD shows convergent outcomes especially in MAF from (0.001 to 0.05).

The characteristics of HBP. Table S1. By comparing the methods 00 comparing the MAF threshold. In chromosome 16 the number of blocks is more than that in chromosome 15 since chromosome 16 has a higher number of SNPs (see Table 3.7 in chapter 3). Similarly, chromosome 18 has 16450 SNPs and chromosome 17 has 14027 SNPs, chromosome 18 has higher number of haplotype blocks (Figure C.5).

6.2 Total number of blocks with considering the singleton

In this parameter we have rearranged the order of the method for the visualization purpose to be as the following: CIT, FGT, BigLD and SSLD. Figure 6.4 is the bar charts of the total number of blocks with considering the singleton over the 22 chromosomes. As in the previous parameter, twenty bars for each

chromosome to compare the methods and MAF thresholds. The CIT produces the highest number of haplotype blocks considering the singleton blocks.

Figure 6.4: The total number of haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks resulted by applying four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from NARAC dataset.

The highest number of total haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks in a descending order is as following: CIT, FGT, BigLD, and SSLD. The higher is the MAF the higher is total haplotype blocks with considering the singleton. Nevertheless, the MAF=0.001 has a relatively high values with CIT method. For more detailed results see Table B.2 in appendix B.

Figure 6.5 shows the general pattern of this parameter. The MAF=0.1 has the highest values, which may indicate high number of singleton blocks as a result of decreasing the number of haplotype blocks i.e. many SNPs could be end up without belonging to a large haplotype block as a result of reduction of the blocks because of high MAF.

Here we provide our explanation of why CIT has the highest values of total haplotype blocks considering the singleton blocks. The CIT method has a high number of haplotype blocks (as shown in Figure 6.3) with a small number of SNPs in each block (as will be discussed in Figure 6.7) so the remaining singleton SNP is very high. In the contrast, The SSLD has a relatively small number of haplotype

blocks (see Figure 6.3) with a high number of SNPs in each block (see Figure 6.7) which means high coverage of blocks and the remaining singletons SNPs are relatively little. The total number of haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks is also a data dependent, it increases with the number of SNPs increases. The highest value is by CIT in chromosome 2 with MAF threshold equals 0.1 while the lowest value is with SSLD method in chromosome 21 with MAF threshold equals 0.01 (see Figure C.7 and Figure C.12). It is obvious that the total number of haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks is also a data dependent, it increases with the number of SNPs increases. In general, the CIT and SSLD have different pattern than FGT and BigLD. In CIT and SSLD methods the MAF=0.001 has a higher value than MAF with 0.01,0.02 and 0.05 values. FGT and BigLD methods have an ascending order; the higher is the MAF the higher is the number of haplotype blocks with singleton blocks (see Figure 6.5).

Figure 6.5: The total number of haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks using the four proposed methods and five MAF on genome-wide scale of NARAC data.

6.3 Total number of SNPs in all blocks

Figure 6.6 summarize the total number of SNPs in all blocks along the 22 chromosomes. The axes are as the previous charts; the partitioning is performed 20 times for each chromosome to compare the methods and the MAF thresholds. The all results are Table B.3 in appendix B. The detailed bar charts in appendix C Figure C.7 to Figure C.12. We reordered the methods to clearly visualize the pattern of the data. The SSLD with $MAF \leq 0.001$ produces the highest number of total number of SNPs in all block in chromosome 2 (41,996), while the highest number in general for the entire data was with $MAF \leq 0.01$ (502242). Contradictorily, the CIT with

MAF ≤ 0.1 produces the lowest number of SNPs in the blocks of the entire data which are 388934, and the lowest number in the chromosome 22 haplotype blocks (5,668 SNPs). The results are convincing because the higher is the number of blocks the higher is the number of SNPs in blocks and vice versa. As we described previously that the lower is the MAF the higher is the haplotype blocks. The question here is why sometimes 0.01 produces a higher number of SNPs in blocks than 0.001? However, the difference between the two results is subtle. These results indicate that the number of blocks not necessarily affect the number of SNPs within blocks. We suggest that SSLD produces a larger number of SNPs in blocks because it produces a high block length as it will reveal in the next section. The SNP coverage is the highest in SSLD. Figure 6.7 shows the bar chart of the total; number of SNPs in all blocks for the genome-wide data and differentiates the results of the different methods and MAF thresholds. The total number of SNPs in all blocks is data dependent, the higher is the SNP data the number of SNPs in all blocks. However, this role is not always perfect. Despite chromosome 22 has higher number of SNPs than chromosome 21, it produces lower number of SNPs in all blocks than chromosome 21. In general, the total number of SNPs in all blocks decreases with the MAF threshold increases in all methods except in the CIT with MAF=0.001 which has a lower value than in MAF=0.01.

Figure 6.6: The total number of SNPs in all blocks by applying four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from NARAC dataset.

Figure 6.7 shows the bar charts of the total SNPs in all blocks in all chromosomes.

Figure 6.7: Total number of SNPs in all blocks

6.4 The total length of all blocks (bp)

In this parameter we count the length in base pair rather than counting the SNPs in the blocks. Figure 6.8 shows the total length of all blocks in all chromosomes.

Figure 6.8: The total length of all blocks (bp) by applying four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

The same trend is obvious across all chromosomes. Figure 6.9 illustrates the overall result of the length of all blocks. SSLD always shows the highest total length of blocks in all chromosomes and with all MAF thresholds.

Figure 6.9: The total length of all blocks (bp) using the four proposed methods and five MAF on a genome-wide scale of NARAC data.

All methods have shorter block length with MAF threshold equals 0.1. The MAF range from 0.001 to 0.05 do not affect the results too much. FGT presents a consistent pattern; the more is the MAF the less is the length. BigLD shows roughly the same result in all MAF thresholds results except 0.1 where the length becomes much shorter. The length of blocks depends also in the data; chromosome 2 has the longest blocks in base pair and the chromosome 22 has the shortest blocks (see Figure C.19 in Appendix C)

6.5 The mean number of SNPs in blocks

Figure 6.10 summarize the mean number of SNPs in blocks along the 22 chromosomes. The BigLD and SSLD has higher mean number of SNPs in blocks than FIG and CIT. In general, the MAF does not affect the mean number of SNPs in blocks so much. The BigLD has almost the same mean number of SNPs in blocks in the range from 0.001 to 0.05 and a higher mean number of SNPs in blocks at MAF=0.1. The SSLD's mean number of SNPs in blocks increases with the MAF threshold increases. CIT has almost the same mean number of SNPs in blocks in the range from 0.01 to 0.05 and a slightly lower at MAF=0.1 and a relatively much lower at MAF=0.001.

Figure 6.11: The mean number of SNPs in blocks by applying four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

Figure 6.11 illustrates the mean number of SNPs in blocks for all chromosomes. The mean number of SNPs in blocks for all chromosomes are rounded two decimal places and presented in Table B.5 in appendix B. The highest mean number of SNPs in blocks is in chromosome 6 using SSLD with MAF=0.1 which equals to 6.637. The lowest mean number of SNPs in blocks is in chromosome 19 using CIT and with MAF=0.001.

Figure 6.10: The mean number of SNPs in blocks using the four proposed methods and five MAF on a genome-wide scale of NARAC data.

6.6 The mean block length in base pair

Figure 6.12 exhibits the mean block length in each chromosome by using the four haplotype block partitioning methods and the five MAF thresholds. The mean block length is method dependent. The highest mean block length is produced by

Figure 6.12: The mean block length in base pair by applying four haplotype block partitioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

SSLD. The second highest values are in BigLD. The FGT and CIT resulted in convergent values. The mean block length decreases with increasing MAF threshold in FGT. In contrast, the mean block length increases with increasing MAF threshold in SSLD. In CIT, the higher is the MAF the higher is the mean block length but the values are higher in the moderate value of MAF especially in MAF=0.02 and it somewhat drop down at MAF=0.1. BigLD block length roughly does not affected by MAF.

The maximum mean block length appears in chromosome 4 using SSLD with MAF 0.1 which equals to 28,514 bp. The minimum value is 7606 bp in chromosome 11 using FGT with MAF 0.1 (Figure C.31 and Figure C.37 in appendix C). The results are rounded to the nearest integer value. See Table B.1 in appendix B for details.

Unlike the previous parameters this one does not affect by the number of SNPs. Figure 6.13 shows the mean block length for the 22 chromosomes.

Figure 6.13: The mean block length in base pair using the four proposed methods and five MAF on a genome-wide scale of NARAC data.

6.7 The mean r^2 within blocks

The bar chart in Figure 6.14 illustrates the mean r^2 within blocks for the 22 chromosomes by using the four proposed methods and the five MAF thresholds.

Figure 6.14: The mean r^2 within blocks by applying four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

The correlation mean r^2 within the blocks is higher in BigLD in general than the other methods. It is data-dependent also; chromosome 4 has higher mean r^2 than other chromosomes. Typically, the topmost r^2 within the blocks are given by the following descending order: BigLD, CIT, FGT, and SSLD. This rule is not true in chromosome 9, where BigLD forms the lowest mean r^2 within the blocks. Generally, the higher MAF the higher r^2 within block. Contrastingly, in the BigLD method, the mean r^2 within a block decrease with the MAF threshold increases. However, the extent to which the MAF affects the BigLD mean r^2 within blocks is very small.

The range of mean r^2 within a block is vary from approximately 2.5 to 4. Figure 6.15 demonstrates mean r^2 within a block for the 22 chromosomes all together.

Figure 6.15: The mean r^2 within blocks using the four proposed methods and five MAF on a genome-wide scale of NARAC data.

6.8 The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks (without considering the singleton blocks)

The bar chart in Figure 6.16 illustrates the mean r^2 between the consecutive haplotype blocks without considering the singleton blocks for the 22 chromosomes by using the four proposed methods and the five MAF thresholds. In general, the SSLD has the lowest mean r^2 between consecutive blocks while the FGT has the highest. The higher is the MAF the higher is the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks. The highest mean r^2 between consecutive blocks value is in chromosome 8 by FGT and 0.1 MAF. The lowest values of mean r^2 between consecutive blocks is in chromosome 19, and the lowest value produced by SSLD and 0.01 MAF.

Figure 6.17: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks by applying four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

The pattern is approximately the same across the entire data (see Figure 6.17 and Figures C.47 to C.52 in appendix C). The detailed results are in Table B.8 in appendix B.

Figure 6.16: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks by applying four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

The range of this parameter is from 0.23 to 0.13. This is a logical result since the r^2 between blocks should be less than the r^2 within the block. The low r^2 between blocks is a good indication that this site is not a block and is a sign of recombination events. The ascending order of the mean r^2 between blocks is SSLD, BigLD, CIT and FGT. These results meet our expectation because FGT does not depend on measuring the r^2 in its definition this result in a high r^2 between the blocks.

6.9 The mean r^2 between consecutive all blocks (with singleton)

The bar chart in Figure 6.18 represents the mean r^2 between the consecutive haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks for the 22 chromosomes by using the four proposed methods and the five MAF thresholds. In a like manner of the previous parameter that measures the r^2 , this parameter increases with the MAF increases. Figure 6.15 illustrates mean r^2 between blocks with considering the singleton SNPs for the 22 chromosomes all at once. The ascending order of the mean r^2 between blocks with considering the singleton blocks is BigLD, SSLD, CIT and FGT. The highest value of mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks was in chromosome 8 by using FGT and 0.1 MAF threshold. The lowest value was in chromosome 19 by BigLD and 0.01 MAF (Figure C.49 to Figure C.58 in appendix C).

Figure 6.18: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks by applying four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

It is a good point for BigLD to have the highest mean r^2 within blocks and the least mean r^2 between blocks with considering the singleton blocks. This give indication that the blocks are in a close correlation and the breaking points and singleton SNPs are less likely to be attached to the blocks. The range of mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with considering singleton blocks is from 0.2167 to 0.1266. These values are less than that within blocks and between consecutive blocks without the singleton. We suggest that the interpretation is that there are no correlations between the singleton blocks to form a block.

Figure 6.19: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks using the four proposed methods and five MAF on a genome-wide scale of NARAC data.

6.10 The intersection percentage

We also have measured the intersection percentage between the methods. This parameter shows to which extent the proposed methods have given the same sites of blocks. Figure 6.20 is a line charts that demonstrates the intersection between method, the effect of MAF and where the methods are agree the most. For the detailed results see Table B.10 in appendix B.

The methods are in the highest match in chromosome 4 where the intersection percentage reaches 72.6%. The lowest match is in chromosome 19 where intersection percentage reaches 53%. It is obvious from the line chart that the higher is the MAF the lower is the intersection percentage among the methods. We can conclude that the data and the MAF both affect the results of the different methods.

Figure 6.20: The intersection percentage among four haplotype block portioning methods with five different MAF thresholds over 22 chromosomes from the NARAC dataset.

6.11 The processing times

The processing time of on Haploview was 336 hours for all chromosomes by applying the five MAF thresholds by the three methods (CIT, FGT and SSLD). The by BigLD have taken 40 hours for partitioning the 22 chromosomes five times by applying the five MAF thresholds.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and future considerations

In this dissertation, we have provided a descriptive analysis for a high throughput case-control genotyped dataset produced by NARAC. The percentage of missing data for each chromosome was calculated, and it ranged between 0.68% and 1.23%. The statistical calculations demonstrate the pattern and distribution of the genotypes, alleles, and their MAF. The allele "T" was absent in all data; however, it may be because of the genotyping process, yet it is still questionable. The SNPs are classified according to the MAF to find the effect of each range. The consequences of the SNPs were obtained by the EVP tool. The descriptive data were presented in tables, pie charts, bar charts, and line charts.

In this empirical study, we have shown the detailed steps for preparing high-density data of 1,096,342,718 genotyped SNPs. Reformatting, imputation, and recoding data into several genotype formats were conducted as a beforehand process. Our sequence of pre-processing includes preparing the character to be a format that is suitable for Imputation which has solved the problem of missing data. The next step is recording data in 0,1,2 format to be ideal for the BigLD. The proposed approach explains how to deal with such a big dataset, which makes it suitable for haplotype block partitioning. We were eventually preparing data for Haploview that can provide clear haplotype block partitioning, association analysis, and furthermore.

Our pre-processing steps pose as a practical guide for the researchers and geneticists who want to make similar analyses. We have gathered all codes and build them under the R programming language, which simplified the process and the workflow. This paper evokes a vivid image of how to pre-process genome-wide data under a personal computer environment in a clearly defined manner. The entire time computing was relatively long; about 750 hours; Thus, in the future work, the parallel computing should be considered. Nowadays, the high throughput genome-scale data are available more than any time before. So, it is essential to address such data to exploit them and focus on understanding and preparing them in different forms, which eventually help to utilize them.

This study tends to answer several questions regarding MAF. Is it worthy to consider low MAF in complex traits association studies? To how much degree MAF

affects the pattern of variation structure in the genome? How MAF affect haplotype block partitioning. We conduct this study over 4 different common haplotype block partitioning methods on whole genome genotyped dataset; NARAC dataset using different MAF thresholds (0.001, 0.02, 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1). In the end of the study we provide some recommendation when choosing MAF threshold in haplotype block partitioning. The novelty of this work that there no direct relationship found between MAF and Haplotype block partitioning and LD. We want to reveal it and uncover the effect of MAF.

In this study, we have investigated the effects MAF threshold on the results of haplotype partitioning for four recent and popular haplotype block partitioning methods: BigLD in R programming language and three methods in Haploview (CIT, FGT, and SSLD). BigLD has the lower number of the total haplotype blocks. The highest number of haplotype blocks descending order is as following: FGT, CIT, SSLD, and BigLD. The number of haplotype blocks decreases with increasing MAF threshold. The patterns are almost the same along all chromosomes. The BigLD has the highest mean r^2 within the blocks and the least mean r^2 between blocks with considering the singleton blocks. The BigLD is outweighed also because it has the shortest processing time.

We recommend taking the MAF in consideration when applying a haplotype block partition. However, it is a tradeoff, higher MAF produces a higher correlation within the blocks but its trunk a portion of data that may could be significant. We hope that our results and observation will serve as a guide for the researchers and geneticist when dealing with haplotype blocks and MAF.

Future work computer tools that were adequate as a flexible tool formats and analysis variety of options to control what is displayed. Large amounts of polymorphism data can be organized so that patterns Manipulation, SNPs data are essential for quality assessment integrated

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Appendix A

Data description and annotation

We aim to prepare the North American rheumatoid arthritis Consortium (NARAC) data for further analysis to investigate the role of minor allele frequency (MAF) in haplotype block partitioning. We have classified the data into four categories depending on their corresponding MAF. The four ranges of MAF are the very rare SNPs that have MAFs less than 0.001, the rare SNPs (0.001-0.01), the low-frequency SNPs (0.01 - 0.05), and finally, the common SNPs (>0.05). The second step to find the effectiveness of each category is by applying the effect variant predictor tool (EVP)[157] to produce the annotation of the regions that include the SNPs. EVP could provide insight into how much the SNPs are influential. From the result, we have built eight tables that describe the percentage of each region.

Types of consequences annotation

We have summarized the main consequences types that appear in the NARAC dataset as described by EVP, as shown in table1. Tables A. 2-5 are for all consequence's annotation. Tables A. 6-9 are concentrating on the coding annotation [203]. The results lead to intuitive insight into the SNPs and their corresponding MAF as the following:

- Intron variants represent about 50% of all SNPs. The SNPs with low-frequency MAF shows the least intron variants.
- There is no splice region variant in the entire dataset except in the chromosome 20 SNPs with rare MAF.
- Missense variants appear more in common SNPs. The missense variant percentage is directly proportional to MAF. Where, The lower MAF, the higher the synonymous variant percentage.
- The following regions appear more in common SNPs: start lost, stop lost, stop gained, coding sequence variant and, incomplete terminal codon variant.

Table A.1 The main annotation types.

Consequence type	Description
Intron variants	Is a transcript variant occurring within an intron
Non-coding transcript variants	Is a transcript variant of a non-coding RNA gene
Downstream gene variant	Is a sequence variant located 3' of a gene
Upstream gene variant	Is a sequence variant located 5' of a gene
Intergenic variant	Is a sequence variant located in the intergenic region, between genes
Nonsense-mediated decay (NMD) transcript variant	Is a variant in a transcript region that is the target of NMD
Regulatory region variant	Is a sequence variant located within a regulatory region
Non-coding transcript exon variant	Is a sequence variant that changes non-coding exon sequence in a non-coding transcript
Transcription factor (TF) binding site variant	Is a sequence variant located within a transcription factor binding site
3-prime untranslated region (UTR) variant	Is a UTR variant of the 3' UTR
Missense variant	It is a sequence variant that changes one or more bases, resulting in a different amino acid sequence. The length, in this case, is preserved.
Synonymous variant	Is a sequence variant where there is no resulting change to the encoded amino acid
Start lost	Is a codon variant that changes at least one base of the canonical start codon
Stop lost	Is a sequence variant where at least one base of the terminator codon (stop) is changed, resulting in an elongated transcript
Stop gained	It is a sequence variant with a premature stop resulted from changing one or more base of a codon.

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Stop retained variant	A sequence variant where one or more base in the terminator codon is changed, but the terminator remains
Coding sequence variant	Is a sequence variant that changes the coding sequence
Incomplete terminal codon variant	Is a sequence variant where at least one base of the final codon of an incompletely annotated transcript is changed

A.1 Tables of all consequences

Table A.2: The percentage of the SNPs consequences of very rare SNPs in the entire autosomal dataset.

Chr. number	Intron variants	Non-coding transcript variant	Downstream Gene variant	Upstream Gene variant	Intergenic variant	NMD transcript variant	Regulatory region variant	Non-coding transcript exon variant	TF-binding site variant	3 prime UTR variant	Missense variant	Synonymous variants	5 prime UTR	Splice region variant	Others
1	50	18	8	6	5	6	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	52	20	6	6	6	5	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	54	22	5	5	5	5	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	53	18	4	4	9	6	4	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	49	23	6	4	6	4	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
6	47	20	8	7	4	3	3	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	2
7	54	17	6	5	5	6	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
8	55	25	5	3	4	3	3	<1	1	0	0	0	0	0	<1
9	53	16	5	5	9	5	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
10	57	16	5	5	5	4	4	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
11	51	15	9	9	5	5	4	<1	0	1	0	0	0	0	<1
12	54	15	9	6	5	5	4	<1	0	1	0	0	0	0	<1
13	47	22	4	4	10	4	4	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
14	49	21	6	9	4	4	3	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
15	51	19	6	6	4	7	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
16	54	17	8	5	3	6	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
17	48	10	12	8	3	8	4	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	1
18	52	25	4	3	6	3	4	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
19	54	16	8	5	5	7	3	<1	0	1	0	0	0	0	<1
20	54	16	6	5	8	3	5	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
21	50	40	3	2	2	0	1	<1	0	<1	0	<1	0	0	<1
22	45	20	10	9	3	4	5	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Mean	50	18	8	6	5	6	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1

Table A.3: The percentage of the SNPs consequences of rare SNPs in the entire autosomal dataset.

Chr. number	Intron variants	Non-coding transcript variant	Downstream Gene variant	Upstream Gene variant	Intergenic variant	NMD transcript variant	Regulatory region variant	Non-coding transcript exon	TF-binding side variant	3 prime UTR variant	Missense variant	Synonymous variants	5 prime UTR	Splice region variant	Others
1	49	17	7	7	5	6	4	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	52	25	5	4	5	4	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
3	55	18	6	5	5	5	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	64	16	4	4	4	2	2	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
5	50	21	6	5	7	5	4	<1	1	0	0	0	0	0	<1
6	48	22	8	5	6	3	4	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
7	54	18	5	6	6	5	4	<1	1	0	0	0	0	0	<1
8	51	22	5	6	5	5	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	53	16	7	5	7	4	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
10	62	13	5	4	5	5	4	<1	0	0	1	0	0	0	<1
11	51	18	7	8	6	4	4	<1	1	0	0	0	0	0	<1
12	55	15	6	7	5	5	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
13	45	22	6	7	10	2	4	<1	1	0	0	0	0	0	<3
14	50	20	8	7	5	4	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
15	53	21	7	4	3	5	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
16	54	16	8	5	5	7	3	1	0	<1	0	0	<1	0	0
17	46	12	8	14	3	6	3	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
18	52	20	5	4	10	3	5	<1	<1	<1	0	0	<1	0	0
19	54	17	8	5	3	6	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
20	53	14	9	5	6	3	6	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
21	50	44	3	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	48	22	9	7	3	3	4	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Mean	52.23	19.50	6.45	5.68	5.23	4.18	3.68	1.36	0.51	0.08	0.09	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.89

Table A.4: The percentage of the SNPs consequences of low-frequency SNPs in the entire autosomal dataset.

Chr. number	Intron variants	Non-coding transcript variant	Downstream Gene variant	Upstream Gene variant	Intergenic variant	NMD transcript variant	Regulatory region variant	Non-coding transcript exon	TF- binding side variant	3 prime UTR variant	Missense variant	Synonymous variants	5 prime UTR	Splice region variant	Others
1	48	18	7	7	5	7	4	<2	0	1	0	0	0	0	<2
2	51	20	7	5	5	4	4	<2	0	0	1	0	0	0	<2
3	55	21	5	4	4	5	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
4	57	17	5	3	7	5	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
5	50	22	5	5	6	4	4	<2	1	0	0	0	0	0	<2
6	45	18	13	7	6	2	3	<3	0	0	1	0	0	0	<3
7	54	17	6	5	5	5	4	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
8	55	22	5	4	5	4	3	<1	1	0	0	0	0	0	<1
9	51	14	7	6	7	4	5	<3	0	0	1	0	0	0	<3
10	58	15	5	5	6	4	4	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
11	51	16	8	8	4	3	4	<3	0	0	1	0	0	0	<3
12	54	15	8	6	4	5	4	<2	0	1	0	0	0	0	<2
13	47	21	5	4	11	4	5	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
14	49	18	9	6	4	5	4	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
15	51	20	7	5	3	5	4	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
16	51	17	8	8	4	5	3	<2	0	0	1	0	0	0	<2
17	45	15	11	9	3	5	4	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	3
18	53	21	4	4	7	4	4	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
19	51	17	8	8	4	5	3	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
20	49	18	8	5	5	3	6	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
21	54	29	4	4	3	1	3	<1	0	0	1	0	0	0	<1
22	47	17	10	9	3	4	5	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
Mean	48	18	7	7	5	7	4	<2	0	1	0	0	0	0	<2

Table A.5: The percentage of the SNPs consequences of common SNPs in the entire autosomal dataset.

Chr. number	Intron variants	Non-coding transcript variant	Downstream Gene variant	Upstream Gene variant	Intergenic variant	NMD transcript variant	Regulatory region variant	Non-coding transcript exon	TF- binding side variant	3 prime UTR variant	Missense variant	Synonymous variants	5 prime UTR	Splice region variant	Others
1	49	17	8	7	5	5	5	<2	0	0	1	0	0	0	<2
2	51	23	5	5	5	4	4	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
3	55	20	5	5	4	6	3	<1	0	0	1	0	0	0	<1
4	56	17	5	4	7	5	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
5	49	20	6	5	6	4	4	<3	1	0	0	0	0	0	<3
6	44	18	12	10	5	2	3	<3	0	0	1	0	0	0	<3
7	55	18	5	5	5	5	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
8	53	23	6	5	5	3	3	<1	1	0	0	0	0	0	<1
9	51	15	7	6	8	4	5	<2	1	0	0	0	0	0	<2
10	59	13	5	5	6	4	4	<2	1	0	0	0	0	0	<2
11	51	16	8	8	4	4	4	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
12	53	15	8	7	4	5	4	<2	0	1	0	0	0	0	<2
13	46	22	5	5	11	3	5	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
14	49	19	8	7	4	4	4	<2	0	0	1	0	0	0	<3
15	52	19	7	6	3	5	4	<2	0	1	0	0	0	0	<2
16	53	16	8	7	4	6	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
17	45	16	11	10	3	5	4	<3	0	0	1	0	0	0	<3
18	53	21	5	5	6	4	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
19	37	10	18	17	2	4	3	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	3
20	49	18	7	7	6	3	5	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
21	50	28	5	5	5	2	3	<1	0	1	0	0	0	0	<1
22	47	18	9	9	3	4	4	<3	0	0	1	0	0	0	<3
Mean	52.23	19.50	6.45	5.68	5.23	4.18	3.68	1.36	0.51	0.08	0.09	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.89

A.2 Tables of coding consequences

Table A.6: The percentage of SNPs coding consequences of very rare SNPs.

Chr	Missense variants	Synonymous variant	Start lost	Stop lost	Stop gained	Stop retained	Coding sequence variant	Incomplete terminal codon variant
Chr 1	61	39	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 2	51	49	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 3	59	41	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 4	60	40	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 5	64	36	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 6	92	6	0	0	2	0	0	0
Chr 7	69	31	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 8	29	71	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 9	75	25	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 10	50	50	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 11	43	57	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 12	67	33	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 13	50	50	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 14	19	81	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 15	52	48	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 16	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 17	34	66	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 18	33	67	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 19	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 20	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 22	50	50	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	50.3810	49.5238	0	0	0.0952	0	0	0

Table A.7: The percentage of SNPs coding consequences of rare SNPs.

Chr	Missense variants	Synonymous variant	Start lost	Stop lost	Stop gained	Stop retained	Coding sequence variant	Incomplete terminal codon variant
Chr 1	49	47	0	0	4	0	0	0
Chr 2	62	38	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 3	86	14	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 4	66	34	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 5	54	46	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 6	71	27	0	0	2	0	0	0
Chr 7	38	54	8	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 8	48	52	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 9	43	57	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 10	97	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 11	47	53	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 12	75	25	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 13	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 14	67	33	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 15	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 16	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 17	38	62	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 19	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 20	100		0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 21	50	50	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 22	79	21	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	60.4762	38.8571	0.3810	0	0.2857	0	0	0

Table A.8: The percentage of SNPs coding consequences of low-frequency SNPs.

Chr	Missense variants	Synonymous variant	Start lost	Stop lost	Stop gained	Stop retained	Coding sequence variant	Incomplete terminal codon variant
Chr 1	67	31	0	0	2	0	0	0
Chr 2	72	28	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 3	50	41	0	0	9	0	0	0
Chr 4	74	24	0	2	0	0	0	0
Chr 5	56	39	0	0	5	0	0	0
Chr 6	93	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 7	57	43	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 8	71	28	1	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 9	68	30	0	0	0	0	1	1
Chr 10	87	13	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 11	80	20	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 12	60	39	0	0	1	0	0	0
Chr 13	82	18	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 14	52	41	0	0	7	0	0	0
Chr 15	53	47	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 16	71	27	0	0	2	0	0	0
Chr 17	74	26	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 18	71	29	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 19	71	27	0	0	2	0	0	0
Chr 20	55	34	2	0	9	0	0	0
Chr 21	68	32	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chr 22	34	66	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	66.6363	31.3636	0.1364	0.0909	1.6818	0	0.04545	0.04545

Table A.9: The percentage of SNPs coding consequences of common SNPs.

Chr	Missense variants	Synonymous variant	Start lost	Stop lost	Stop gained	Stop retained	Coding sequence variant	Incomplete terminal codon variant
Chr 1	69	29	0	<1	1	0	<1	0
Chr 2	69.5	28.5	<1	<1	<1	0	0	0
Chr 3	70.4	28.4	<1	0	1	0	0	0
Chr 4	68.6	28.6	<1	0	1	1	0	0
Chr 5	64.7	32.7	0	0	2	<1	<1	<1
Chr 6	71	26	1	<1	1	0	<1	0
Chr 7	61.6	36.6	<1	<1	1	0	0	0
Chr 8	62.9	35.9	<1	<1	<1	<1	<1	<1
Chr 9	62	36	0	1	1	0	0	0
Chr 10	65	33	0	<1	1	0	<1	0
Chr 11	68	31	<1	<1	<1	0	0	0
Chr 12	64.6	33.6	<1	<1	1	0	<1	<1
Chr 13	63.8	35.8	0	0	<1	0	0	0
Chr 14	63.8	34.8	0	<1	1	0	0	0
Chr 15	63.8	31.8	1	<1	2	1	<1	0
Chr 16	61.8	36.8	0	0	1	0	<1	<1
Chr 17	66.6	31.6	<1	<1	1	<1	<1	0
Chr 18	62.5	35.5	0	0	2	0	0	0
Chr 19	66.7	31.7	0	<1	1	<1	<1	0
Chr 20	68	31	0	0	<1	0	<1	<1
Chr 21	70	29	0	0	1	0	0	0
Chr 22	77	22	0	0	1	0	0	0
Mean	66.4227	31.7864	0.2341	0.2273	1.0046	0.1273	0.04	0.01

Appendix B

Supplementary results

In this appendix we have presented the tables of the measured parameters across the 22 chromosomes.

B.1 Total number of haplotype blocks

Table B.1: The total number of haplotype blocks resulted by partitioning NARAC data using four different methods and five MAF thresholds.

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Chr. 1	FGT	7659	7635	7626	7500	6904
	CIT	7345	7239	7193	7028	6461
	SSLD	6638	6381	6339	6176	5731
	BigLD	6161	6127	6111	6036	5657
Chr. 2	FGT	8479	8463	8458	8333	7747
	CIT	8206	8088	8052	7847	7253
	SSLD	7138	6915	6862	6679	6256
	BigLD	6647	6604	6601	6502	6176
Chr. 3	FGT	7032	7018	7007	6894	6374
	CIT	6819	6728	6679	6532	5992
	SSLD	5939	5758	5694	5694	5213
	BigLD	5518	5470	5460	5398	5124
Chr. 4	FGT	6072	6055	6045	5956	5528
	CIT	5920	5817	5768	5648	5262
	SSLD	5920	5093	5047	4937	4616
	BigLD	5054	5032	5013	4951	4705
Chr. 5	FGT	6405	6385	6373	6273	5817
	CIT	6193	6117	6074	5921	5429
	SSLD	5364	5182	5137	4997	4672
	BigLD	4962	4956	4940	4876	4584
Chr. 6	FGT	6472	6464	6451	6368	5891
	CIT	6194	6107	6065	5895	5510
	SSLD	5414	5231	5167	5068	4760
	BigLD	5084	5053	5042	4966	4681
Chr. 7	FGT	5624	5606	5600	5516	5074

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	CIT	5395	5328	5296	5193	4783
	SSLD	4763	4632	4600	4498	4210
	BigLD	4350	4334	4315	4279	4031
Chr. 8	FGT	5875	5860	5851	5745	5310
	CIT	5667	5560	5526	5410	4979
	SSLD	4890	4709	4671	4554	4319
	BigLD	4315	4298	4288	4238	4033
Chr. 9	FGT	5116	5096	5088	5012	4592
	CIT	4935	4850	4823	4709	4308
	SSLD	4367	4214	4181	4090	3806
	BigLD	4315	4298	4288	4238	4033
Chr. 10	FGT	5365	5356	5348	5255	4819
	CIT	5137	5047	5014	4909	4536
	SSLD	4641	4470	4423	4313	4034
	BigLD	4037	4027	4002	3938	3742
Chr. 11	FGT	5052	5039	5028	4947	4532
	CIT	4807	4756	4721	4607	4250
	SSLD	4261	4124	4092	4019	3745
	BigLD	3898	3883	3867	3839	3580
Chr. 12	FGT	4909	4899	4889	4809	4420
	CIT	4693	4630	4608	4497	4167
	SSLD	4226	4099	4068	3953	3953
	BigLD	3922	3902	3887	3829	3612
Chr. 13	FGT	3831	3823	3817	3766	3485
	CIT	3666	3590	3558	3443	3206
	SSLD	3216	3108	3080	2998	2814
	BigLD	2898	2893	2887	2818	2669
Chr. 14	FGT	3461	3454	3452	3397	3123
	CIT	3353	3314	3292	3200	2939
	SSLD	2926	2842	2814	2751	2580
	BigLD	2699	2685	2677	2616	2454
Chr. 15	FGT	3187	3179	3165	3105	2863
	CIT	3167	3111	3089	2973	2718
	SSLD	2855	2750	2717	2623	2464
	BigLD	2456	2443	2428	2390	2297
Chr. 16	FGT	3401	3396	3388	3313	3313
	CIT	3272	3255	3240	3150	3150
	SSLD	3035	2950	2930	2846	2846

Chr. 17	BigLD	2477	2465	2463	2431	2304
	FGT	2819	2816	2812	2764	2501
	CIT	2718	2695	2672	2616	2365
	SSLD	2618	2556	2537	2482	2297
	BigLD	2299	2289	2277	2238	2131
Chr. 18	FGT	3195	3186	3182	3138	2866
	CIT	3095	3063	3044	2962	2709
	SSLD	2798	2733	2710	2638	2467
	BigLD	2461	2449	2442	2387	2285
Chr. 19	FGT	1994	1983	1979	1927	1743
	CIT	1849	1840	1830	1771	1618
	SSLD	1896	1867	1860	1812	1651
	BigLD	1618	1610	1598	1578	1479
Chr. 20	FGT	2773	2766	2762	2718	2420
	CIT	2652	2634	2623	2554	2316
	SSLD	2344	2285	2280	2218	2056
	BigLD	2088	2072	2074	2035	1897
Chr. 21	FGT	1589	1585	1581	1557	1434
	CIT	1527	1509	1505	1458	1350
	SSLD	1399	1361	1352	1315	1252
	BigLD	1205	1193	1197	1189	1109
Chr. 22	FGT	1605	1601	1598	1572	1444
	CIT	1552	1540	1535	1507	1394
	SSLD	1461	1423	1413	1373	1257
	BigLD	1248	1256	1255	1227	1160

B.2 Tables of the total number of haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks

Table B.2: The total number of haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks by partitioning NARAC data using four different methods and five MAF thresholds.

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
		Chr. 1	FGT	12977	13359	13552
CIT	15127		14578	14572	15120	17370
BigLD	11631		11737	11805	12162	13705
SSLD	8757		8716	8787	9224	10973
Chr. 2	FGT	14489	14864	15050	15891	18516

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	CIT	16750	16200	16260	16742	19059
	BigLD	11940	12021	12089	12509	14068
	SSLD	9232	9214	9282	9710	11409
Chr. 3	FGT	12084	12386	12534	13205	15263
	CIT	13817	13384	13411	13777	15605
	BigLD	10192	10230	10273	10590	11681
	SSLD	7717	7661	7718	7718	9472
Chr. 4	FGT	9961	10238	10383	10966	12843
	CIT	11380	10931	10914	11320	13070
	BigLD	9157	9238	9258	9570	10740
	SSLD	11380	6794	6838	7224	8519
Chr. 5	FGT	10683	10938	11085	11744	13744
	CIT	12123	11738	11724	12151	14024
	BigLD	9316	9359	9384	9673	10789
	SSLD	6880	6836	6872	7215	8574
Chr. 6	FGT	10732	11018	11145	11781	13983
	CIT	12379	11894	11868	12170	14077
	BigLD	9175	9256	9306	9519	10783
	SSLD	6921	6866	6921	7272	8743
Chr. 7	FGT	9668	9882	9994	10589	12347
	CIT	11048	10763	10777	11122	12671
	BigLD	8056	8097	8147	8457	9448
	SSLD	6170	6141	6189	6556	7860
Chr. 8	FGT	9970	10231	10395	11030	12851
	CIT	11473	11004	11032	11422	13200
	BigLD	7882	7908	7995	8303	9335
	SSLD	6304	6250	6302	6604	7898
Chr. 9	FGT	8904	9146	9263	9797	11367
	CIT	10240	9891	9929	10170	11620
	BigLD	6768	6832	6880	7118	7985
	SSLD	5700	5641	5668	5970	7037
Chr. 10	FGT	9015	9281	9387	9959	11791
	CIT	10591	10175	10176	10497	12041
	BigLD	7459	7530	7556	7781	8706
	SSLD	5910	5875	5902	6225	7420
Chr. 11	FGT	8688	8920	9052	9548	11103
	CIT	10000	9722	9745	10057	11460
	BigLD	7173	7240	7290	7480	8402

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	SSLD	5553	5507	5548	5820	6837
Chr. 12	FGT	8256	8449	8553	9024	10687
	CIT	9496	9188	9174	9411	10924
	BigLD	7306	7340	7384	7660	8666
	SSLD	5502	5465	5492	5750	5750
Chr. 13	FGT	6362	6541	6630	7084	8288
	CIT	7329	7066	7073	7294	8460
	BigLD	5278	5303	5324	5504	6156
	SSLD	4146	4121	4145	4386	5161
Chr. 14	FGT	5858	6001	6076	6445	7617
	CIT	6815	6628	6639	6806	7857
	BigLD	4987	5038	5057	5183	5776
	SSLD	3875	3860	3874	4153	4867
Chr. 15	FGT	5551	5704	5810	6175	7118
	CIT	6445	6227	6243	6471	7376
	BigLD	4530	4577	4589	4765	5279
	SSLD	3747	3743	3768	4002	4654
Chr. 16	FGT	6253	6384	6473	6788	6788
	CIT	7329	7183	7192	7348	7348
	BigLD	4775	4783	4818	4894	5461
	SSLD	4121	4111	4142	4308	4308
Chr. 17	FGT	5189	5275	5338	5637	6529
	CIT	6101	5960	5950	6132	6881
	BigLD	4478	4497	4501	4629	5065
	SSLD	3583	3579	3594	3784	4436
Chr. 18	FGT	5592	5732	5815	6123	7179
	CIT	6469	6294	6322	6557	7511
	BigLD	4570	4600	4610	4769	5461
	SSLD	3718	3734	3767	3902	4667
Chr. 19	FGT	3748	3811	3845	4063	4642
	CIT	4462	4393	4399	4504	4883
	BigLD	3279	3286	3274	3389	3708
	SSLD	2709	2737	2755	2906	3315
Chr. 20	FGT	4808	4909	4952	5238	6193
	CIT	5586	5434	5431	5623	6413
	BigLD	3884	3913	3918	4052	4554
	SSLD	3170	3154	3187	3346	4094
Chr. r.	FGT	2780	2847	2875	3056	3531

	CIT	3212	3136	3135	3221	3669
	BigLD	2242	2264	2266	2336	2544
	SSLD	1873	1867	1876	1987	2369
Chr. 22	FGT	2988	3043	3076	3234	3752
	CIT	3452	3358	3371	3434	3931
	BigLD	2418	2431	2467	2513	2762
	SSLD	2055	2058	2070	2130	2484

B.3 Tables of All No. SNPs in all blocks

Table B.3: All numbers of SNPs in all blocks by partitioning NARAC data using four different methods and five MAF thresholds.

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
		Chr. 1	BigLD	35459	35319	35235
	CIT	33147	33590	33550	32837	30020
	FGT	35611	35205	35003	33985	30866
	SSLD	38810	38594	38481	37881	35687
Chr. 2	BigLD	38797	38673	38602	38083	36198
	CIT	35546	35978	35882	35195	32284
	FGT	38080	37689	37498	36532	33321
	SSLD	41996	41791	41670	41059	38937
Chr. 3	BigLD	32016	31930	31877	31498	30133
	CIT	29692	30034	29958	29445	27077
	FGT	31638	31322	31163	30379	27801
	SSLD	34912	34787	34666	34666	32431
Chr. 4	BigLD	28525	28422	28383	28009	26593
	CIT	27168	27514	27482	26956	24820
	FGT	28739	28445	28290	27618	25313
	SSLD	27168	30927	30837	30341	28725
Chr. 5	BigLD	29258	29209	29168	28815	27407
	CIT	27682	27991	27962	27382	25017
	FGT	29334	29059	28900	28141	25685
	SSLD	32096	31958	31877	31394	29710
Chr. 6	BigLD	31483	31371	31310	31021	29472
	CIT	29389	29787	29771	29299	27007
	FGT	31314	31020	30880	30161	27482
	SSLD	34067	33939	33820	33370	31591

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Chr. 7	BigLD	25538	25481	25412	25066	23827
	CIT	23591	23809	23763	23315	21356
	FGT	25200	24968	24850	24171	21971
	SSLD	27837	27735	27655	27186	25594
Chr. 8	BigLD	27423	27380	27283	26925	25688
	CIT	25184	25546	25484	24978	22769
	FGT	26895	26619	26446	25705	23449
	SSLD	29576	29449	29359	28940	27411
Chr. 9	BigLD	23080	22998	22954	22688	21635
	CIT	20823	21087	21022	20667	18816
	FGT	22340	22078	21953	21343	19353
	SSLD	24795	24701	24641	24248	22897
Chr. 10	BigLD	24909	24828	24777	24488	23367
	CIT	22877	23203	23169	22743	20826
	FGT	24681	24406	24292	23627	21359
	SSLD	27062	26926	26852	26419	24945
Chr. 11	BigLD	23202	23120	23054	22836	21655
	CIT	21284	21511	21453	21027	19267
	FGT	22841	22596	22453	21876	19906
	SSLD	25185	25094	25021	24676	23385
Chr. 12	BigLD	22981	22927	22868	22534	21311
	CIT	21562	21807	21799	21451	19608
	FGT	23018	22815	22701	22150	20098
	SSLD	25089	24999	24941	24568	24568
Chr. 13	BigLD	17862	17832	17805	17556	16755
	CIT	16579	16766	16727	16391	14988
	FGT	17711	17524	17429	16924	15439
	SSLD	19312	19229	19177	18854	17895
Chr. 14	FGT	BigLD	15663	15598	15571	15384
	CIT	CIT	14489	14637	14604	14345
	SSLD	FGT	15554	15404	15327	14903
	BigLD	SSLD	17002	16933	16891	16549
Chr. 15	FGT	BigLD	14092	14032	14005	13791
	CIT	CIT	12888	13050	13012	12668
	SSLD	FGT	13802	13641	13521	13096
	BigLD	SSLD	15274	15173	15115	14787
Chr. 16	BigLD	14162	14142	14105	13997	13303
	CIT	12403	12532	12508	12262	12262

	FGT	13608	13472	13375	12985	12985
	SSLD	15374	15299	15248	14998	14998
Chr. 17	BigLD	11848	11819	11803	11636	11093
	CIT	10644	10762	10749	10511	9511
	FGT	11657	11568	11501	11154	9999
	SSLD	13062	13004	12970	12725	11888
Chr. 18	BigLD	14341	14299	14282	14068	13274
	CIT	13076	13219	13172	12855	11648
	FGT	14053	13904	13817	13465	12137
	SSLD	15530	15449	15393	15186	14250
Chr. 19	BigLD	7575	7560	7560	7425	7007
	CIT	6623	6683	6667	6503	5971
	FGT	7482	7408	7370	7100	6337
	SSLD	8423	8366	8341	8142	7572
Chr. 20	BigLD	12047	12002	11999	11826	11186
	CIT	10909	11043	11035	10774	9746
	FGT	11808	11700	11653	11323	10070
	SSLD	13017	12974	12936	12715	11805
Chr. 21	BigLD	7014	6980	6982	6904	6616
	CIT	6366	6424	6421	6288	5732
	FGT	6860	6789	6757	6552	5954
	SSLD	7577	7545	7527	7379	6934
Chr. 22	BigLD	7035	7030	6993	6919	6603
	CIT	6305	6387	6369	6278	5668
	FGT	6822	6763	6727	6543	5897
	SSLD	7611	7570	7548	7448	6978

B.4 Tables of total length of all blocks (bp)

Table B.4: Total length of all blocks (bp)

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
		Chr. 1	BigLD	125449776	124851948	124410363
	CIT	128960794	132354172	132250055	128442188	115370848
	FGT	137199726	133999529	132543161	127340955	114474921
	SSLD	162597342	162892659	162549400	160044054	151719508
Chr. 2	BigLD	140790493	139989246	139578981	137436705	129058714
	CIT	136101949	139486128	138898456	135092513	120136970

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	FGT	146006072	143060285	141750183	136416548	123412571
	SSLD	175392179	175590161	175175298	172842861	164438500
Chr. 3	BigLD	115978640	115559677	115254662	113342694	107757700
	CIT	115798854	118577891	118372944	115883799	106308174
	FGT	121610605	119305254	118256045	114495020	104377816
	SSLD	148506112	148683128	148329390	148329390	139713072
Chr. 4	BigLD	109895369	109571283	109462875	107984089	101660485
	CIT	114443884	116850315	116517106	113558794	102922600
	FGT	119149183	117345794	116108529	112497592	101634583
	SSLD	114443884	141386714	141110425	139041947	131622689
Chr. 5	BigLD	104771914	104473035	104374988	103036870	97714975
	CIT	105788501	107961696	107845805	105451673	95389903
	FGT	110025404	108487588	107448723	103617941	94045756
	SSLD	133115114	133588233	133654092	132015555	125268932
Chr. 6	BigLD	104330915	103820178	103564704	102249806	97070122
	CIT	105946966	108447504	108487419	106203890	96488027
	FGT	109239542	107452180	106764190	103446937	93495073
	SSLD	129784756	129874119	129532603	127512363	121422678
Chr. 7	BigLD	87848136	87506920	87301370	85350416	80364096
	CIT	87247675	88851788	88742021	86285986	77217727
	FGT	92007267	90051148	89432281	85725962	76843392
	SSLD	112680804	112689173	112379171	110085875	103176371
Chr. 8	BigLD	86410870	86227206	85757702	84116172	79506759
	CIT	85245420	88152507	88052309	85711952	76277769
	FGT	89320891	87573519	86496641	83459692	75132554
	SSLD	108798908	108658425	108036301	106425824	100280838
Chr. 9	BigLD	67415365	67226649	66958287	66027712	62685479
	CIT	61679753	63428555	63257768	62210266	55727407
	FGT	62995247	64262186	63653575	61109399	55046205
	SSLD	80209698	80614054	80778720	79269355	74767231
Chr. 10	BigLD	78390319	78046040	77916947	76748872	72644472
	CIT	77023896	78804340	78805460	77124205	69252933
	FGT	80879969	79433665	78902862	76463752	67668620
	SSLD	96773912	96867487	96775580	95519848	90450566
Chr. 11	BigLD	78637211	78259367	78138056	76899185	72867738
	CIT	81992796	83431274	83187865	81483902	74219911
	FGT	46694669	45322226	44583827	41883396	34471424
	SSLD	103110803	103422390	103226103	101536043	57030491

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Chr. 12	BigLD	76619842	76366807	76086560	74876398	69929769
	CIT	77229590	79071068	79037423	77717425	69754294
	FGT	81884904	80699770	79935522	77147200	69448228
	SSLD	98552595	98887048	98760900	96787086	96787086
Chr. 13	BigLD	60219847	60128259	60067167	59088397	56300128
	CIT	58204744	59601018	59615369	58696322	52498409
	FGT	60612271	59649946	59218768	56955719	51074244
	SSLD	73194935	73369754	73458152	72487539	69025002
Chr. 14	BigLD	51915274	51631124	51637552	50498139	47705571
	CIT	51031050	51967469	51850362	50961767	45575391
	FGT	54375766	53560425	53130464	51036359	45944163
	SSLD	64497071	64642544	64586298	62816571	60024293
Chr. 15	BigLD	44984193	44643020	44625444	43702744	41507232
	CIT	43854931	44957863	44963675	43469753	38728648
	FGT	47778164	46217512	45460659	43218773	38962458
	SSLD	56733250	56318752	56305217	55146453	51661930
Chr. 16	BigLD	39809762	39772718	39630105	39175373	36603893
	CIT	35651891	36360379	36340367	35207672	35207672
	FGT	40666744	39319972	38753717	37137353	37137353
	SSLD	51057000	51182694	51011712	50172944	50172944
Chr. 17	BigLD	40087890	40008325	39969776	39418694	37356725
	CIT	38573133	39854729	40025139	39006936	35014785
	FGT	43826129	43126095	42692444	40681065	36143301
	SSLD	52496607	52612769	52900708	52017529	48766574
Chr. 18	BigLD	45542485	45424241	45327393	44761207	41862826
	CIT	42461112	43335878	43217020	42100122	37026914
	FGT	44974064	44130014	43642860	41975090	37191845
	SSLD	54592988	54535016	54558815	54048633	50439637
Chr. 19	BigLD	27321804	27227922	27328128	26594090	24807383
	CIT	23773756	24210176	24093221	23323767	21127761
	FGT	27043813	26527619	26248940	24923967	21714614
	SSLD	34562581	34258165	34128994	33298377	31289277
Chr. 20	BigLD	36072043	35858054	35850419	35307109	33631682
	CIT	33357798	34136163	34155615	33262177	29731025
	FGT	35444515	34937153	34694946	33533273	29977833
	SSLD	43449975	43691570	43527151	42866053	39856507
Chr. 21	BigLD	20965543	20875066	20842194	20424394	19676539
	CIT	18024293	18475681	18468492	17978825	16231799

	FGT	19594984	19217350	19047169	18079821	16363316
	SSLD	23767856	23727018	23744964	23267729	21856172
Chr. 22	BigLD	18530243	18511226	18376204	18230729	17338153
	CIT	17854094	18282348	18189558	17893410	15780909
	FGT	19314483	19048397	18886051	18054782	16039091
	SSLD	23294697	23321111	23202916	23104997	21806165

B.5 Tables of mean no. SNPs in blocks

Table B.5: The mean number of SNPs in blocks.

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Chr. 1	BigLD	5.76	5.76	5.77	5.77	5.81
	CIT	4.51	4.64	4.66	4.67	4.65
	FGT	4.65	4.61	4.59	4.53	4.47
	SSLD	5.85	6.05	6.07	6.13	6.23
Chr. 2	BigLD	5.84	5.86	5.85	5.86	5.86
	CIT	4.33	4.45	4.46	4.49	4.45
	FGT	4.49	4.45	4.43	4.38	4.30
	SSLD	5.88	6.04	6.07	6.15	6.22
Chr. 3	BigLD	5.80	5.84	5.84	5.84	5.88
	CIT	4.35	4.46	4.49	4.51	4.52
	FGT	4.50	4.46	4.45	4.41	4.36
	SSLD	5.88	6.04	6.09	6.09	6.22
Chr. 4	BigLD	5.64	5.65	5.66	5.66	5.65
	CIT	4.59	4.73	4.76	4.77	4.72
	FGT	4.73	4.70	4.68	4.64	4.58
	SSLD	4.59	6.07	6.11	6.15	6.22
Chr. 5	BigLD	5.90	5.89	5.90	5.91	5.98
	CIT	4.47	4.58	4.60	4.62	4.61
	FGT	4.58	4.55	4.53	4.49	4.42
	SSLD	5.98	6.17	6.21	6.28	6.36
Chr. 6	BigLD	6.19	6.21	6.21	6.25	6.30
	CIT	4.74	4.88	4.91	4.97	4.90
	FGT	4.84	4.80	4.79	4.74	4.67
	SSLD	6.29	6.49	6.55	6.58	6.64
Chr. 7	BigLD	5.87	5.88	5.89	5.86	5.91
	CIT	4.37	4.47	4.49	4.49	4.46

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	FGT	4.48	4.45	4.44	4.38	4.33
	SSLD	5.84	5.99	6.01	6.04	6.08
Chr. 8	BigLD	6.36	6.37	6.36	6.35	6.37
	CIT	4.44	4.59	4.61	4.62	4.57
	FGT	4.58	4.54	4.52	4.47	4.42
	SSLD	6.05	6.25	6.29	6.35	6.35
Chr. 9	BigLD	6.20	6.21	6.19	6.17	6.20
	CIT	4.22	4.35	4.36	4.39	4.37
	FGT	4.37	4.33	4.31	4.26	4.21
	SSLD	5.68	5.86	5.89	5.93	6.02
Chr. 10	BigLD	6.17	6.17	6.19	6.22	6.24
	CIT	4.45	4.60	4.62	4.63	4.59
	FGT	4.60	4.56	4.54	4.50	4.43
	SSLD	5.83	6.02	6.07	6.13	6.18
Chr. 11	BigLD	5.95	5.95	5.96	5.95	6.05
	CIT	4.43	4.52	4.54	4.56	4.53
	FGT	4.52	4.48	4.47	4.42	4.39
	SSLD	5.91	6.08	6.11	6.14	6.24
Chr. 12	BigLD	5.86	5.88	5.88	5.89	5.90
	CIT	4.59	4.71	4.73	4.77	4.71
	FGT	4.69	4.66	4.64	4.61	4.55
	SSLD	5.94	6.10	6.13	6.22	6.22
Chr. 13	BigLD	6.16	6.16	6.17	6.23	6.28
	CIT	4.52	4.67	4.70	4.76	4.67
	FGT	4.62	4.58	4.57	4.49	4.43
	SSLD	6.00	6.19	6.23	6.29	6.36
Chr. 14	BigLD	5.80	5.81	5.82	5.88	5.96
	CIT	4.32	4.42	4.44	4.48	4.43
	FGT	4.49	4.46	4.44	4.39	4.31
	SSLD	5.81	5.96	6.00	6.02	6.07
Chr. 15	BigLD	5.74	5.74	5.77	5.77	5.74
	CIT	4.07	4.19	4.21	4.26	4.23
	FGT	4.33	4.29	4.27	4.22	4.16
	SSLD	5.35	5.52	5.56	5.64	5.67
Chr. 16	BigLD	5.72	5.74	5.73	5.76	5.77
	CIT	3.79	3.85	3.86	3.89	3.89
	FGT	4.00	3.97	3.95	3.92	3.92
	SSLD	5.07	5.19	5.20	5.27	5.27

Chr. 17	BigLD	5.15	5.16	5.18	5.20	5.21
	CIT	3.92	3.99	4.02	4.02	4.02
	FGT	4.14	4.11	4.09	4.04	4.00
	SSLD	4.99	5.09	5.11	5.13	5.18
Chr. 18	BigLD	5.83	5.84	5.85	5.89	5.81
	CIT	4.22	4.32	4.33	4.34	4.30
	FGT	4.40	4.36	4.34	4.29	4.23
	SSLD	5.55	5.65	5.68	5.76	5.78
Chr. 19	BigLD	4.68	4.70	4.73	4.71	4.74
	CIT	3.58	3.63	3.64	3.67	3.69
	FGT	3.75	3.74	3.72	3.68	3.64
	SSLD	4.44	4.48	4.48	4.49	4.59
Chr. 20	BigLD	5.77	5.79	5.79	5.81	5.90
	CIT	4.11	4.19	4.21	4.22	4.21
	FGT	4.26	4.23	4.22	4.17	4.16
	SSLD	5.55	5.68	5.67	5.73	5.74
Chr. 21	BigLD	5.82	5.85	5.83	5.81	5.97
	CIT	4.17	4.26	4.27	4.31	4.25
	FGT	4.32	4.28	4.27	4.21	4.15
	SSLD	5.42	5.54	5.57	5.61	5.54
Chr. 22	BigLD	5.64	5.60	5.57	5.64	5.69
	CIT	4.06	4.15	4.15	4.17	4.07
	FGT	4.25	4.22	4.21	4.16	4.08
	SSLD	5.21	5.32	5.34	5.42	5.55

B.6 Tables mean block length (bp)

Table B.6: The mean block length (bp).

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Chr. 1	BigLD	20361.92	20377.34	20358.43	20314.25	20324.81
	CIT	17557.63	18283.49	18385.94	18275.78	17856.50
	FGT	17913.53	17550.69	17380.43	16978.79	16580.96
	SSLD	24494.93	25527.76	25642.75	25913.87	26473.48
Chr. 2	BigLD	21181.06	21197.64	21145.13	21137.60	20896.81
	CIT	16585.66	17246.06	17250.18	17215.82	16563.76
	FGT	17219.73	16904.20	16759.30	16370.64	15930.37
	SSLD	24571.61	25392.65	25528.32	25878.55	26284.93

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Chr. 3	BigLD	21018.24	21126.08	21108.91	20997.16	21030.00
	CIT	16981.79	17624.54	17723.15	17740.94	17741.68
	FGT	17293.89	16999.89	16876.84	16607.92	16375.56
	SSLD	25005.24	25822.01	26050.12	26050.12	26800.90
Chr. 4	BigLD	21744.24	21774.90	21835.80	21810.56	21606.90
	CIT	19331.74	20087.73	20200.61	20106.02	19559.60
	FGT	19622.72	19379.98	19207.37	18888.11	18385.42
	SSLD	19331.74	27760.99	27959.27	28163.25	28514.45
Chr. 5	BigLD	21114.86	21080.11	21128.54	21131.43	21316.53
	CIT	17081.95	17649.45	17755.32	17809.77	17570.44
	FGT	17178.05	16991.01	16859.99	16518.08	16167.40
	SSLD	24816.39	25779.28	26017.93	26418.96	26812.70
Chr. 6	BigLD	20521.42	20546.25	20540.40	20589.97	20737.05
	CIT	17104.77	17757.90	17887.46	18015.93	17511.44
	FGT	16878.79	16623.17	16550.02	16244.81	15870.83
	SSLD	23972.06	24827.78	25069.21	25160.29	25508.97
Chr. 7	BigLD	20194.97	20190.80	20232.07	19946.35	19936.52
	CIT	16171.95	16676.39	16756.42	16615.83	16144.20
	FGT	16359.76	16063.35	15970.05	15541.33	15144.54
	SSLD	23657.53	24328.41	24430.25	24474.41	24507.45
Chr. 8	BigLD	20025.69	20062.17	19999.46	19848.08	19714.05
	CIT	15042.42	15854.77	15934.19	15843.24	15319.90
	FGT	15203.56	14944.29	14783.22	14527.36	14149.26
	SSLD	22249.27	23074.63	23129.16	23369.75	23218.53
Chr. 9	BigLD	18122.41	18159.55	18067.54	17952.07	17951.17
	CIT	12498.43	13078.05	13115.85	13210.93	12935.80
	FGT	12313.38	12610.32	12510.53	12192.62	11987.41
	SSLD	18367.23	19130.06	19320.43	19381.26	19644.57
Chr. 10	BigLD	19417.96	19380.69	19469.50	19489.30	19413.27
	CIT	14993.95	15614.10	15717.08	15710.78	15267.40
	FGT	15075.48	14830.78	14753.71	14550.67	14042.05
	SSLD	20851.95	21670.58	21880.08	22146.96	22422.05
Chr. 11	BigLD	20173.73	20154.36	20206.38	20031.05	20354.12
	CIT	17056.96	17542.32	17620.81	17686.98	17463.51
	FGT	9242.81	8994.29	8867.11	8466.42	7606.23
	SSLD	24198.73	25078.17	25226.32	25264.01	15228.44
Chr. 12	BigLD	19535.91	19571.20	19574.62	19555.08	19360.40
	CIT	16456.34	17077.98	17152.22	17282.06	16739.69

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	FGT	16680.57	16472.70	16350.08	16042.25	15712.27
	SSLD	23320.54	24124.68	24277.51	24484.46	24484.46
Chr. 13	BigLD	20779.80	20784.05	20806.08	20968.20	21094.09
	CIT	15876.91	16601.95	16755.30	17048.02	16375.05
	FGT	15821.53	15602.92	15514.48	15123.66	14655.45
	SSLD	22759.62	23606.74	23850.05	24178.63	24529.14
Chr. 14	BigLD	19235.00	19229.47	19289.34	19303.57	19439.92
	CIT	15219.52	15681.19	15750.41	15925.55	15507.11
	FGT	15711.00	15506.78	15391.21	15023.95	14711.55
	SSLD	22042.74	22745.44	22951.78	22834.09	23265.23
Chr. 15	BigLD	18316.04	18273.85	18379.51	18285.67	18070.19
	CIT	13847.47	14451.26	14556.06	14621.51	14248.95
	FGT	14991.58	14538.38	14363.56	13919.09	13608.96
	SSLD	19871.54	20479.55	20723.30	21024.19	20966.69
Chr. 16	BigLD	16071.77	16134.98	16090.18	16114.92	15887.11
	CIT	10896.05	11170.62	11216.16	11177.04	11177.04
	FGT	11957.29	11578.32	11438.52	11209.58	11209.58
	SSLD	16822.73	17350.07	17410.14	17629.28	17629.28
Chr. 17	BigLD	17437.10	17478.52	17553.70	17613.36	17530.14
	CIT	14191.73	14788.40	14979.47	14910.91	14805.41
	FGT	15546.69	15314.66	15182.23	14718.19	14451.54
	SSLD	20052.18	20584.03	20851.68	20957.91	21230.55
Chr. 18	BigLD	18505.68	18548.08	18561.59	18752.08	18320.71
	CIT	13719.26	14148.18	14197.44	14213.41	13668.11
	FGT	14076.39	13851.23	13715.54	13376.38	12976.92
	SSLD	19511.43	19954.27	20132.40	20488.49	20445.74
Chr. 19	BigLD	16886.16	16911.75	17101.46	16853.04	16773.08
	CIT	12857.63	13157.70	13165.69	13169.83	13057.95
	FGT	13562.59	13377.52	13263.74	12934.08	12458.18
	SSLD	18229.21	18349.31	18348.92	18376.59	18951.71
Chr. 20	BigLD	17275.88	17306.01	17285.64	17349.93	17728.88
	CIT	12578.36	12959.82	13021.58	13023.56	12837.23
	FGT	12782.01	12630.93	12561.53	12337.48	12387.53
	SSLD	18536.68	19121.04	19090.86	19326.44	19385.46
Chr. 21	BigLD	17398.79	17497.96	17412.03	17177.79	17742.60
	CIT	11803.73	12243.66	12271.42	12331.16	12023.55
	FGT	12331.65	12124.51	12047.55	11611.96	11410.96
	SSLD	16989.18	17433.52	17562.84	17694.09	17457.01

Chr. 22	BigLD	14847.95	14738.24	14642.39	14857.97	14946.68
	CIT	11503.93	11871.65	11849.87	11873.53	11320.59
	FGT	12033.95	11897.81	11818.56	11485.23	11107.40
	SSLD	15944.35	16388.69	16421.03	16828.11	17347.78

B.7 Tables of mean r^2 within a block

Table B.7: The mean r^2 within a block.

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Chr. 1	BigLD	0.3851	0.3852	0.385	0.3837	0.3832
	CIT	0.2964	0.2918	0.2927	0.299	0.3232
	FGT	0.2733	0.2773	0.2791	0.2903	0.3192
	SSLD	0.2543	0.2574	0.2593	0.2667	0.2852
Chr. 2	BigLD	0.3986	0.3977	0.3975	0.3971	0.3934
	CIT	0.3129	0.309	0.3101	0.3154	0.3401
	FGT	0.2882	0.293	0.2948	0.3039	0.3317
	SSLD	0.2682	0.2727	0.274	0.2799	0.2979
Chr. 3	BigLD	0.3993	0.3978	0.3981	0.3993	0.3963
	CIT	0.3106	0.3064	0.3064	0.3135	0.337
	FGT	0.2857	0.2896	0.2918	0.3018	0.3288
	SSLD	0.265	0.2689	0.2706	0.2706	0.2947
Chr. 4	BigLD	0.407	0.4069	0.4062	0.4039	0.4058
	CIT	0.3151	0.3095	0.3095	0.3176	0.3405
	FGT	0.295	0.2994	0.3008	0.3093	0.3354
	SSLD	0.3151	0.2706	0.2727	0.281	0.2988
Chr. 5	BigLD	0.3943	0.3942	0.3936	0.3937	0.3902
	CIT	0.3044	0.3004	0.3008	0.3088	0.3332
	FGT	0.2806	0.2843	0.2865	0.2957	0.3249
	SSLD	0.254	0.2571	0.2593	0.2675	0.2869
Chr. 6	BigLD	0.3878	0.3871	0.387	0.3837	0.3835
	CIT	0.2917	0.2872	0.2887	0.2961	0.3168
	FGT	0.2722	0.276	0.2777	0.2862	0.3132
	SSLD	0.2499	0.2538	0.2558	0.2637	0.2814
Chr. 7	BigLD	0.3988	0.3981	0.3984	0.3975	0.3914
	CIT	0.2999	0.2982	0.2968	0.3048	0.3265
	FGT	0.278	0.2811	0.2827	0.2917	0.3207
	SSLD	0.2611	0.2643	0.2657	0.2724	0.2934

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Chr. 8	BigLD	0.3993	0.398	0.3975	0.398	0.3967
	CIT	0.3155	0.3106	0.3116	0.3175	0.3486
	FGT	0.292	0.2962	0.2978	0.3071	0.3389
	SSLD	0.2686	0.2715	0.2737	0.2801	0.3005
Chr. 9	BigLD	0.1811	0.1808	0.1804	0.1801	0.1815
	CIT	0.3074	0.3022	0.3022	0.309	0.3308
	FGT	0.2824	0.2866	0.2887	0.2984	0.3262
	SSLD	0.2607	0.265	0.2658	0.2746	0.2907
Chr. 10	BigLD	0.3825	0.381	0.3807	0.3794	0.3765
	CIT	0.2955	0.2918	0.2925	0.299	0.3254
	FGT	0.2728	0.2769	0.2789	0.2881	0.3184
	SSLD	0.2537	0.2583	0.2595	0.2668	0.2877
Chr. 11	BigLD	0.3926	0.3927	0.3929	0.393	0.3873
	CIT	0.2999	0.2963	0.2975	0.3048	0.3298
	FGT	0.279	0.2839	0.2859	0.2956	0.3241
	SSLD	0.2591	0.2623	0.2636	0.2698	0.2888
Chr. 12	BigLD	0.3863	0.3857	0.3856	0.3869	0.3837
	CIT	0.2969	0.2915	0.2919	0.2969	0.3228
	FGT	0.2739	0.2775	0.2794	0.2877	0.3173
	SSLD	0.2509	0.2548	0.2564	0.2644	0.2644
Chr. 13	BigLD	0.3778	0.3772	0.3767	0.3762	0.3744
	CIT	0.2971	0.2916	0.2922	0.2982	0.3209
	FGT	0.2739	0.2787	0.2807	0.2912	0.3138
	SSLD	0.2496	0.253	0.2552	0.2639	0.28
Chr. 14	BigLD	0.3845	0.3845	0.3842	0.3812	0.3812
	CIT	0.2974	0.2931	0.2943	0.3	0.3294
	FGT	0.2704	0.2735	0.2758	0.2852	0.3184
	SSLD	0.249	0.2538	0.2551	0.2655	0.2869
Chr. 15	BigLD	0.39	0.3907	0.3903	0.3878	0.3877
	CIT	0.3128	0.3068	0.3078	0.3163	0.3462
	FGT	0.2853	0.2906	0.2941	0.3043	0.3333
	SSLD	0.2647	0.2689	0.2695	0.2775	0.2961
Chr. 16	BigLD	0.3809	0.3806	0.3807	0.3799	0.3771
	CIT	0.2971	0.2942	0.2948	0.3022	0.3022
	FGT	0.2752	0.2779	0.2804	0.2911	0.2911
	SSLD	0.2552	0.2603	0.262	0.2687	0.2687
Chr. 17	BigLD	0.3919	0.3899	0.3887	0.3899	0.3904
	CIT	0.3011	0.2971	0.297	0.303	0.3337

	FGT	0.2701	0.2733	0.2755	0.2866	0.3197
	SSLD	0.2623	0.2649	0.266	0.274	0.2964
Chr. 18	BigLD	0.4008	0.4005	0.3999	0.3997	0.3962
	CIT	0.309	0.3052	0.307	0.3136	0.3433
	FGT	0.2807	0.2851	0.2873	0.2982	0.3266
	SSLD	0.2662	0.272	0.2738	0.2806	0.299
Chr. 19	BigLD	0.3965	0.3954	0.3939	0.3925	0.3913
	CIT	0.3146	0.3117	0.3109	0.3163	0.3332
	FGT	0.2674	0.2717	0.2729	0.2837	0.3146
	SSLD	0.2617	0.2643	0.2654	0.2738	0.2936
Chr. 20	BigLD	0.3887	0.3906	0.3893	0.3858	0.3817
	CIT	0.3023	0.2987	0.2999	0.3057	0.3351
	FGT	0.2769	0.2798	0.2815	0.2931	0.3264
	SSLD	0.2581	0.2606	0.2629	0.2694	0.2944
Chr. 21	BigLD	0.3904	0.3889	0.3881	0.3933	0.3881
	CIT	0.3096	0.3042	0.304	0.3107	0.3421
	FGT	0.2854	0.2894	0.292	0.3025	0.3342
	SSLD	0.2693	0.2728	0.2735	0.2839	0.3087
Chr. 22	BigLD	0.3871	0.3884	0.389	0.391	0.3872
	CIT	0.293	0.2899	0.2916	0.2968	0.3297
	FGT	0.2723	0.2765	0.2787	0.2864	0.3208
	SSLD	0.262	0.266	0.269	0.2726	0.2948

B.8 Tables of the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without considering singleton blocks.

Table B.8: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without considering the singleton blocks.

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
		Chr. 1	BigLD	0.1657	0.168	0.1695
Chr. 1	CIT	0.1638	0.1622	0.1639	0.1719	0.1936
	FGT	0.1656	0.1727	0.1755	0.1858	0.2071
	SSLD	0.1436	0.1492	0.1516	0.1609	0.1803
	Chr. 2	BigLD	0.1761	0.1796	0.1815	0.1878
Chr. 2	CIT	0.1795	0.1779	0.1803	0.1888	0.2099
	FGT	0.1741	0.1803	0.1827	0.1939	0.2208
	SSLD	0.1579	0.1635	0.1665	0.1759	0.197
	Chr. 1:	BigLD	0.1729	0.1753	0.177	0.1849

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	CIT	0.1773	0.1757	0.1771	0.1829	0.2036
	FGT	0.1726	0.1773	0.1811	0.191	0.2133
	SSLD	0.1576	0.1614	0.1643	0.1643	0.1872
Chr. 4	BigLD	0.1676	0.1704	0.171	0.1776	0.1951
	CIT	0.1711	0.1714	0.1728	0.1838	0.2008
	FGT	0.1699	0.176	0.1795	0.1887	0.2108
	SSLD	0.1711	0.1563	0.1583	0.1678	0.185
Chr. 5	BigLD	0.17	0.1738	0.1757	0.1834	0.1993
	CIT	0.1781	0.1783	0.1786	0.1856	0.2067
	FGT	0.1758	0.1817	0.1848	0.1949	0.2193
	SSLD	0.1496	0.1555	0.1564	0.1656	0.1877
Chr. 6	BigLD	0.1665	0.1708	0.1721	0.1774	0.1961
	CIT	0.1698	0.1691	0.1691	0.1757	0.198
	FGT	0.171	0.1771	0.1793	0.1907	0.2149
	SSLD	0.1496	0.1543	0.1562	0.1681	0.1912
Chr. 7	BigLD	0.1634	0.1656	0.1658	0.1722	0.1891
	CIT	0.1694	0.1682	0.1687	0.1755	0.1977
	FGT	0.1715	0.1751	0.1775	0.1877	0.21
	SSLD	0.1458	0.1505	0.152	0.1632	0.1865
Chr. 8	BigLD	0.1784	0.1815	0.1832	0.1913	0.2081
	CIT	0.1878	0.1856	0.1874	0.196	0.2191
	FGT	0.183	0.1893	0.193	0.2058	0.2307
	SSLD	0.165	0.168	0.171	0.1809	0.2085
Chr. 9	BigLD	0.164	0.1663	0.1679	0.1741	0.1916
	CIT	0.1723	0.171	0.173	0.1808	0.2047
	FGT	0.1756	0.1833	0.186	0.1949	0.2178
	SSLD	0.1566	0.1582	0.1596	0.1663	0.1914
Chr. 10	BigLD	0.1618	0.1656	0.1658	0.1716	0.1915
	CIT	0.1696	0.1693	0.1703	0.1752	0.202
	FGT	0.1671	0.174	0.1764	0.1866	0.2127
	SSLD	0.1517	0.1581	0.1586	0.1697	0.1876
Chr. 11	BigLD	0.169	0.1725	0.1743	0.1786	0.1962
	CIT	0.1743	0.1743	0.1766	0.1824	0.2023
	FGT	0.174	0.1828	0.1854	0.1973	0.2195
	SSLD	0.1493	0.1553	0.1579	0.1689	0.1898
Chr. 12	BigLD	0.1661	0.1681	0.1704	0.1754	0.1867
	CIT	0.1689	0.1683	0.1694	0.1734	0.1934
	FGT	0.1652	0.1709	0.1743	0.181	0.2051

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	SSLD	0.1475	0.152	0.155	0.1606	0.1606
Chr. 13	BigLD	0.157	0.1595	0.1606	0.1655	0.1837
	CIT	0.167	0.1638	0.1631	0.1699	0.1934
	FGT	0.1686	0.1762	0.1783	0.1864	0.209
	SSLD	0.1512	0.1568	0.1589	0.1671	0.19
Chr. 14	BigLD	0.1606	0.1649	0.1657	0.1725	0.1878
	CIT	0.1643	0.1638	0.1651	0.169	0.1903
	FGT	0.1673	0.1722	0.1755	0.1844	0.2105
	SSLD	0.1453	0.1493	0.1503	0.162	0.1817
Chr. 15	BigLD	0.1592	0.1611	0.1633	0.1681	0.1834
	CIT	0.1605	0.1624	0.1651	0.1734	0.1962
	FGT	0.1657	0.1722	0.1763	0.1853	0.2033
	SSLD	0.1538	0.1555	0.1585	0.167	0.1837
Chr. 16	BigLD	0.1539	0.1563	0.1559	0.1604	0.1746
	CIT	0.1686	0.1689	0.1709	0.1745	0.1745
	FGT	0.1679	0.1736	0.1763	0.1843	0.1843
	SSLD	0.1525	0.1577	0.1608	0.1674	0.1674
Chr. 17	BigLD	0.1588	0.1605	0.1624	0.1647	0.1782
	CIT	0.1529	0.1502	0.1517	0.158	0.1754
	FGT	0.1498	0.1542	0.1569	0.1653	0.1848
	SSLD	0.1425	0.1466	0.1488	0.1547	0.1716
Chr. 18	BigLD	0.161	0.1637	0.1635	0.1641	0.1841
	CIT	0.1727	0.1706	0.1723	0.1797	0.2027
	FGT	0.1706	0.1759	0.1783	0.1914	0.2127
	SSLD	0.1461	0.1541	0.1563	0.1637	0.1883
Chr. 19	BigLD	0.1323	0.1325	0.1334	0.1358	0.1439
	CIT	0.1391	0.1386	0.1394	0.1431	0.1538
	FGT	0.1412	0.1452	0.146	0.1548	0.1662
	SSLD	0.126	0.1304	0.1307	0.1392	0.1493
Chr. 20	BigLD	0.1497	0.1503	0.153	0.1591	0.1703
	CIT	0.1602	0.1601	0.161	0.1703	0.1896
	FGT	0.1578	0.1627	0.1648	0.1759	0.201
	SSLD	0.1462	0.1501	0.1536	0.1606	0.1829
Chr. 21	BigLD	0.15	0.1511	0.1516	0.1594	0.1728
	CIT	0.1621	0.1625	0.1645	0.1694	0.1903
	FGT	0.1571	0.1617	0.1631	0.1743	0.1963
	SSLD	0.1455	0.1459	0.1484	0.1551	0.1823
Chr. r.	BigLD	0.1562	0.1569	0.1583	0.1632	0.1802

	CIT	0.1579	0.1586	0.1602	0.1667	0.1806
	FGT	0.1631	0.1671	0.1693	0.1784	0.1946
	SSLD	0.1461	0.1474	0.1487	0.1533	0.1676

B.9 Tables of the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with considering the singleton blocks.

Table B.92: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with considering the singleton blocks.

Chr. No.	Method MAF	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Chr. 1	BigLD	0.1397	0.1398	0.1408	0.1445	0.1544
	CIT	0.175	0.1804	0.1814	0.1853	0.1948
	FGT	0.1952	0.1953	0.1951	0.1951	0.1979
	SSLD	0.1489	0.1524	0.1532	0.1585	0.1704
Chr. 2	BigLD	0.1513	0.1526	0.1535	0.1568	0.1679
	CIT	0.1854	0.1899	0.1911	0.1956	0.2031
	FGT	0.203	0.2032	0.2031	0.2033	0.2081
	SSLD	0.1615	0.1646	0.1664	0.1699	0.182
Chr. 3	BigLD	0.1481	0.1492	0.15	0.1528	0.1626
	CIT	0.1869	0.1906	0.1909	0.1942	0.2049
	FGT	0.2004	0.2003	0.2005	0.2008	0.2056
	SSLD	0.1625	0.1644	0.1658	0.1658	0.176
Chr. 4	BigLD	0.1468	0.1484	0.1486	0.1502	0.1611
	CIT	0.1835	0.1889	0.1898	0.1938	0.2009
	FGT	0.196	0.1961	0.1966	0.1975	0.2032
	SSLD	0.1835	0.1589	0.16	0.1638	0.1717
Chr. 5	BigLD	0.1437	0.1458	0.1467	0.1505	0.1597
	CIT	0.1859	0.19	0.1914	0.1944	0.2039
	FGT	0.2052	0.2055	0.2061	0.2063	0.2111
	SSLD	0.1538	0.1571	0.1577	0.1621	0.1754
Chr. 6	BigLD	0.1431	0.145	0.1448	0.1488	0.1596
	CIT	0.1792	0.1842	0.1848	0.1885	0.1964
	FGT	0.1999	0.1997	0.1996	0.2008	0.2036
	SSLD	0.1562	0.1583	0.1593	0.1635	0.174
Chr. 7	BigLD	0.1389	0.1403	0.1406	0.1454	0.1557
	CIT	0.1853	0.1879	0.1889	0.1919	0.2023
	FGT	0.2021	0.202	0.2021	0.2036	0.2081
	SSLD	0.1499	0.1528	0.1529	0.1586	0.1728

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Chr. 8	BigLD	0.152	0.1535	0.154	0.1571	0.1686
	CIT	0.1945	0.2003	0.2031	0.2067	0.2146
	FGT	0.2109	0.2107	0.2112	0.2125	0.2167
	SSLD	0.1661	0.168	0.1688	0.1746	0.1911
Chr. 9	BigLD	0.1445	0.1451	0.146	0.1502	0.1601
	CIT	0.1877	0.1927	0.1938	0.1964	0.2069
	FGT	0.2062	0.2057	0.2061	0.2062	0.2089
	SSLD	0.1638	0.1639	0.1645	0.1679	0.1826
Chr. 10	BigLD	0.1392	0.1414	0.1417	0.1444	0.1585
	CIT	0.183	0.1884	0.1888	0.1914	0.2013
	FGT	0.1995	0.2003	0.2004	0.201	0.2054
	SSLD	0.1559	0.1587	0.1584	0.1628	0.1727
Chr. 11	BigLD	0.1465	0.1477	0.1487	0.1518	0.1635
	CIT	0.1845	0.1886	0.1897	0.1924	0.2001
	FGT	0.2024	0.2029	0.2026	0.2039	0.2071
	SSLD	0.1528	0.1567	0.1585	0.1641	0.1745
Chr. 12	BigLD	0.1406	0.1414	0.1423	0.1451	0.1556
	CIT	0.1755	0.1814	0.1823	0.1864	0.1934
	FGT	0.1889	0.1884	0.1886	0.19	0.1948
	SSLD	0.1507	0.1527	0.1551	0.1583	0.1583
Chr. 13	BigLD	0.1391	0.14	0.1409	0.1445	0.1563
	CIT	0.1763	0.1809	0.1821	0.1873	0.1972
	FGT	0.1964	0.197	0.1968	0.1973	0.2002
	SSLD	0.157	0.1598	0.1599	0.1636	0.1778
Chr. 14	BigLD	0.1383	0.1403	0.141	0.1465	0.155
	CIT	0.1783	0.183	0.1839	0.1868	0.197
	FGT	0.1963	0.1961	0.1959	0.1975	0.202
	SSLD	0.1511	0.1528	0.153	0.1576	0.1714
Chr. 15	BigLD	0.1428	0.145	0.145	0.1492	0.1599
	CIT	0.1774	0.185	0.1867	0.1912	0.2023
	FGT	0.196	0.1957	0.1968	0.1965	0.2004
	SSLD	0.1601	0.1599	0.1613	0.1655	0.1749
Chr. 16	BigLD	0.1384	0.14	0.1395	0.1423	0.1499
	CIT	0.184	0.1873	0.1885	0.19	0.19
	FGT	0.1997	0.1983	0.1984	0.199	0.199
	SSLD	0.1576	0.1599	0.161	0.164	0.164
Chr. 17	BigLD	0.1432	0.144	0.1452	0.1473	0.1557
	CIT	0.1777	0.1806	0.1818	0.1841	0.1927

	FGT	0.1943	0.194	0.1938	0.1935	0.1977
	SSLD	0.1529	0.155	0.1564	0.1595	0.1673
Chr. 18	BigLD	0.1465	0.1471	0.1462	0.1466	0.1605
	CIT	0.1861	0.1885	0.1896	0.1919	0.2034
	FGT	0.2008	0.2008	0.2005	0.2022	0.2061
	SSLD	0.1514	0.1554	0.1566	0.161	0.175
Chr. 19	BigLD	0.1257	0.1266	0.1267	0.1306	0.1377
	CIT	0.169	0.1704	0.1712	0.1753	0.1829
	FGT	0.1859	0.1853	0.1854	0.1875	0.1917
	SSLD	0.14	0.1421	0.1422	0.1483	0.1553
Chr. 20	BigLD	0.1347	0.1358	0.1358	0.1387	0.1502
	CIT	0.182	0.1863	0.1865	0.1927	0.1963
	FGT	0.1938	0.1943	0.1936	0.1957	0.1995
	SSLD	0.1536	0.1558	0.1565	0.1613	0.1712
Chr. 21	BigLD	0.1397	0.1419	0.1418	0.1472	0.1553
	CIT	0.1894	0.192	0.1933	0.1948	0.201
	FGT	0.1936	0.1941	0.194	0.1959	0.1961
	SSLD	0.1521	0.1522	0.1545	0.1575	0.1694
Chr. 22	BigLD	0.1308	0.1317	0.1324	0.1325	0.1475
	CIT	0.1803	0.1846	0.1858	0.189	0.1917
	FGT	0.1965	0.196	0.1967	0.1964	0.1971
	SSLD	0.1556	0.1549	0.1549	0.158	0.1677

B.10 Tables of the intersection percentage of the four methods of partitioning

Table B.10: The intersection percentage of the four methods of partitioning.

Chr. No.	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Chr. 1	69.41044	69.7696	69.60346	67.76125	60.40705
Chr. 2	69.85484	70.34702	70.04763	68.14924	61.00249
Chr. 3	69.28318	69.75743	69.50668	67.93404	61.03025
Chr. 4	72.64926	72.55118	72.45617	70.63872	63.79796
Chr. 5	70.48078	71.05498	70.8854	68.98727	61.88266
Chr. 6	71.84461	72.35059	72.11447	70.59088	63.06291
Chr. 7	69.45698	69.72028	69.4775	67.52154	60.55601
Chr. 8	70.59697	71.28429	70.88093	68.80929	61.66828
Chr. 9	68.92988	69.43892	69.10977	67.34155	59.98546
Chr. 10	69.97282	70.45992	70.23402	68.32092	61.07797

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Chr. 11	69.05994	69.3772	69.13925	67.50387	60.07101
Chr. 12	70.28636	70.88564	70.68462	69.04608	61.8168
Chr. 13	71.24296	71.7518	71.51467	69.61269	62.30116
Chr. 14	69.1772	69.53373	69.28862	67.69539	60.19163
Chr. 15	68.5884	69.29976	68.90387	66.38006	59.53854
Chr. 16	63.98542	64.39247	64.08262	62.61239	59.67801
Chr. 17	63.74849	64.21901	64.16197	62.30128	55.82092
Chr. 18	68.83891	69.11854	68.7234	66.78419	59.1003
Chr. 19	60.1126	60.44825	60.31832	58.73755	53.08575
Chr. 20	68.0705	68.36668	68.33779	66.17063	58.5061
Chr. 21	68.21513	68.78649	68.7368	67.03515	60.00497
Chr. 22	65.3504	65.94759	65.50884	64.156	57.45277

Appendix C

Supplementary results

In this appendix the we shall present the charts of the measured parameters.

C.1 The total number of haplotype blocks.

Figure C.1 shows that chromosome 2 gives the highest number of haplotype blocks.

Figure C.1: The total number of haplotype blocks along chromosomes from 1 to 4.

chromosome 4 the SSLD with MAF=0.001 produce relatively high value.

Figure C.2: The total number of haplotype blocks along chromosomes from 5 to 8.

Figure C.2 shows different order in chromosome 6, where BigLD has higher number of blocks than SSLD.

Figure C.3: The total number of haplotype blocks along chromosomes from 9 to 12.

In Figure C.3, the pattern of chromosome 6 is repeated in chromosome 9. The BigLD shows convergent outcomes especially in MAF from (0.001 to 0.05).

Figure C.4: The total number of haplotype blocks along chromosomes from 13 to 16.

In Figure C.4 it is obvious that the BigLD has a very small number of haplotype blocks comparing to other methods. More than 1000 blocks in FGT compared to BigLD. The number of haplotype blocks depends on the total number of SNPs. In

chromosome 16 the number of blocks is more than that in chromosome 15 since chromosome 16 has higher number of SNPs (see Table 3.2 in chapter 3).

Figure C.5: The total number of haplotype blocks along chromosomes from 17 to 20.

Similarly, chromosome 18 has 16450 SNPs and chromosome 17 has 14027 SNPs, chromosome 18 has higher number of haplotype blocks (Figure C.5).

Figure C.6: The total number of haplotype blocks along chromosomes 21 and 22

Chromosome 21 has the lower number of haplotype blocks and the lowest value with BigLD method and 0.1 MAF.

C. 2 The total number of haplotype blocks with considering the singleton blocks.

Figure C.7 shows that MAF= 0.1 produces the highest values and that's logically true because it has the lower number of haplotype blocks and as a result the highest number of remaining singleton SNPs.

Figure C.7: The total number of haplotype blocks considering the singleton blocks along chromosomes from 1 to 4

In Figure C.8 chromosome 8 has higher values than chromosome 7.

Figure C.8: The total number of haplotype blocks considering the singleton blocks along chromosomes from 6 to 8

The explanation is that chromosome 8 has higher number of SNPs (see Table 3.3).

Figure C.9: The total number of haplotype blocks considering the singleton blocks along chromosomes from 9 to 12

Figure C.9 and Figure C.10 shows the different in the pattern with MAF =0.001.

Figure C.10: The total number of haplotype blocks considering the singleton blocks along chromosomes from 13 to 16

Figure C.11: The total number of haplotype blocks considering the singleton blocks along chromosomes from 17 to 20

Figure C.12 shows the lowest value in SSLD with $MAF = 0.01$.

Figure C.12: The total number of haplotype blocks considering the singleton blocks along chromosomes 21 and chromosome 22

C. 3 Total number of SNPs in all blocks

Figure C.13 shows that chromosomes 2 has the highest values.

Figure C.13: The total number of SNPs in all haplotype blocks from chromosome 1 to 4

Figure C.14 shows that chromosome 6 has higher values than chromosome 5, 4 and 8. The explanation is that chromosome 6 has high number of SNPs (see Table 3.4 in chapter 3)

Figure C.14: The total number of SNPs in all haplotype blocks from chromosome 5 to 8

Similarly, in chromosome 10 which have relatively high number of SNPs (Figure C.15).

Figure C.16: The total number of SNPs in all haplotype blocks from chromosome 9 to 12

Figure C.17 clearly shows that the different in CIT pattern.

Figure C.18: The total number of SNPs in all haplotype blocks from chromosome 13 to 16

Figure C.19 shows that chromosome 19 has relatively low values and that because it has smaller number of SNPs than its neighboring chromosomes (see Table 3.7 in chapter 3).

Figure C.20: The total number of SNPs in all haplotype blocks from chromosome 17 to 20

Figure C.21 elucidates the lowest value of the total number of SNPs in all blocks in chromosome 22 using CIT with MAF 0.1.

Figure C.22: The total number of SNPs in all haplotype blocks from chromosomes 21 and 22

C. 4 The total length of all blocks (pb)

The SSLD result in chromosome 4 with MAF=0.001 has a distinct pattern (Figure C.19)

Figure C.23: The total length of all blocks (pb) from chromosome 1 to 4

Figure C.20 emphasizes that SSLD has a comparable long block length (bp)

Figure C.24: The total length of all blocks (pb) from chromosome 5 to 8

There's a big drop in the results of FGT in chromosome 11 as shown in Figure C.20

Figure C.25: The total length of all blocks (pb) from chromosome 9 to 12

The FGT has a regular style with MAF (Figure C.22)

Figure C.26: The total length of all blocks (pb) from chromosome 13 to 16

Chromosome 19 has a lower number of SNPs than chromosome 20 and that why there is a drop in its block length.

Figure C.27: The total length of all blocks (pb) from chromosome 17 to 20

The sorter block length is in chromosome 22 by CIT method at MAF =0.1.

Figure C.28: The total length of all blocks (pb) for chromosome 21 and 22

C. 5 Mean number of SNPs in blocks

Figure C.25 shows that the SSLD produces the highest mean number of blocks from chromosome 1 to 4 and Big LD produces the second highest mean number of

Figure C.29: Mean number of SNPs in a block from chromosome 1 to 4

blocks. CIT and FGT result in relatively low mean number of SNPs in a block. The chromosome 6 has the highest mean number of SNPs in a block. The highest value at MAF threshold equals 0.1 by applying SSLD (see Figure C.26).

Figure C.30: Mean number of SNPs in a block from chromosome 5 to 8

In Figure C.27, the pattern is slightly different; the BigLD has the highest mean number of blocks.

Figure C.31: Mean number of SNPs in blocks from chromosome 9 to 12

The same pattern appears in rest of chromosomes (see Figure C.28 , Figure C.29 and Figure C.30).

Figure C.32: Mean number of SNPs in blocks from chromosome 13 to 16

Applying CIT with MAF = 0.001 to chromosome 19 result in the lowest mean number of SNPs in a block

Figure C.33: Mean number of SNPs in blocks from chromosome 17 to 20

In chromosomes 21 and 22 , mean number of SNPs in a block are range from 4 to 5.9 (see figure C.30)

Figure C.34: Mean number of SNPs in blocks from chromosome 21 to 22

C. 6 Mean block length in base pair

The maximum mean block length is in chromosome 4 using SSLD with MAF 0.1 (see Figure C.31).

Figure C.35: Mean block length in bp from chromosome 1 to 4

It seems that the mean block length do not affected by the number of SNPs.

Figure C.36: Mean block length in bp from chromosome 5 to 8

The lower mean block length is in chromosome 11 using FGT with MAF 0.1.

Figure C.37: Mean block length in bp from chromosome 9 to 12

The BigLD has a stable block length and do not affected too much by the data or MAF (Figure C.33 and Figure C.34).

Figure C.38: Mean block length in bp from chromosome 13 to 16

The CIT usually gives a peak mean block length at the middle values of MAF (see Figure C.35 and Figure C.36).

Figure C.39: Mean block length in bp from chromosome 17 to 20.

The results and patterns are convergent the in all chromosomes (see Figure C.36).

Figure C.40 Mean block length in bp for chromosomes 21 and 22

C. 7 The mean r^2 within a block

It is obvious that BigLD has the highest mean r^2 within a block, and in the other methods this value increases with the MAF threshold increases (see Figure C.37).

Figure C. 41: The mean r^2 within blocks from chromosome 1 to 4

On the contrary , the BigLD r^2 within a block decreases with the MAF threshold increases (see Figure C.38).

Figure C.42: The mean r^2 within blocks from chromosome 5 to 8

In chromosome 9, the results are quite different, large drop in the BigLD gives mean r^2 within a block.

Figure C. 43: The mean r^2 within blocks from chromosome 9 to 12

The range mean r^2 within a block is from 2.5 to 4 (Figure 40).

Figure C.44: The mean r^2 within blocks from chromosome 14 to 16

The BigLD is higher than other methods by about 1 except in chromosome 9.

Figure C. 45: The mean r^2 within blocks from chromosome 17 to 20

It seems that the effected of MAF is lower in BigLD than that in the other three methods (see Figure C.42)

Figure C. 46: The mean r^2 within blocks for chromosomes 21 and 22

C. 8 The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks (without singleton blocks)

The SSLD has the lower r^2 between consecutive blocks and the FGT has the highest (see Figure C.43).

Figure C.47: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks from chromosome 1 to 4

The highest r^2 between consecutive blocks is in chromosome 8 by FGT and 0.1 MAF (Figure C.44).

Figure C.48: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks from chromosome 5 to 8

The range of this parameter is from 0.23 to 0.13.

Figure C.49: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks from chromosome 9 to 12

The pattern is approximately the same across the entire data.

Figure C.50: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks from chromosome 13 to 16

The lowest values of mean r^2 between consecutive blocks is in chromosome 19 in general, and the lowest value produced by SSLD and 0.01 MAF (Figure C.47).

Figure C.51: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks from chromosome 17 to 20

The higher is the MAF the higher is the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks.

Figure C.52: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks without singleton blocks from chromosome 21 to 22

C.9 The mean r^2 between consecutive all blocks (with singleton)

Figure C.53: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks from chromosome 1 to 4

In like manner, the mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks increases with the MAF increases (Figure C.49 and Figure C.50).

Figure C.54: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks from chromosome 5 to 8

Figure C.56: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks from chromosome 9 to 12

The range of mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with considering singleton blocks is from 0.2167 to 0.1266.

Figure C.55: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks from chromosome 13 to 16

Figure C.58: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks from chromosome 17 to 20

The highest value of mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks was in chromosome 8 by using FGT and 0.1 MAF threshold. The lowest value was in chromosome 19 by BigLD and 0.01 MAF (see Figure C.54 and Figure C.57).

Figure C.57: The mean r^2 between consecutive blocks with singleton blocks from chromosome 21 to 22

Paper I

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Haplotype Block Partitioning for NARAC Dataset Using Interval Graph Modeling of Clusters Algorithm

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Abstract

5. List of Abbreviations

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Abstract:

Recently, genome-wide association studies (GWAS) depend on haplotype blocks rather than individual Consortium (NARAC) dataset and then compared to confidence interval test (CIT), four-gamete test (FGT), and the solid spine of linkage disequilibrium (SSLD) methods. The dataset is preprocessed, and missing SNPs are imputed. This study demonstrates the distinctions between haplotype block partitioning methods and detects the haplotype blocks for NARAC dataset. The comparative study gives a better understanding of each method and produces different outcomes with different parameters.

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I. Introduction

Studies associate the susceptibility and severity of many diseases of unknown causes with genetic factors [1]. The basic structural units of the DNA are the nucleotides. They consist of four different nitrogenous bases: thymine, cytosine, adenine, and guanine represented by the letters respectively T, C, A, and G [2]. DNA of any two humans is SNPs in each block are correlated, it means that the next SNP can be predicted according to the previous SNPs in the sequence [7], [9]. The measured parameter is known as linkage disequilibrium. Associate the SNPs to the complex diseases but, a more efficient trend is to consider a haplotype blocks in association studies [10]. A haplotype block is a set of closely linked SNPs [9], [10]. Single SNPs approach experiences restricted efficiency when dealing with genome-wide data of complex diseases. Another drawback of single SNPs approach is the epistatic impact when different gene loci contribute to the same phenotype [11]. The appearance of haplotype block partitioning studies begins with the beginning of the current century. The

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Paper II

Pre-processing Steps for Genome-wide High-density NARAC Dataset Facilitates its Haplotype Block PartitioningFatma S. Ibrahim¹, Mohamed N. Saad¹, Ashraf M. Said¹, Hesham F. A. Hamed²¹ Biomedical Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering, Minia University, Egypt² Electrical Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering, Minia University, Egypt**ABSTRACT**

The pre-processing phase is a crucial step to prepare any data for deep considerable analysis. Genome-wide data is considered as big data, dealing with such data is not an easy task and still pose a significant challenge. The genome-wide association study (GWAS) is based on substantial high-density data with high throughput. In this paper, we have illustrated the main pre-processing steps on data from North American Rheumatoid Arthritis Consortium (NARAC) for preparing it for haplotype block partitioning using different methods and with different platforms. The pre-processed data will be applied to imputation, BigLD block partitioning under R and Haploview methods. Our sequence of pre-processing steps includes preparing the characters to be in a form that is suitable for imputation. The next step is recording data in 0,1,2 format to be proper for the BigLD. We were eventually preparing data for Haploview that can provide clear haplotype block partitioning, association analysis, and furthermore.

Keywords: Minor allele frequency, Genome-wide studies, Single nucleotide polymorphism. Haplotype block. Linkage disequilibrium.

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1. Introduction

Genetic variations, especially single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), hold an enormous promise for scientists in diagnosis, treatment, prevention, cure many diseases, and the causes of certain phenotypes [1], [2]. SNPs are the most common genetic variation type [3], [4], and they compose about 90% of all human genetic variation [5]. Each SNP stands for a substitution in a single DNA nucleotide [6], [7]. SNPs are characterized by having at least a frequency of 1% of an allele in a population [1]. Commonly, SNPs do not occur within genes and found in non-coding regions [8], [9]; yet how they contribute to disorders and phenotypes is unknown. Several research disciplines are based on SNPs including; large-scale population-based genetic association studies [10], family-based disease inheritance tracking, gene mapping [11], crop genetics [12] pharmacogenetic applications [14] and, etc. [13]. SNPs act as a biomarker, i.e., identifier for traits and diseases, therefore work very well in studies that are non-hypothesis driven [15], [16]. In the last years, SNPs serve as a powerful tool prominently in complex disease association studies and uncovered the risk loci [10], [17]–[20]. Since SNPs are inherited together through generations, SNPs at different loci are linked to each other, and this property of the association is called linkage disequilibrium (LD) [21]–[23]. As a consequence of the recombination events, the association is cut and form block-like structures through the genome sequence called haplotype blocks [24], [25]. Likewise, haplotype blocks are treated as biomarkers and are often preferred over

Arabic summary

تحتوي الرسالة على سبعة فصول نوجزها فيما يلي:

الفصل الأول: المقدمة، الخلفية والتمهيد

تناول هذا الفصل المقدمة وخلفية عن المعلوماتية الحيوية وصولاً الى الارتباط بين اشكال نيوكليوتيدات المتعددة وكتل النمط الفردي وتطبيقاته وأهميته وخاصة في الأمراض كالتهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي. وبعدها تناولت الباحثة الدوافع وراء الرسالة وهدف الرسالة ثم مكونات الرسالة.

الفصل الثاني: مراجعة الدراسات السابقة

قدم هذا الفصل خلفية عامة عن أهم المشاريع التي أطلقت في مجال الجينوم والتي كانت تهتم بالاختلافات الجينية. كما تم تقديم مراجعة الدراسات السابقة بالتسلسل الزمني لها و تم عرض الطرق والبرامج التي استخدمت في تقسيم كتل النمط الفردي منذ اكتشافها في 2001 وحتى عام 2020.

الفصل الثالث: وصف البيانات واستكشافها

في هذا الفصل تم عرض توصيف مفصل عن البيانات المستخدمة وما تم حسابه من النسبة المئوية للبيانات المفقودة. وعُرض فيه باستفاضة الإجراءات الاستكشافية التي تمت لفهم طبيعة البيانات ومنها نسبة تردد الأليل طفيف في البيانات. حيث تم تقسيم البيانات بناء على ذلك لأربعة أقسام والبحث في كل قسم على دورها الجيني من حيث مكان كل SNP. وألحق مرفق (أ) الذي حوى ما تم الوصول اليه لكل قسم من البيانات.

الفصل الرابع: المعالجة المسبقة للبيانات وضبط الجودة

تناول هذا الفصل عمليات المعالجة المسبقة وعملية احتساب البيانات المفقودة وتم عرض الخطوات في جداول وأشكال توضيحية.

الفصل الخامس: الطرق المقترحة لتقسيم كتلة النمط الفردي

قُدم في هذا الفصل الطرق التي تم اعتمادتها في تقسيم كتل النمط الفردي. ومخطط تفصيلي بالخطوات التي اتبعتها. وشرحت كل طريقة على حدة. وتم عرض النتائج بالتفصيل في مرفق (ب) كجداول وفي مرفق (ج) الذي حوى الرسوم البيانية.

الفصل السادس: النتائج ومناقشة

في هذا الفصل تم مناقشة النتائج ومقارنتها. والنتائج المميزة لكل طريقة من الطرق المستخدمة ودور تردد الأليل طفيف على النتائج. وتم تقييم النتائج بناء على معايير منها: العدد الكلي لكتل النمط الفردي، العدد الكلي لكتل النمط الفردي مع اعتبار أشكال النيوكليونات ككتل منفصلة، العدد الكلي للأشكال النيوكليونات المتعددة في كل كتل النمط الفردي، الطول الكلي لكتل النمط الفردي، متوسط عدد أشكال النيوكليونات المتعددة في كتل النمط الفردي، متوسط عدد طول كتل النمط الفردي بالعدد زوج القواعد النيتروجينية، متوسط χ^2 في كتل النمط الفردي، متوسط χ^2 بين كتل النمط الفردي، متوسط χ^2 بين كتل النمط الفردي مع اعتبار أشكال النيوكليونات المتعددة البينية ككتل منفصلة، نسبة التشابه ووقت العمليات الحسابية.

الفصل السابع: الخلاصة والاعتبارات المستقبلية

عرض هذا الفصل مجموعة من الاستنتاجات وكذلك بعض النقاط الخاصة بإجراء بعض البحوث المستقبلية.

ملخص الرسالة

تعد كتل النمط الفردي خاصة مهمة في الربط بين الامراض والعوامل الجينية خاصة في تقليص عدد اشكال نيوكليوتيدات المتعددة. كما يعتبر توصيف والمعالجة المسبقة خطوة هامة لإعداد أي بيانات لتحليل دقيق وعميق. وتعد البيانات على مستوى الجينوم -الذي يشمل كل المحتوى الوراثي- بيانات هائلة ولذلك فإن التعامل معها ليس بالمهمة السهلة ولا يزال يمثل تحديًا كبيرًا للباحثين. وتعتمد دراسة الارتباط على مستوى الجينوم GWAS على تلك البيانات عالية الكثافة وذات الإنتاجية الوفيرة. في هذا البحث قمنا أولاً بعمل توصيف كامل لبيانات من اتحاد أمريكا الشمالية لالتهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي (NARAC). وصفنا البيانات بشكل عام من خلال عرض عدد الإناث والذكور في كل من الحالات المصابة والسليمة. وحساب قيمة تردد الأليل الطفيف (MAF) minor allele frequency لكل من أشكال النيوكليوتيدات المفردة -single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP). وقمنا بتقسيم SNP طبقاً لتردد الأليل الطفيف MAF الى أربعة اقسام من حيث ندرة من أشكال النيوكليوتيدات المفردة SNP. تساعد نتائج التحليل الوصفي الباحثين في الحصول على نظرة عامة على البيانات وتوفير فهم دقيق وعميق الحدسي لبيانات جينية من هذا النوع. كما قمنا بتوضيح خطوات المعالجة المسبقة الرئيسية للبيانات والتي من أهمها إعادة تشكيل البيانات لتناسب كل طريقة من طرق التقسيم وحتى تتلاءم مع المنصات المختلفة. وقمنا بعملية احتساب البيانات المفقودة Imputation من ثم إعدادها وتقسيمها الى كتل النمط الفردي Haplotype blocks باستخدام طرق ومنصات مختلفة. وقد تم تطبيق البيانات المعالجة مسبقاً وطريقة BigLD لتقسيم كتلة النمط الفردي باستخدام لغة البرمجة R وكذلك تم اعتماد ثلاث طرق أخرى باستخدام منصة Haploview واستخدمنا مع كل منهم خمس عتبات مختلفة من تردد أليل طفيف MAF وعليه قمنا بتحديد النمط العام لكل طريقة ودور تردد أليل طفيف MAF في عملية تقسيم كتل النمط الفردي. وأظهرت النتائج تباين كبير في نتائج كل طريقة وكل عتبة. كما نتج عن طريقة BigLD أعلى ارتباط في الكتل وأقلها عددًا وكذلك أقل من حيث الوقت بثمانية اضعاف من الطرق الأخرى. كما أظهرت النتائج لعشرة مقاييس مختلفة استخدمت لتقييم النتائج دور MAF في تقسيم كتل النمط الفردي. وعليه فإن هذا البحث يعطي منظور واضح لأكثر الطرق شيوعاً في تقسيم كتل النمط الفردي وأفضلها من حيث الوقت والنتائج. كما يرسم صورة واضحة لتأثير تردد الأليل طفيف.

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تنفيذ خوارزميات تحليل الارتباط الجيني لبيانات التهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي بناء على كتل النمط الفردي

رسالة

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